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Multi-Higgs production in the Higgs Effective Field Theory

VBS + h in the Equivalence–Theorem limit via field
redefinitions: constraints on Higgs–gauge couplings

Relatori:

Prof. Juan José SANZ-CILLERO

Prof. Luca GIRLANDA

Laureanda:

Alessia NASONI

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Abstract

Present experimental data are consistent with the Standard Model (SM) Higgs mechanism for electroweak symmetry breaking (EWSB); yet its underlying dynamics of EWSB —therefore, the exact nature of the Higgs itself —remains open. Within experimental uncertainties, deviations from the SM predictions are possible, and can be captured in the model-independent framework provided by Effective Field Theories (EFTs). At energies $m_W \ll \sqrt{s} \ll \Lambda$, the Equivalence Theorem (ET) allows to probe the scalar sector — namely, the Higgs and the Nambu-Goldstone modes — through longitudinal vector-boson scattering (VBS), $V_L V_L$. In particular, VBS provides access to the strengths of $hV_L V_L$ and $hhV_L V_L$ interactions. In the Higgs Effective Field Theory (HEFT), these are controlled, respectively, by parameters a_1 and a_2 ($a_1 = 2$, $a_2 = 1$ in the SM). The parameter a_1 is relatively well constrained, whereas bounds on a_2 are looser, inferred mostly from double-Higgs VBS ($V_L V_L \rightarrow hh$). In this work, we study how the so-far unexploited process $V_L V_L \rightarrow V_L V_L h$ can sharpen constraints on (a_1, a_2) . Focusing on the charged channel $W_L^+ W_L^- \rightarrow Z_L Z_L h$, we compute the leading-order (LO) tree-level amplitude using the ET, treating all external states as massless and neglecting $\mathcal{O}(m_W/\sqrt{s})$ effects; transverse gauge interactions and Yukawas are switched off so that the scalar sector can be treated in isolation. The resulting amplitude is controlled by a definite combination of a_1 and a_2 . We obtain the result in two equivalent ways: (i) from the canonical HEFT Lagrangian and (ii) after applying nonlinear field redefinitions that remove vertices involving three fields from the original Lagrangian and reduce to one operator only the relevant contribution to the process in consideration. In the field-redefined basis, the set of tree-level Feynman diagrams collapses to a single contact diagram. Subsequently, we derive the cross-section and compare the result with the Standard Model Effec-

tive Theory (SMEFT) prediction. Within SMEFT, correlations (which are absent in HEFT) among couplings make the channel more strongly suppressed than in HEFT. Finally, we perform a toy joint analysis that combines $V_L V_L \rightarrow hh$, external knowledge of a_1 , and two different scenarios for the uncertainty on $V_L V_L \rightarrow V_L V_L h$. The obtained 68% confidence regions suggest that even conservative improvements on this process could lead to a reduction of the allowed (a_1, a_2) region.

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Introduction

In recent years, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiment has consolidated the success of the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics as an accurate description of fundamental interactions [1]. The discovery of a 125 GeV “Higgs” scalar [2, 3, 4] and the measurement of its dominant interactions confirmed the “Higgs mechanism” as an appropriate description, within the current experimental and theoretical uncertainties, of electroweak (EW) symmetry breaking (EWSB) [5, 6, 7, 8].

Yet, the dynamics underlying the EWSB, and therefore the exact nature of the Higgs boson itself, is still an open quest [9]. To improve our understanding we need to study the dynamics of the scalar sector as a whole, targeting at once the Higgs boson and the Nambu-Goldstone states. At high energies, by virtue of the Equivalence Theorem (ET) [10], these can be accessed in the form of longitudinally polarized W and Z bosons, which we denote W_L^\pm and Z_L , or V_L collectively.

In particular, longitudinally polarized vector boson scattering (VBS) processes bear a certain relevance at hadron colliders [11]: since they are tightly connected with EWSB, their identification and measurement provide a probe of the spontaneous symmetry breaking mechanism, complementing other Higgs-related measurements.

In the SM, specific relations between the couplings $V_L V_L h$ and $V_L V_L h h$ enforce exact cancellations of the VBS leading high-energy growth, so that $V_L V_L$ amplitudes are suppressed and perturbative unitarity is preserved. This would no longer be the case if those relations were slightly violated. The correct language to parameterize and test such deviations in a UV model-independent way is provided by Effective Field Theories (EFTs).

Two EFTs stand out as powerful predictive frameworks: the Standard Model

Effective Field Theory (SMEFT), where EWSB is realized linearly, with the Higgs embedded in a $SU_L(2)$ doublet, and the Higgs Effective Field Theory (HEFT), where EWSB is realized nonlinearly and the Higgs is a $SU(2)_L$ singlet separated from the triplet of the Nambu-Goldstone bosons [9, 12].

In HEFT, the strength of the interaction vertices $V_L V_L h$ and $V_L V_L hh$ is controlled by the two parameters a_1 and a_2 , respectively. In the SM, $a_1 = 2$ and $a_2 = 1$. While a_1 is relatively well known experimentally, bounds on a_2 are still loose but improving [13, 14], mainly through studies of $V_L V_L \rightarrow hh$.

At leading order (LO), at energy scales where the ET is in force and in the limit where all the external particles involved are massless, the VBS processes $V_L V_L \rightarrow hh$ and $V_L V_L \rightarrow V_L V_L h$ are controlled by combinations of a_1 and a_2 ; at SM values exact cancellations happen, resulting in the complete suppression of the amplitudes.

In this thesis, we focus on the charged VBS process $W_L^+ W_L^- \rightarrow Z_L Z_L h$ at center-of-mass energies (\sqrt{s}) well above the EW scale $\sim m_W$ and below the cutoff for new physics $\sim \Lambda$, i.e. $m_W \ll \sqrt{s} \ll \Lambda$. We work in the approximation of the ET, neglecting $\mathcal{O}(m_W/\sqrt{s})$ effects and higher, in the limit where all the states involved are massless; furthermore, we neglect Yukawa couplings and transverse gauge interactions. We employ a convenient parametrization for the HEFT Lagrangian, calculate the amplitude and show how the computation can be simplified through field redefinitions; we compute the cross-section and contrast the HEFT predictions with the linear-realization (SMEFT) benchmark, which enforces correlations among the couplings a_1, a_2 that do not hold in HEFT. Finally, we assess the prospective impact of this channel on (a_1, a_2) when combined with $V_L V_L \rightarrow hh$ and external information on a_1 .

No experimental datasets are used in this study: a realistic statistical analysis is outside our scope. Next-to-leading-order (NLO) corrections are required to sharpen the predictions. NLO results for $V_L V_L \rightarrow hh$ and $V_L V_L \rightarrow hhh$ are presented in Ref. [15], which is complementary to this work.

Conventions

We use the “mostly minus” Minkowski metric $\eta_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(1, -1, -1, -1)$. Lorentz indices are raised or lowered with $\eta_{\mu\nu}$. We write $a \cdot b \equiv a_\mu b^\mu$. The totally antisymmetric Levi-Civita tensor is normalized as $\epsilon^{123} = +1$.

For SU(2) we take generators $T^i = \sigma^i/2$ with $\text{Tr}(T^i T^j) = \frac{1}{2} \delta^{ij}$ and where σ^i , $i = 1, 2, 3$, are the Pauli matrices satisfying $[\sigma^i, \sigma^j] = 2i\epsilon^{ijk}\sigma^k$ and $\sigma^i \sigma^j = \delta^{ij} \mathbf{1} + i\epsilon^{ijk}\sigma^k$.

For SU(3)_c, the generators of the fundamental representation are the Gell-Mann matrices $\frac{1}{2}\lambda^a$ ($a = 1, 2, \dots, 8$). They are hermitian, traceless, and satisfy the commutation relations $[\frac{\lambda^a}{2}, \frac{\lambda^b}{2}] = if^{abc}\frac{\lambda^c}{2}$, where f^{abc} are the real and totally antisymmetric SU(3)_c structure constants.

Dirac matrices satisfy $\{\gamma^\mu, \gamma^\nu\} = 2\eta^{\mu\nu}$, $\gamma^5 = i\gamma^0\gamma^1\gamma^2\gamma^3$, and $\not{a} \equiv \gamma^\mu a_\mu$. Left and right projectors are defined as $P_{L,R} \equiv (1 \mp \gamma^5)/2$.

We work in natural units (nu), where $\hbar = 1$ and $c = 1$. Thus, every quantity carries dimensions of a power of energy. We take the electronvolt (eV) as unit of energy. Cross-sections are expressed in femtobarns (fb). For reference,

$$\begin{aligned} \hbar &= 6.582 \times 10^{-22} \text{ MeV s}, & (\hbar c)^2 &= 0.3894 \text{ GeV}^2 \text{ mb}, \\ \hbar c &= 1.973 \times 10^{-13} \text{ MeV m}, & 1 \text{ fb} &= 2.56819 \times 10^{-6} \text{ TeV}^{-2}. \end{aligned}$$

The Standard Model of Particle Physics

Particle physics aims to describe the basic building blocks of matter and the fundamental forces that govern their interactions. As experimental and theoretical progress has been made, our understanding of which particles can be considered elementary has changed over time. The currently accepted theoretical framework to describe fundamental particles and their strong, weak, and electromagnetic interactions is provided by the Standard Model, where elementary particles and their associated fields are classified according to their spin and interaction properties.

An essential feature of the SM is that it is a *gauge* theory. Gauge invariance is a powerful tool to determine the dynamics of the electroweak and strong forces: these are introduced as gauge interactions, and described in terms of spin-1 gauge fields. Furthermore, the SM is a *renormalizable* quantum field theory: this ensures ultraviolet divergences can be absorbed into a finite set of parameters, providing predictiveness at accessible energies.

The full SM symmetry group is $SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$. The high-energy $U(1)$ symmetry is called hypercharge and is denoted $U(1)_Y$, while the low-energy $U(1)$, associated with electromagnetism, is denoted $U(1)_{EM}$. The strong interaction is described by the color $SU(3)_c$ group, and is mediated by eight massless gluons. The electromagnetic and weak interactions, unified by the electroweak $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ group [16, 17], are mediated by four gauge bosons: the weak force is mediated by the charged W^\pm and the neutral Z boson, with masses $M_W = 80.4 \text{ GeV}$ and $M_Z = 91.2 \text{ GeV}$, while the electromagnetic force is mediated by the massless photon γ . The photon is a linear combination of the hypercharge gauge boson B_μ and the neutral $SU(2)$ boson W_μ^3 . The spin 1/2 (fermionic) matter content of the model is constituted by leptons and quarks, and their corresponding antiparticles.

The masses of the gauge bosons and fermions are generated, in the SM, by a mass generation mechanism, the Higgs mechanism [7, 6, 8, 5], based on the symmetry breaking pattern $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y \rightarrow U(1)_{EM}$.

2.1 Matter fields and their transformation properties

In the SM, particles are organized in a three-fold family structure, or in three generations, as can be seen in Table 2.1:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \nu_e & u \\ e^- & d \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \nu_\mu & c \\ \mu^- & s \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \nu_\tau & t \\ \tau^- & b \end{bmatrix}; \quad (2.1)$$

the corresponding antiparticles are organized similarly, with same mass and opposite charges. Each different type of quark or lepton is called *flavour*.

We adopt the notation $\mathcal{E} = (e^-, \mu^-, \tau^-)$ for the lepton fields (called electron, muon, tau leptons), all with electric charge $Q = -1$ in units of the elementary charge, and, correspondingly, $\mathcal{N} = (\nu_e, \nu_\mu, \nu_\tau)$ for the electrically neutral lepton fields (called electronic neutrino, muonic neutrino, tauonic neutrino), all with charge $Q = 0$.

Similarly, for quarks we adopt the notation $\mathcal{U}^\alpha = (u^\alpha, c^\alpha, t^\alpha)$ for the up-type quarks (up, charm, top), with electric charge $Q = 2/3$, and $\mathcal{D}^\alpha = (d^\alpha, s^\alpha, b^\alpha)$ for the down-type quarks (down, strange, bottom), with electric charge $Q = -1/3$. The index α indicates the color degree of freedom, which is a property of quarks only. It runs from 1 to 3, corresponding to the three colors of QCD: red, green, and blue.

Interactions between particles carrying color charge (i.e. quarks and gluons) are described by Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD), the $SU(3)_c$ gauge theory of the strong interaction.

Under the $SU(2)_L$ group left-handed fermions transform as doublets, while right-handed fermions are singlets; no right-handed neutrinos have ever been

observed, and they are not included in the SM. Then, each family can be written

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{N} & \mathcal{U}^\alpha \\ \mathcal{E} & \mathcal{D}^\alpha \end{bmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{N} \\ \mathcal{E} \end{pmatrix}_L, \quad \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{U}^\alpha \\ \mathcal{D}^\alpha \end{pmatrix}_L, \quad \mathcal{E}_R, \quad \mathcal{U}^\alpha_R, \quad \mathcal{D}^\alpha_R. \quad (2.2)$$

Electrically charged leptons and quarks interact via electromagnetic and weak forces, while left-handed neutrinos interact only via the weak force. Additionally, all leptons are color singlets.

We introduce the following notation. We denote q_f^α a quark of flavour f and color α , where $f = u, d, c, s, t, b$ is the quark flavour, transforming in the fundamental representation of color $SU(3)_c$. In a vectorial fashion, $q_f^T = (q_f^1, q_f^2, q_f^3)$.

For quark and lepton doublets, we introduce the notation

$$\mathcal{Q} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{U} \\ \mathcal{D} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{L} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{N} \\ \mathcal{E} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.3)$$

motivated by the fact that the left components, $\mathcal{Q}_L \equiv P_L \mathcal{Q}$ and $\mathcal{L}_L \equiv P_L \mathcal{L}$, transform as $SU(2)_L$ doublets, where $P_L \equiv (1 - \gamma_5)/2$ denotes the projector on the left chirality, and $P_R \equiv (1 + \gamma_5)/2$ denotes the projector on the right chirality.

Finally, there is the family of spin-0 bosons, described, in the SM, by a doublet field of self-interacting scalar fields, which gives rise to the symmetry breaking sector (SBS) of the model. The family is populated by the Higgs boson particle; its prediction ([5, 7, 6, 8]) and subsequent discovery at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) in 2012 [4, 2, 3], consistent with EW symmetry breaking via the Higgs mechanism, is one of the most celebrated achievements of the SM. The SBS is needed to provide a mechanism for the generation of mass for the gauge bosons and fermions.

Notation		Generation		
		I	II	III
\mathcal{L}	\mathcal{E}	e^-	μ^-	τ^-
	\mathcal{N}	ν_e	ν_μ	ν_τ
\mathcal{Q}	\mathcal{U}	u^α	c^α	t^α
	\mathcal{D}	d^α	s^α	b^α

Table 2.1: Fermionic content of the Standard Model.

An arbitrary local $SU(3)_c$ transformation in color space of a quark field reads

$$q_f^\alpha \longrightarrow (q_f^\alpha)' = U_c^{\alpha\beta} q_f^\beta, \quad (2.4)$$

where U_c is a $SU(3)_c$ 3×3 unitary (i.e., $U_c^\dagger U_c = 1$) and unimodular (i.e., $\det U_c = 1$) matrix. In exponential form,

$$U_c = \exp \left\{ i \frac{\lambda^a}{2} \theta_c^a(x) \right\}, \quad (2.5)$$

where $\frac{1}{2}\lambda^a$ ($a = 1, 2, \dots, 8$) denote the Gell-Mann matrices, which are the generators of the fundamental representation of the $SU(3)_c$ algebra, and $\theta_c^a(x)$ are the arbitrary parameters of the local transformation, depending on the spacetime coordinate x ; a sum over repeated colour indices is understood. The matrices λ^a are Hermitian and traceless, and satisfy the commutation relations

$$\left[\frac{\lambda^a}{2}, \frac{\lambda^b}{2} \right] = i f^{abc} \frac{\lambda^c}{2}, \quad (2.6)$$

where f^{abc} are the real and totally antisymmetric $SU(3)_c$ structure constants.

For infinitesimal values of $\theta_c^a(x)$, the above color gauge transformation of Eq. (2.4) reads

$$q^\alpha \rightarrow q^\alpha - i \theta_c^a(x) \frac{\lambda_{\alpha\beta}^a}{2} q^\beta. \quad (2.7)$$

Under a transformation of the EW gauge group $G_{EW} \equiv SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$, the left-handed doublet fermionic fields transform as

$$\mathcal{L}_L \rightarrow \exp(i y_L^{\mathcal{L}} \beta) U_L \mathcal{L}_L, \quad \mathcal{Q}_L \rightarrow \exp(i y_L^{\mathcal{Q}} \beta) U_L \mathcal{Q}_L, \quad (2.8)$$

while the right-handed singlets transform as

$$\mathcal{U}_R \rightarrow \exp(i y_R^{\mathcal{U}} \beta) \mathcal{U}_R, \quad \mathcal{E}_R \rightarrow \exp(i y_R^{\mathcal{E}} \beta) \mathcal{E}_R, \quad \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \exp(i y_R^{\mathcal{D}} \beta) \mathcal{D}_R. \quad (2.9)$$

The parameters y_i are called hypercharges, and are free parameters of the SM. Here, U_L is a unitary and unimodular matrix denoting a $SU(2)_L$ transformation,

and can be written as

$$U_L = \exp \left\{ i\theta_L^i(x) \frac{\sigma^i}{2} \right\}, \quad (i = 1, 2, 3) \quad (2.10)$$

and acts only on the left-handed doublets \mathcal{L}_L and \mathcal{Q}_L . The parameters $\theta_L^i(x)$ are the infinitesimal parameters of the local $SU(2)_L$ transformation, which depend on the spacetime coordinate x . The σ^i are the Pauli matrices, which are the generators of the fundamental representation of $SU(2)_L$, and satisfy the commutation relations

$$\left[\frac{\sigma^i}{2}, \frac{\sigma^j}{2} \right] = i\epsilon^{ijk} \frac{\sigma^k}{2}, \quad (2.11)$$

where ϵ^{ijk} are the totally antisymmetric structure constants of $SU(2)_L$. A general $U(1)_Y$ transformation of the fermionic fields can be written as

$$U_Y(\beta) = \exp(i\beta(x)Y) \quad (2.12)$$

where Y is the hypercharge operator, and $\beta(x)$ is the infinitesimal parameter of the local $U(1)_Y$ transformation, which depends on the spacetime coordinate x .

Under an infinitesimal $SU(2)_L$ transformation, the doublets \mathcal{L}_L and \mathcal{Q}_L transform as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &\rightarrow \mathcal{L} + i\theta_L^i(x) T^i P_L \mathcal{L}, \\ \mathcal{Q} &\rightarrow \mathcal{Q} + i\theta_L^i(x) T^i P_L \mathcal{Q}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

Under a $U(1)_Y$ transformation, the fermionic fields transform as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &\rightarrow \mathcal{L} + i\beta(x) \left(y_L^{\mathcal{L}} P_L + \begin{pmatrix} y_R^{\mathcal{N}} & 0 \\ 0 & y_R^{\mathcal{E}} \end{pmatrix} P_R \right) \mathcal{L}, \\ \mathcal{Q} &\rightarrow \mathcal{Q} + i\beta(x) \left(y_L^{\mathcal{Q}} P_L + \begin{pmatrix} y_R^{\mathcal{M}} & 0 \\ 0 & y_R^{\mathcal{D}} \end{pmatrix} P_R \right) \mathcal{Q}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

The hypercharge, Y , altogether with the third weak isospin component $T_3 \equiv \sigma^3/2$ (which is $1/2$ for the upper components of the EW doublets, and $-1/2$ for the lower components), determine the electric charge Q of a given fermionic field ψ through the relation $Q = T_3 + Y$. Their values are assigned to guarantee the

	\mathcal{U}_R	\mathcal{U}_L	\mathcal{D}_R	\mathcal{D}_L	\mathcal{N}_L	\mathcal{E}_R	\mathcal{E}_L
y	2/3	1/6	-1/3	1/6	-1/2	-1	-1/2
T_3	0	1/2	0	-1/2	1/2	0	-1/2
Q	2/3	2/3	-1/3	-1/3	0	-1	-1

Table 2.2: Hypercharge assignments, values of T_3 , and electric charges $Q = Y + T_3$ in the SM. See Section 2.2.2.

absence of gauge and gravitational anomalies in the theory, and they are given in Table 2.2.

2.2 $SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ Lagrangian

The $SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ invariant Lagrangian describing the matter and gauge sectors of the SM, built from the gauge principle, is given by the sum of the two terms below:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{YM}} = -\frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} G_{\mu\nu} G^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} W_{\mu\nu} W^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{4} B_{\mu\nu} B^{\mu\nu}, \quad (2.15)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_m = i\bar{Q}\not{D}^{\mathcal{Q}}Q + i\bar{\mathcal{L}}\not{D}^{\mathcal{L}}\mathcal{L}. \quad (2.16)$$

Here, \mathcal{L}_{YM} in Eq. (2.15) contains the kinetic terms for the gauge fields and their self-interactions; the gauge fields appear as a consequence of the gauge principle, to guarantee the invariance of the Lagrangian under local $SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ transformations. The SM fermionic matter content is described by \mathcal{L}_m in Eq. (2.16), where the Dirac operators acting on Q and \mathcal{L} fermions are defined in terms of the covariant derivatives as

$$\not{D}^{\mathcal{Q}} \equiv \gamma^\mu D_\mu^{\mathcal{Q}} = \gamma^\mu \left[\partial_\mu - ig_s G_\mu - ig W_\mu P_L + ig' (Y_L^{\mathcal{Q}} P_L + Y_R^{\mathcal{Q}} P_R) B_\mu \right], \quad (2.17)$$

$$\not{D}^{\mathcal{L}} \equiv \gamma^\mu D_\mu^{\mathcal{L}} = \gamma^\mu \left[\partial_\mu - ig W_\mu P_L + ig' (Y_L^{\mathcal{L}} P_L + Y_R^{\mathcal{L}} P_R) B_\mu \right]. \quad (2.18)$$

In Eqs. (2.17) and (2.18), $Y_{L,R}^{(\mathcal{L},\mathcal{Q})}$ denotes the hypercharge matrices,

$$Y_{L,R}^{\mathcal{Q},\mathcal{L}} = \begin{pmatrix} y_{L,R}^{\mathcal{U},\mathcal{N}} & 0 \\ 0 & y_{L,R}^{\mathcal{D},\mathcal{E}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.19)$$

The covariant derivatives are defined so that $\mathcal{L}_{\text{YM}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{m}}$ is invariant under a local $\text{SU}(3)_{\text{c}} \times \text{SU}(2)_{\text{L}} \times \text{U}(1)_{\text{Y}}$ transformation. Notably, the covariant derivatives incorporate the gauge fields and their interactions with the fermionic fields; the universality of the quark and lepton interactions arising from \mathcal{L}_{m} is a direct consequence of the assumed gauge symmetry.

In Eq. (2.17), we denote $G_{\mu} = G_{\mu}^a \lambda^a / 2$ the gluon matrix field in $\text{SU}(3)_{\text{c}}$ color space,¹ where G_{μ}^a are the gluon fields, $a = 1, \dots, 8$, and λ^a the Gell-Mann matrices. We denote g_s the strong coupling; all colour-triplet quark flavours couple to the gluon fields with g_s . In Eq. (2.15), $G_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu}^a \lambda^a / 2$, $a = 1, \dots, 8$, is the field strength tensor of the gluon fields,

$$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \partial_{\mu} G_{\nu} - \partial_{\nu} G_{\mu} - ig_s [G_{\mu}, G_{\nu}]; \quad (2.20)$$

which gives rise to the triple and quartic self-interactions of the gluon fields, of strengths g_s and g_s^2 respectively; this fact is a consequence of the non-abelian nature of the $\text{SU}(3)_{\text{c}}$ gauge group.

In Eqs. (2.17) and (2.18), the electroweak $\text{SU}(2)_{\text{L}}$ gauge fields are $W_{\mu} = W_{\mu}^i T^i$ ². G is the weak coupling, and the weak field strength (in Eq. (2.15)) is $W_{\mu\nu} = W_{\mu\nu}^i T^i$, with $i = 1, 2, 3$:

$$W_{\mu\nu} = \partial_{\mu} W_{\nu} - \partial_{\nu} W_{\mu} - ig [W_{\mu}, W_{\nu}]; \quad (2.21)$$

which yields, in \mathcal{L}_{YM} , cubic and quartic self-interactions among the weak gauge fields.

Finally, B_{μ} in Eqs. (2.17) and (2.18) denotes the $\text{U}(1)_{\text{Y}}$ gauge field; g' is the weak hypercharge coupling; $B_{\mu\nu}$ in Eq. (2.15) is the corresponding field strength

¹Matrix subindices are understood, with α, β being the $\text{SU}(3)_{\text{c}}$ color indices, and $a = 1, \dots, 8$ being the $\text{SU}(3)_{\text{c}}$ gauge group indices:

$$[G^{\mu}(x)]_{\alpha\beta} \equiv \left(\frac{\lambda^a}{2} \right)_{\alpha\beta} G_{\mu}^a(x).$$

²Again, matrix subindices are understood, with α, β being the $\text{SU}(2)_{\text{L}}$ doublet indices, and $i = 1, 2, 3$ being the $\text{SU}(2)_{\text{L}}$ gauge group indices:

$$[W^{\mu}(x)]_{\alpha\beta} \equiv (T^i)_{\alpha\beta} W_{\mu}^i(x).$$

tensor:

$$B_{\mu\nu} \equiv \partial_\mu B_\nu - \partial_\nu B_\mu. \quad (2.22)$$

In the next subsection we examine how gauge fields and related quantities transform under local $G_{\text{SM}} \equiv \text{SU}(3)_c \times \text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{U}(1)_Y$ transformations to ensure the invariance of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{YM}} + \mathcal{L}_m$ (Eqs. (2.15) and (2.16)).

2.2.1 $\text{SU}(3)_c \times \text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{U}(1)_Y$ invariance

To ensure invariance under the local gauge transformations defined in Eqs. (2.5), (2.10), and (2.12), the gauge fields must transform as follows:

$$G_\mu \rightarrow U_c G_\mu U_c^{-1} - \frac{1}{g_s} (\partial_\mu U_c) U_c^{-1} \quad (2.23)$$

$$W_\mu \rightarrow U_L W_\mu U_L^{-1} - \frac{1}{g} (\partial_\mu U_L) U_L^{-1} \quad (2.24)$$

$$B_\mu \rightarrow B_\mu + \frac{1}{g'} (\partial_\mu U_Y) U_Y^{-1}, \quad (2.25)$$

where U_c , U_L , U_Y are defined in Eqs. (2.5), (2.10), (2.12) respectively. The corresponding infinitesimal transformations read

$$G_\mu^a \rightarrow G_\mu^a - \frac{1}{g_s} \partial_\mu \theta_c^a(x) - f^{abc} \theta_c^b(x) G_\mu^c, \quad a = 1 \dots 8 \quad (2.26)$$

$$W_\mu^a \rightarrow W_\mu^a - \frac{1}{g} \partial_\mu \theta_L^a(x) - \epsilon^{abc} \theta_L^b(x) W_\mu^c, \quad a = 1 \dots 3 \quad (2.27)$$

$$B_\mu \rightarrow B_\mu + \frac{1}{g'} \partial_\mu \beta(x). \quad (2.28)$$

The above transformation properties ensure that the covariant derivatives $D_\mu^\mathcal{Q}$ and $D_\mu^\mathcal{L}$ (Eqs. (2.17), (2.18)), under a local transformation $U(\theta_c^a(x), \theta_L^i(x), \beta(x)) \in G_{\text{SM}}$, transform as

$$D_\mu^{\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{L}} \xrightarrow{G_{\text{SM}}} (D_\mu^{\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{L}})' = U D_\mu^{\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{L}} U^\dagger, \quad (2.29)$$

ensuring that the fermionic Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_m (Eq. (2.16)) is invariant under local G_{SM} transformations.

The field strength tensors $G_{\mu\nu}$ and $W_{\mu\nu}$ transform covariantly under $\text{SU}(3)_c$ and $\text{SU}(2)_L$ transformations, respectively, while the $\text{U}(1)_Y$ field strength tensor

$B_{\mu\nu}$ is invariant under $U(1)_Y$ transformations:

$$G_{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{SU(3)_c} U_c G_{\mu\nu} U_c^\dagger, \quad (2.30)$$

$$W_{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{SU(2)_L} U_L W_{\mu\nu} U_L^\dagger, \quad (2.31)$$

$$B_{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{U(1)_Y} B_{\mu\nu}, \quad (2.32)$$

where U_c and U_Y are given in Eqs. (2.5) and (2.10) respectively. Then, each of the kinetic terms in the Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_{YM} is invariant under local G_{SM} . The invariance of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{YM}} + \mathcal{L}_m$ is ensured.

2.2.2 Physical electroweak gauge fields

In nature, we do not directly observe the $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ gauge fields $W_\mu^1, W_\mu^2, W_\mu^3, B_\mu$, but linear combinations with well-defined electric charge Q : two electrically neutral bosons, the photon A_μ and the Z boson Z_μ , and two electrically charged W bosons, W_μ^+ and W_μ^- .

The electric charge operator Q is defined as $Q = T_3 + Y$, and acts like

$$Q \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{N} \\ \mathcal{E} \end{pmatrix}_L = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} + y_L^{\mathcal{N}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} + y_L^{\mathcal{E}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{N} \\ \mathcal{E} \end{pmatrix}_L, \quad Q\mathcal{E}_R = Y\mathcal{E}_R, \quad (2.33)$$

$$Q \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{U} \\ \mathcal{D} \end{pmatrix}_L = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} + y_L^{\mathcal{U}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} + y_L^{\mathcal{D}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{U} \\ \mathcal{D} \end{pmatrix}_L, \quad Q\mathcal{U}_R = Y\mathcal{U}_R, \quad Q\mathcal{D}_R = Y\mathcal{D}_R, \quad (2.34)$$

without distinguishing between left and right-handed components (See Table 2.2). Expanding $W_\mu = W_\mu^i T^i$ as

$$W_\mu = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} W_\mu^3 & \sqrt{2}(W^1 - iW^2) \\ \sqrt{2}(W^1 + iW^2) & -W_\mu^3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.35)$$

we identify $W^\pm = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(W^1 \mp iW^2)$ as the charged W^+ and W^- bosons, which carry electric charge $+1$ and -1 respectively, as can be seen from the commutation relations $[Q, T_1 \pm iT_2] = \mp(T_1 \pm iT_2)$. On the other hand, both W_μ^3 and B_μ are electrically neutral, as $[Q, T_3] = 0$ and $[Q, Y] = 0$. Then they can be rotated into

their combinations A_μ, Z_μ by a field redefinition:

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z_\mu \\ A_\mu \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_W & \sin \theta_W \\ -\sin \theta_W & \cos \theta_W \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} W_\mu^3 \\ B_\mu \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.36)$$

The parameter of the rotation is the Weinberg angle θ_W , or weak mixing angle, defined in terms of the EW couplings as $\tan \theta_W \equiv g'/g$. Then A_μ and its orthogonal combination Z_μ can be written as

$$A_\mu = \frac{g'W_\mu^3 + gB_\mu}{\sqrt{g^2 + g'^2}}, \quad Z_\mu = \frac{gW_\mu^3 - g'B_\mu}{\sqrt{g^2 + g'^2}}. \quad (2.37)$$

The photon field, A_μ , couples to fermions with coupling constant Qe , where e is the electron charge,

$$e = \frac{gg'}{\sqrt{g^2 + g'^2}}; \quad (2.38)$$

it also couples with the charged gauge fields W_μ^\pm , but not with the neutral Z_μ , as can be checked expanding Eq. (2.15); this fact is consistent with the photon not coupling to electrically neutral fields and, in particular, not self-interacting. Furthermore, the rotation in Eq. (2.36) gives rise to specific couplings to fermionic bilinears in Eq. (2.16), the electromagnetic charged and neutral currents. Experiments directly measure the values of electric charge e and the Weinberg angle θ_W (among other physical observables). The gauge couplings g, g' themselves are not measured directly; their ratio is inferred from the measured value of θ_W , and their absolute values are conventionally fixed by normalizing the electric charge. A detailed review of the SM is out of the scope of this work, and can be found in many familiar textbooks, for example, Ref. [18].

2.3 Symmetry breaking sector

The Lagrangian of Eq. (2.15) and (2.16), which introduces gauge fields and their interactions with fermionic matter fields in a gauge invariant fashion, has apparently one major problem: all the involved fields are massless, yet experimentally W^\pm, Z , and all the charged fermions are heavy; only the photon is massless. Adding mass terms like $M_W^2 W_\mu^a W^{\mu a}$ or $-m\bar{\mathcal{L}}\mathcal{L}$ is not an option, as they would

spoil gauge invariance (and renormalizability). A massless gauge boson has only two polarizations, while a massive spin-1 particle should have three. In order to generate the missing longitudinal polarizations of the bosons W^\pm and Z , without breaking gauge invariance, three additional degrees of freedom must be added to the massless $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ gauge theory. To do so, the existence of a symmetry breaking sector (SBS) coupled to the SM was postulated [6]:³

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{YM}} + \mathcal{L}_m + \mathcal{L}_{\text{SBS}}. \quad (2.40)$$

The Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_{SBS} is still invariant under the full $SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ group; it is formulated to drive the spontaneous symmetry breaking of the group $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ to $U(1)_{\text{EM}}$. In the most common description, the SBS comprises a $SU(2)_L$ doublet ϕ of complex scalar fields, called the Higgs doublet:

$$\phi(x) \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \phi^+(x) \\ \phi^0(x) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.41)$$

Its gauged Lagrangian, $\mathcal{L}_\phi \subset \mathcal{L}_{\text{SBS}}$, reads

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = (D_\mu \phi)^\dagger (D^\mu \phi) - V(\phi), \quad (2.42)$$

where the covariant derivative D_μ is defined as

$$D_\mu \phi = \left(\partial_\mu - i\frac{g}{2}\sigma^a W_\mu^a + iY_\phi g' B_\mu \right) \phi; \quad (2.43)$$

here, the hypercharge assignment is $Y_\phi = 1/2$, so that the electric charges of the components are $Q(\phi^+) = 1$ and $Q(\phi^0) = 0$; ϕ is a self-interacting field. The potential $V(\phi)$ reads

$$V(\phi) = -\mu^2 \phi^\dagger \phi + \lambda (\phi^\dagger \phi)^2, \quad (2.44)$$

with $\mu > 0$ and $\lambda > 0$.

³Gauge invariance would allow also the so-called θ -term

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta = \frac{g^2 \bar{\theta}}{64\pi^2} \epsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} \sum_{a=1}^8 \mathcal{G}_{\mu\nu}^a \mathcal{G}_{\rho\sigma}^a, \quad (2.39)$$

which explicitly violates P and CP . Empirical data on electric moments tell us that this term is small ($\approx 10^{-10}$), then we can omit it in the discussions [19].

From Eqs. (2.42) and (2.43) we see that \mathcal{L}_s includes the interactions of ϕ with the EW gauge fields. The interactions of ϕ with the SM fermions are described by another term, the Yukawa Lagrangian $\mathcal{L}_{\text{YM}} \subset \mathcal{L}_{\text{SBS}}$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{YK}} = -\bar{\mathcal{U}}_L \phi H_U \mathcal{U}_R - \bar{\mathcal{D}}_L \phi H_D \mathcal{D}_R - \bar{\mathcal{E}}_L \phi H_E \mathcal{E}_R + \text{h.c.} , \quad (2.45)$$

where H_U, H_D, H_E are the Yukawa couplings. Gathering Eqs. (2.42) and (2.45) together, the full symmetry breaking Lagrangian is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SBS}} = \mathcal{L}_\phi + \mathcal{L}_{\text{YK}}. \quad (2.46)$$

In the next section we describe how the W^\pm, Z , and the charged fermions acquire mass in the SM through the Higgs mechanism.

2.4 Electroweak symmetry breaking

The potential $V(\phi)$ in Eq. (2.44) is chosen ad hoc to have a non-trivial minimum and break the EW symmetry $\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{U}(1)_Y$ down to $\text{U}(1)_{\text{EM}}$, as we are going to see. There is an infinite set of degenerate states with minimum energy, satisfying

$$|\langle 0 | \phi^{(0)} | 0 \rangle| = \sqrt{\frac{\mu^2}{2\lambda}} \equiv \frac{v}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (2.47)$$

Experimentally, $v \simeq 246$ GeV. Note that only the neutral scalar field can acquire a VEV, because the electric charge is conserved.

The choice of a particular ground state leads to what is called the spontaneous breaking of the $\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{U}(1)_Y$ symmetry to the electromagnetic subgroup $\text{U}(1)_{\text{EM}}$, which by construction still remains a true symmetry of the vacuum.

According to the Goldstone theorem [20, 21], if a Lagrangian is invariant under a continuous symmetry group G (in this case, $\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{U}(1)_Y$), but the vacuum is only invariant under a subgroup $H \subset G$ (in this case, $\text{U}(1)_{\text{EM}}$), then there must exist as many massless spin-0 particles (the so-called Nambu-Goldstone bosons) as generators of G which do not belong to H . Such generators are said to be *broken*. Different degenerate vacua are connected by elements of G/H (in this case,

$SU(2)_L$), called the *coset* of G with respect to H . Note that the coset is not a subset of G : for instance, it does not contain the identity element of G .

After SSB, the scalar doublet ϕ can be parameterized as

$$\phi(x) = \exp \left\{ i \frac{\sigma^i}{2} \omega^i(x) \right\} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ v + h(x) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.48)$$

where $\omega^i(x)$ are real scalar fields representing the Goldstone bosons, and $h(x)$ is the physical Higgs boson field. Notably, the local $SU(2)_L$ invariance of the Lagrangian allows to rotate the Goldstone bosons away. This amounts to set $\omega^i(x) = 0$, which corresponds to the so-called unitary gauge.

Substituting Eq. (2.48) in the scalar Lagrangian of Eq. (2.42) one can check that the Goldstone bosons are massless, as expected, while the Higgs field acquires mass $m_H \equiv \sqrt{2\lambda}v$ and the bosons W^\pm and Z acquire mass m_W and m_Z respectively. We have, at tree level,

$$m_W = m_Z \cos \theta_W = \frac{1}{2}vg. \quad (2.49)$$

Experimentally, it has been found that $M_W \approx 80$ GeV and $M_Z \approx 91$ GeV, and $\sin^2(\theta_W) \approx 0.23$ [14]. The electroweak parameter ρ is defined as

$$\rho = \frac{M_W}{M_Z \cos \theta_W}, \quad (2.50)$$

and in the SM is automatically equal to 1 at tree level [22].

Rotating away the Goldstone bosons does not imply getting rid of them: the number of degrees of freedom (d.o.f.) remains the same before and after SSB, as we see below.

Before SSB, the Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_ϕ (Eq. (2.42)) contains three massless bosons W^\pm and Z , and four real scalar fields, i.e. the three Goldstone bosons and the Higgs. Massless spin-1 fields have two physical polarizations; then, the total number of d.o.f. $3 \times 2 + 4 = 10$.

After SSB, the weak gauge bosons become massive, acquiring one additional longitudinal polarization. We have then $3 \times 3 = 9$ d.o.f. in the gauge sector, plus the remaining scalar particle h . The photon remains massless and retains two

polarizations: its degrees of freedom do not change.

The total number of d.o.f. remains the same: what happens is that the d.o.f.s originally associated with the Goldstone bosons get absorbed, in the unitary gauge, by the longitudinal polarizations of the now massive gauge bosons. In this sense, it is usual to say that the Goldstone bosons are "eaten" by the gauge bosons. It was necessary to introduce additional d.o.f. (scalars) in the gauge theory in order to give masses to the gauge bosons. The Higgs appears because the scalar doublet contains too many fields.

To conclude this section, we briefly review fermion masses. They arise from SSB via the Yukawa couplings in \mathcal{L}_{YK} and are proportional to the Higgs vacuum expectation value (VEV) v :

$$\begin{aligned} M_Q &= v H_Q + \text{h.c.}, \\ M_L &= v H_L + \text{h.c.} \end{aligned} \tag{2.51}$$

In general, the mass matrices generated after symmetry breaking are not diagonal in flavour space, so they do not coincide with the physical (mass-eigenstate) fermions observed experimentally. Diagonalization requires unitary rotations among chiral fermion fields in flavour space. In the quark sector this produces, in the charged-current interactions, the unitary Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix V_{CKM} of dimension $n_g \times n_g$, with n_g the number of generations [23, 24]. For $n_g = 3$, V_{CKM} depends on four independent parameters (three mixing angles and one CP-violating phase) which (assuming CPT invariance) implies T violation; this has been observed in the neutral-kaon system [25]. We do not discuss this aspect further.

2.5 An approximate global symmetry in the SBS sector

The Higgs Lagrangian of Eq. (2.42) has a "hidden" *approximate* and *global* symmetry $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$, which is spontaneously broken to $SU(2)_{L+R}$, the diagonal subgroup of $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ [26] when the Higgs acquires a VEV. To make this symmetry evident, we rewrite the Higgs Lagrangian of Eq. (2.42) in terms the

2×2 bi-doublet representation Σ ,

$$\Sigma = (\phi^c, \phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \phi^{0*} & \phi^+ \\ -\phi^- & \phi^0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.52)$$

where ϕ^c is the conjugate of the Higgs doublet,

$$\phi^c = i\sigma^2 \phi^* = \begin{pmatrix} \phi^{0*} \\ -\phi^- \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.53)$$

which transforms as a doublet under $SU(2)_L$, just as ϕ (this is a special property of the $SU(2)$ group), and has opposite hypercharge, i.e., $Y_{\phi^c} = -1/2$. Making use of the identity $\text{Tr } \Sigma^\dagger \Sigma = 2\phi^\dagger \phi$, the Lagrangian of Eq. (2.42) in terms of Σ reads

$$\mathcal{L}_\Sigma \equiv \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} (D_\mu \Sigma)^\dagger D^\mu \Sigma - V(\Sigma), \quad (2.54)$$

where the potential is

$$V(\Sigma) = -\frac{\mu^2}{2} \text{Tr} (\Sigma^\dagger \Sigma) + \frac{\lambda}{4} (\text{Tr } \Sigma^\dagger \Sigma)^2, \quad (2.55)$$

and the gauge covariant derivative reads

$$D_\mu \Sigma = \partial_\mu \Sigma - i\frac{g}{2} \sigma^a W_\mu^a \Sigma + i\frac{g'}{2} B_\mu \Sigma \sigma^3. \quad (2.56)$$

The presence of the Pauli matrix σ^3 at the end of the last term in the above derivative is necessary, as ϕ and ϕ^c have opposite hypercharge. We remark that rewriting the Lagrangian in this way leaves the S-matrix unchanged. Under $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ gauge symmetry, the bi-doublet Σ transforms as

$$\begin{aligned} SU(2)_L : \Sigma &\rightarrow L(\theta_L(x))\Sigma \\ U(1)_Y : \Sigma &\rightarrow \Sigma e^{i\frac{1}{2}\sigma^3\theta_Y(x)}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.57)$$

where, again, the presence of the matrix σ^3 in the $U(1)_Y$ transformation is dictated by ϕ and ϕ^c having opposite hypercharges. In this way, \mathcal{L}_Σ in Eq. (2.54) is invariant under $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$. In particular, by construction, the kinetic term in Eq. (2.54) is invariant under (local) $SU(2)_L$ transformations. Instead, it is not invariant under

a $SU(2)_R$ transformation of the kind

$$SU(2)_R : \quad \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma R^\dagger(\theta_R(x)), \quad (2.58)$$

as W_μ is invariant under $SU(2)_R$ transformations, and R^\dagger does not commute with σ^3 (introduced in Eq. (2.56)). However, in the limit $g' \rightarrow 0$, and when the transformation of Eq. (2.58) is taken as *global*, the kinetic term is invariant.

Another way of seeing this is by introducing the doublet χ and its conjugate χ^c [12],

$$\chi = \begin{pmatrix} -\phi^+ \\ \phi^{0*} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \chi^c = i\sigma_2 \chi^* = \begin{pmatrix} \phi^0 \\ \phi^- \end{pmatrix}; \quad (2.59)$$

the scalar Lagrangian rewritten in terms of χ is invariant under transformations

$$SU(2)_R : \quad \chi \rightarrow R^\dagger \chi. \quad (2.60)$$

In the limit $g' \rightarrow 0$ with vanishing Yukawas, the SM scalar sector presents an accidental *global* $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry; the gauged $SU(2)_L$ coincides with the left factor.⁴ The global $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry is often called *chiral symmetry*, because of its formal resemblance with the chiral symmetry of massless QCD Lagrangian with two quarks flavors. The scalar Lagrangian of Eq. (2.54), with the covariant derivative given (when $g' \rightarrow 0$) by

$$D_\mu \Sigma = \partial_\mu \Sigma - i\frac{g}{2} \sigma^a W_\mu^a \Sigma, \quad (2.61)$$

is invariant when the bi-doublet Σ transforms as

$$SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R : \quad \Sigma \rightarrow L \Sigma R^\dagger. \quad (2.62)$$

When the Higgs field acquires a VEV, global $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ is spontaneously broken down to the diagonal subgroup $SU(2)_{L+R}$, the global symmetry of the vacuum state. In the bi-doublet representation, the VEV of the Higgs field, in the unitary gauge, is given by $\langle \Sigma \rangle = \frac{v}{\sqrt{2}} \mathbb{1}_2$, which is not invariant under the global $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ transformations, i.e., $L \langle \Sigma \rangle \neq \langle \Sigma \rangle$ and $\langle \Sigma \rangle R^\dagger \neq \langle \Sigma \rangle$. On the

⁴In the *full* SM this custodial symmetry is only approximate: $U(1)_Y$ gauges the right-hand generator $T_R^3 = \sigma^3/2$ (so $g' \neq 0$ breaks $SU(2)_R$ to $U(1)_Y$), and Yukawa interactions also break $SU(2)_R$ unless the up- and down-type Yukawa couplings are equal within each fermion doublet.

other hand, simultaneous $SU(2)_L$ and $SU(2)_R$ transformations with $L = R \equiv C$ leave $\langle \Sigma \rangle$ unchanged, i.e.,

$$C \langle \Sigma \rangle C^\dagger = \langle \Sigma \rangle.$$

In other words, these transformations leave unbroken the subgroup $SU(2)_{L+R}$, which is often referred to as “custodial symmetry”. We say that the Higgs VEV breaks the global symmetry with the pattern

$$SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R \rightarrow SU(2)_{L+R}. \quad (2.63)$$

The number of broken generators is $3 + 3 - 3 = 3$, corresponding to the number of Goldstone bosons “eaten” by the Higgs mechanism, providing masses and longitudinal polarizations to the W_μ^\pm and W_μ^3 fields.⁵ On the other hand, the B_μ field (corresponding to the photon when $g' \rightarrow 0$) remains massless and does not mix with the other gauge fields.

In the next chapter we work in the limit where $g' \rightarrow 0$ and all Yukawas vanish to explore the consequences of the $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry in the scalar sector.

⁵Note that, in the $g' \rightarrow 0$ custodial limit, the neutral mass eigenstate is W_μ^3 (and the photon is B_μ), so $M_W = M_Z$ and the mass term is invariant under $SU(2)_{L+R}$, reflecting a degeneracy often described as a custodial triplet (W^+, W^-, W^3) [26].

Road to an Electroweak EFT for BSM studies

In Chapter 2, we showed that, in the limit $g' \rightarrow 0$, with vanishing Yukawas, the SM enjoys a global $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry that the Higgs vacuum breaks to $SU(2)_{L+R}$, yielding three Nambu-Goldstone bosons (NGBs) [20, 21]. In this chapter we keep the NGBs explicitly (no unitary gauge) and study their interactions with the Higgs. Exploiting the S-matrix invariance under field redefinitions, we pass from the linear σ -model description to the non-linear σ -model description. Following CCWZ [27, 28, 29], we show the construction of the low-energy effective theory organized in a derivative expansion. This provides the HEFT building blocks and power counting used later to analyze Higgs-Goldstone dynamics and longitudinal gauge-boson scattering.

3.1 The SM scalar sector as a linear sigma model

The $SU(2)_L$ doublet ϕ (Eq. (2.41)) can be written in terms of the real scalar fields $\tilde{h}(x)$, $\pi^i(x)$, where $i = 1, 2, 3$, as

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \phi^+ \\ \phi^0 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \pi^2 + i\pi^1 \\ \tilde{h} - i\pi^3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.1)$$

so that its corresponding conjugate ϕ^c reads

$$\phi^c = i\sigma_2\phi^* = \begin{pmatrix} \phi^{0*} \\ -\phi^- \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{h} + i\pi^3 \\ -\pi^2 + i\pi^1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.2)$$

and the Higgs bi-doublet Σ (Eq. (2.52)) reads

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\tilde{h} + i\pi^i \sigma^i), \quad (3.3)$$

where the σ^i 's are the Pauli matrices. Collecting fields in a real 4-vector $\vec{\varphi}^T = (\pi^1, \pi^2, \pi^3, \tilde{h})$, we can understand chiral symmetry and its breaking pattern in terms of the local isomorphisms $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R \rightarrow SU(2)_{L+R} \approx O(4) \rightarrow O(3)$. Re-expressing the ungauged \mathcal{L}_Σ (Eq. (2.54)) in terms of $\vec{\varphi}$ we obtain

$$\mathcal{L}_\varphi \equiv \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \vec{\varphi})^2 + \frac{\mu^2}{2} \vec{\varphi}^2 - \frac{\lambda}{4} (\vec{\varphi}^2)^2, \quad (3.4)$$

or, equivalently,

$$\mathcal{L}_\varphi = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \vec{\varphi})^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4} (\vec{\varphi}^2 - v^2)^2, \quad (3.5)$$

where $v^2 = \mu^2/\lambda$. \mathcal{L}_φ is invariant under global rotations $g \in O(4)$ of $\vec{\varphi}$. In Cartesian coordinates, non-trivial minima satisfy $\langle \vec{\varphi}^2 \rangle_{vac} = v^2$. Choosing a vacuum, such as the conventional

$$\langle 0 | \tilde{h} | 0 \rangle = v, \quad \langle 0 | \vec{\pi} | 0 \rangle = 0, \quad (3.6)$$

causes $O(4)$ to break down to $O(3)$, as the choice is invariant under $O(3)$ rotations among the π^a fields, but not under the action of $O(4)$ rotations. The number of broken generators is $\frac{4 \times 3}{2} - \frac{3 \times 2}{2} = 3$, corresponding to three Goldstone bosons π^i . Expanding the Lagrangian around the VEV with the redefinition $s = \tilde{h} - v$, we obtain

$$\mathcal{L}_s \equiv \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu s)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \pi^a)^2 + \lambda v^2 s^2 + \lambda v s^3 + \lambda v s \vec{\pi}^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4} s^4 + \frac{\lambda}{4} (\vec{\pi}^2)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} s^2 \vec{\pi}^2, \quad (3.7)$$

and it is immediate verifying that the π^i 's are massless, while s acquires mass $m_s^2 = 2\lambda v^2$.

Now return to the ungauged \mathcal{L}_Σ of Eq. (2.54); the bi-doublet representation makes the global symmetry $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ manifest. As done in Eq. (3.5), we can rewrite it as

$$\mathcal{L}_\Sigma = \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} (\partial_\mu \Sigma)^\dagger \partial^\mu \Sigma - \frac{\lambda}{4} (\text{Tr} (\Sigma^\dagger \Sigma) - v^2)^2. \quad (3.8)$$

Taking the usual VEV $\langle \Sigma \rangle = \frac{v}{\sqrt{2}} \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$, Σ can be decomposed as

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (v + h(x)) U(\omega^a(x)), \quad (3.9)$$

where $U(\omega^a(x))$ is a unitary SU(2) matrix, the three pseudoscalar fields $\omega^a(x)$ parametrize the orientation with respect to the vacuum, and correspond to the NGB fields arising from SSB. The real scalar field h parametrizes the modulus of Σ . The matrix $U(\omega^i)$ inherits the transformation properties of Σ , while $h(x)$ remains invariant under the symmetry group:

$$U(\omega^a) \rightarrow LU(\omega^a)R^\dagger, \quad h \rightarrow h. \quad (3.10)$$

A common choice of parameterization for $U(\omega^i)$ is $U(\omega^i) = \exp(i\omega^i \sigma^i / v)$. Importantly, the symmetry group acts linearly on U and non-linearly on the ω^i 's. More details on this in the next Section 3.3.

With the parameterization of Eq. (3.9), the scalar ungauged Lagrangian reads

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{v^2}{4} \left(1 + \frac{h}{v}\right)^2 \text{Tr}(\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U + \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu h \partial^\mu h - \lambda v^2 h^2 - \lambda v h^3 - \frac{\lambda}{4} h^4, \quad (3.11)$$

with $m_h^2 \equiv 2\lambda v^2$ the mass of H, Eq. (3.11) can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{v^2}{4} \left(1 + \frac{h}{v}\right)^2 \text{Tr}(\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U + \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu h \partial^\mu h - \frac{1}{2} m_h^2 h^2 - \frac{m_h^2}{2v} h^3 - \frac{m_h^2}{8v^2} h^4. \quad (3.12)$$

All the different functional forms of the scalar Lagrangian that we have presented along this section give the same physical predictions. However, the last expression, Eq. (3.12), allows to clearly read off the properties below.

- the (massless) NG bosons have purely derivative couplings, meaning that their contribution to scattering amplitudes depends on the external momenta. These are model-independent, and fixed by the global symmetry.
- The radial variable $h(x)$ describes a massive scalar particle, with mass $m_h^2 = 2\lambda v^2$.
- The potential depends only on $h(x)$, and it is controlled by the parameter

λ . It constitutes the model-dependent part of the Lagrangian.

We started with the identification of the $O(4)$ linear sigma model “hidden” in the ungauged SM scalar Lagrangian, and arrived to the nonlinear sigma model through a change of coordinates: we decomposed the initial complex doublet, or the real quadruplet, into a singlet and a triplet. The vice versa cannot be imposed by the $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry alone: it is not necessary for the singlet and triplet to be part of a quadruplet (or a complex triplet). The physical predictions are the same in every case, but the non-linear sigma model is a more general framework, and lies the basis for the construction of an EFT.¹

With these preliminaries in place, in the next subsection we consider the regime where momenta are such that $p^2 \ll m_h^2$, i.e. where the radial mode h is a heavy field, and we derive a Goldstone-only effective Lagrangian. Using the equations of motion, we obtain the universal LO and NLO terms (at tree level).

3.2 Low-energy NGB dynamics

In the limit $\lambda \gg 1$ (or $m_h^2 \rightarrow \infty$), the field $h(x)$ in Eq. (3.11) is heavy and can be integrated out, leaving only the Goldstone fields as dynamical degrees of freedom. At tree level, keeping the leading term and the first correction in the $1/m_h^2$ expansion, one obtains

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \mathcal{L}_2^{(0)} + \mathcal{L}_4^{(1)} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{m_h^4}, \partial^6\right), \quad (3.13)$$

with

$$\mathcal{L}_2^{(0)} = \frac{v^2}{4} \text{Tr}[(\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U], \quad (3.14)$$

and the NLO piece of order $\mathcal{O}(1/m_h^2)$ given by

$$\mathcal{L}_4^{(1)} = \frac{v^2}{8 m_h^2} \left[\text{Tr}((\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U) \right]^2. \quad (3.15)$$

¹The formalism of the non-linear sigma model was originally introduced to describe the low-energy dynamics of the pion fields in QCD [30, 31], which present a similar symmetry breaking pattern $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R \rightarrow SU(2)_{L+R}$.

Eqs. (3.14) and (3.15) are derived as follows. From Eq. (3.11) the equation of motion (EOM) for $h(x)$ reads

$$(\partial_\mu \partial^\mu + m_h^2)h = \frac{v}{2} \left(1 + \frac{h}{v}\right) \text{Tr}[(\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U] - \lambda(3vh^2 + h^3). \quad (3.16)$$

We solve the EOM iteratively in $1/m_h^2$. To the first non-vanishing order,

$$h(x) = \frac{v}{2m_h^2} \text{Tr}[(\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U] + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\partial^4}{m_h^4}\right). \quad (3.17)$$

Plugging this back into the original Lagrangian (3.11) and discarding terms of $\mathcal{O}(\partial^6/m_h^4)$ and higher yields Eqs. (3.14),(3.15). The same procedure can be iterated to obtain higher-order terms, providing a concrete example of how to derive an effective Lagrangian by integrating out heavy fields. The above discussion can be revised with the path integral formalism: writing

$$\mathcal{Z}(\omega^a) = \int \mathcal{D}h e^{i \int d^4x \mathcal{L}_s[h, \omega^a]}, \quad (3.18)$$

where $\mathcal{Z}(\omega^a)$ is the path integral after integrating out the heavy field H , and $\int d^4x \mathcal{L}_s[h, \omega^a]$ is the action of the full theory. This leads to an effective action $S_{\text{eff}}(\omega^a)$, which admits an expansion in $1/m_h^2$ as $S_{\text{eff}} = S^{(0)} + \frac{1}{m_h^2} S^{(1)} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{m_h^4}\right)$. The leading order term, $S_{\text{eff}}^{(0)}$, can be obtained perturbatively by performing a saddle point approximation, i.e. $S_{\text{eff}}^{(0)} = S(\hat{h}, \omega)$, with \hat{h} being the solution of $\frac{\delta S(\hat{h}, \omega^a)}{\delta h} = 0$ (i.e. of the EOM for H , Eq. (3.16)). The solution can be calculated perturbatively in the expansion parameter $\frac{1}{m_h^2}$, which is specific of the EFT that we are considering. In this procedure, the field ω^a plays the role of an external field.

Owing to its nonlinear functional form, the Lagrangian of Eq. (3.13) contains an infinite tower of derivative interactions between the ω^a fields. It provides a universal, model-independent description of the NG modes at very low energies, and it is a direct consequence of the spontaneous breaking of the global symmetry $\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R$ [29].

3.3 CCWZ coset space coordinates

Having isolated the Goldstone sector, we now introduce a model-independent framework for their transformation properties. The Callan-Coleman-Zumino-Wess (CCWZ) formalism [28, 27] provides a general treatment of theories exhibiting a $G \rightarrow H$ SSB pattern [32, 29], enabling a description of Nambu-Goldstone (NG) dynamics and the construction of the most general low-energy effective Lagrangian for these degrees of freedom. We first review the construction in general terms and then specialize to the coset $G/H = (\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R)/\text{SU}(2)_{L+R}$. Consider a theory with a global symmetry group G spontaneously broken to the subgroup H that leaves the vacuum invariant (the “little group”). The number of broken generators is given by $d = \dim(G) - \dim(H)$; Goldstone’s theorem then implies one massless NG boson per broken generator. In this section, we label T^a the broken generators, with $a = 1, \dots, d$, and indicate with $\omega = (\omega^1, \dots, \omega^d)$ the set of the corresponding NGBs. We label \hat{T}^a , $a = d + 1, \dots, \dim(G)$ the unbroken generators of H .

We recall that, given a subgroup $H \subset G$, the latter admit a unique decomposition in left cosets, $G = H \cup g_1 H \cup g_2 H \cup \dots$, with an infinity of factors in our case. The set of all left cosets of H is called the quotient space, and it is denoted by G/H .

Let $|\text{VEV}\rangle$ be the representative vacuum state of the theory. Then, for every $h \in H$, it holds by construction $h|\text{VEV}\rangle = |\text{VEV}\rangle$. A general configuration $|\Phi\rangle$ is related to $|\text{VEV}\rangle$ by a transformation $g \in G$ according to the ansatz

$$|\Phi\rangle = g|\text{VEV}\rangle, \quad (3.19)$$

where $g \equiv g(\theta^a \hat{T}^a, \omega^a T^a)$. The coordinates θ^a , $a = 1, \dots, \dim(H)$ parametrize the unbroken generators of H . There’s a redundancy hidden in (3.19): to reveal it, we start by noticing that the group element G admits a unique (as it is easy to check) decomposition

$$g(\theta^a(x) \hat{T}^a(x), \omega^b(x) T^b) = \tilde{g}(\omega^a(x) T^a) h(\theta^b(x) \hat{T}^b), \quad (3.20)$$

where $\tilde{g} \equiv \tilde{g}(\omega^a(x) T^a) \in G/H$, and $h \equiv h(\theta^b(x) \hat{T}^b) \in H$. The elements of H , by

construction, leave the vacuum invariant, so that we can write, in force of the decomposition of (3.20),

$$|\Phi\rangle = g |\text{VEV}\rangle = \tilde{g}h |\text{VEV}\rangle = \tilde{g}(\omega^a T^a) |\text{VEV}\rangle = |\omega\rangle; \quad (3.21)$$

i.e., the fields associated with the unbroken ones were the responsible of the redundancy. By construction, they drop out from the ansatz and thus do not count as physical degrees of freedom. Then, we can describe a general configuration of the theory $|\Phi\rangle$ using as coordinates the NGB fields only, which span the left coset space G/H , which is defined as the equivalence class of G modulo H elements multiplication. We can associate in a unique way a set of Goldstone fields ω^a to each element of the coset space G/H ,

In fact, the Goldstone fields are the coordinates of G/H . Additionally, (3.21) inspires us to establish a unique map

$$(\omega^1(x), \dots, \omega^d(x)) \mapsto \tilde{g}((\omega^1(x), \dots, \omega^d(x))) \equiv \xi(\omega(x)) \in G/H; \quad (3.22)$$

we call $\xi(\omega) \in G/H$ *Goldstone matrix*.

Now suppose that we are acting on the state $|\Phi(x)\rangle$ with $g \in G$; from (3.21), we would like to enforce

$$g |\Phi\rangle \equiv \xi(\omega^{(g)}) |\text{VEV}\rangle, \quad \xi(\omega^{(g)}) \in G/H; \quad (3.23)$$

this implicitly defines the action of G on the NGB fields as given by a transformation

$$\omega \rightarrow \omega^{(g)} = f(\omega, g), \quad (3.24)$$

where f is a function that satisfies the composition law of the unbroken group G : if $\omega^{(g_1)} = f(\omega, g_1)$, and $\omega^{(g_2)} = f(\omega^{(g_1)}, g_2)$, then

$$\left(\omega^{(g_1)}\right)^{(g_2)} = f(f(\omega, g_1), g_2) = f(\omega, g_2 g_1) = \omega^{(g_2 g_1)}; \quad (3.25)$$

the coordinates of the G/H manifold allow for a complete description of the unbroken symmetry group G , which still implies powerful constraints on the allowed operators once that the vacuum representative is fixed.

We call ω_{VEV} the coordinates on the NGB manifold corresponding to the vacuum state. Any $h \in H$ induces a transformation that leaves ω_{VEV} invariant, i.e.

$$\omega_{\text{VEV}} \rightarrow \omega_{\text{VEV}}^{(h)} = f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, h) = \omega_{\text{VEV}}. \quad (3.26)$$

Then, for any $g \in G$ and $h \in H$, in force of the composition law of Eq. (3.25)

$$f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, gh) = f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, g), \quad (3.27)$$

then, since we can think of any element of $g \in G$ as an element of the left coset of H , i.e. $g \in \tilde{g}H$, where $\tilde{g} \in G/H$, we have

$$f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, g) = f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, \tilde{g}). \quad (3.28)$$

We can view $f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, \cdot)$ as a function which takes from the set of all the left cosets of H to the manifold of the NGB fields. In addition, the correspondence is invertible: for any g_1, g_2 in G , if $f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, g_1) = f(\omega_{\text{VEV}}, g_2)$, then

$$f(g_1^{-1}g_1, \omega_{\text{VEV}}) = f(1, \omega_{\text{VEV}}) = \omega_{\text{VEV}} = f(g_1^{-1}g_2, \omega_{\text{VEV}}), \quad (3.29)$$

implying that we can find a $h \in H$ such that $g_1^{-1}g_2 = h$, which implies $g_2 \in g_1H$, i.e. g_1 and g_2 belong to the same left coset of H .

So there is a one to one correspondence between the elements of G/H and the manifold of the NGB fields, which we can think of as coordinates of the coset space G/H . In our case, this space is $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R / SU(2)_{L+R}$.

Correspondingly, there will be a transformation rule for the elements of the coset space, $\xi(\omega) \rightarrow \xi(\omega^{(g)})$: how does exactly the action of G on $\xi(\omega)$ look like?

Let us start by observing that the answer cannot be simply " $\xi(\omega^{(g)}) = g\xi(\omega)$ ", as this would not ensure that $\xi(\omega^{(g)})$ remains in the coset space G/H : in principle, we will find $g\xi(\omega) \in G$. But this turns out to provide the solution to the problem: similarly to what we have done in (3.20), we can decompose $g\xi(\omega)$ as the product of one element of the coset space G/H - namely, the $\xi(\omega^{(g)})$ we are looking for - and one "compensating" element h of the little group H , which will depend on the starting point in the G/H space parameterized by ω , and on the particular

transformation $g \in G$ we are considering:

$$g \xi(\omega) \equiv \xi(\omega^{(g)})h(\omega, g), \quad \xi(\omega^{(g)}) \in G/H, h \in H; \quad (3.30)$$

now we are done: we can readily read off the transformation rule for the Goldstone matrix,

$$\forall g \in G : \quad \xi(\omega) \xrightarrow{G} \xi(\omega^{(g)}) = g \xi(\omega) h^\dagger(\omega, g). \quad (3.31)$$

It is easy to see that this induces the symmetry transformation depicted in Eq. (3.23). It is customary to call $\xi(\omega)$ a *representative* of the coset space G/H . In the effective Lagrangian for the NGB modes, only the terms invariant under the transformation $\xi(\omega) \rightarrow g \xi(\omega) h^\dagger(\omega, g)$ are allowed. As can be seen from (3.31), $\omega^{(g)}$ carries a complicated, nonlinear dependence on ω . This is why one often speaks of $\xi(\omega)$ as a *nonlinear* representation, and why it is said that the spontaneously broken group G is *non-linearly realized*.

We can now particularize the discussion to the case of the pattern $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R \rightarrow SU(2)_{L+R}$. A general representative NGB field can be written $\xi(\omega) \equiv (\xi_L(\omega), \xi_R(\omega))$. In its matrix form, we can intuitively think of it as parametrizing the zero energy excitations over the vacuum state $\sim v\mathbf{1}$.

Under $g = (g_L, g_R) \in SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$, the left and right components transform as

$$\xi_L(\omega) \xrightarrow{G} g_L \xi_L(\omega) h^\dagger(\omega, g), \quad \xi_R(\omega) \xrightarrow{G} h(\omega, g) \xi_R(\omega) g_R^\dagger. \quad (3.32)$$

The compensating transformation $h^\dagger(\omega, g)$ for the left and right sector is the same, owing to the fact that $SU(2)_L$ and $SU(2)_R$ are related by a parity transformation that leaves H invariant.

We can get rid of H by combining $U(\omega) = \xi_L(\omega) \xi_R^\dagger(\omega)$, that the transformation rule is

$$U(\omega) \rightarrow g_L U(\omega) g_R^\dagger. \quad (3.33)$$

The canonical choice of representatives is $\xi_L = \xi_R^\dagger \equiv u$, so that $U(\omega) = u(\omega)^2$.

We now work out how the ω^a fields transform under global $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ and under global $SU(2)_{L+R}$. Let g_L (g_R) be an element of $SU(2)_L$ ($SU(2)_R$), given by $g_L = \exp\left\{i\frac{\sigma^a}{2}\theta_L^a\right\}$ ($g_R = \exp\left\{i\frac{\sigma^a}{2}\theta_R^a\right\}$), where θ_L^a (θ_R^a), with $a = 1, 2, 3$, are infinitesimal real parameters, and σ^a are the Pauli matrices. $U(\omega^a)$ can be

parameterized adopting the exponential parametrization $U(\omega^a) = \exp\left\{i\frac{\omega^a}{v} \cdot \tau\right\}$, where the normalizing factor v denotes the vacuum expectation value of the field. Whatever the choice, the parameterization must be linear in ω^a at first order in the expansion, i.e.,

$$U(\omega^a) = 1 + i\frac{\omega^a}{v}\sigma^a + \mathcal{O}(\omega^2). \quad (3.34)$$

We remark that in [33] the discussion is worked out with an adimensional ω , and it is remarked that the normalization of a field is not a physical observable. It is convenient to employ a *canonical* normalization, so that the kinetic term of the field has the standard form $\frac{1}{2}\partial_\mu\omega\partial^\mu\omega$, to avoid complicated factors in the Feynman rules. Anyway, it is important to keep $U(\omega)$, so that the derivative terms are proportional to powers of p^2 . It is easy to check that the Goldstone fields transform as

$$\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R : U(\omega^a) \rightarrow g_L U(\omega^a) g_R^\dagger \implies \omega^a \rightarrow \omega^a + \frac{v}{2}(\theta_L^a - \theta_R^a), \quad (3.35)$$

$$\text{SU}(2)_{L+R} : U(\omega^a) \rightarrow h U(\omega^a) h^\dagger \implies \omega^a \rightarrow \omega^a - \epsilon^{abc}\theta^b\omega^c; \quad (3.36)$$

Eq. (3.35) shows that under an infinitesimal global $\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R$ transformation $U(\omega)$ transforms linearly, but the induced transformation on the NGB fields is nonlinear, as the NGB fields acquire a constant shift. On the other hand, Eq. (3.36) shows that if the transformation belongs to the diagonal group $\text{SU}(2)_{L+R}$, then the NGBs transform linearly.

We say then that the global symmetry $\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R$ is then realized nonlinearly. This is why the model is called nonlinear sigma model.

3.4 Effective $\text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R$ Lagrangian for the NGB modes

At energies well below a heavy scale Λ , the dynamics is governed by the light degrees of freedom and by symmetries. An effective theory establishes a framework in which to reproduce arbitrary sets of low energy data with arbitrarily high precision, on the basis of limited low energy data. For the development of an effective theory, the following steps are required [34, 35]: (i) identifying a separa-

tion of scales; (ii) selecting the appropriate degrees of freedom (integrating out heavy ones if gaps exist); (iii) enforcing the underlying symmetries (and their explicit/spontaneous breakings); (iv) writing the most general Lagrangian consistent with them; (v) organising terms in a momentum (derivative) expansion with a power counting (i.e., an organizational scheme to distinguish between more and less important contributions); (vi) computing observables to the desired order. This operational scheme is underpinned by Weinberg’s “folk theorem” [33]: with analyticity, unitarity, cluster decomposition and the assumed symmetries, the most general Lagrangian yields the most general S -matrix order by order in perturbation theory.

For the breaking $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R \rightarrow SU(2)_{L+R}$, the Nambu - Goldstone bosons (NGBs) are collected in $U(\omega) = \exp(i\omega^a \sigma^a / v)$, which transforms linearly as in Eq. (3.33), while the fields ω^a transform nonlinearly (shift symmetry), as in Eq. (3.35). The EFT expansion in derivatives is constrained by this symmetry; Lorentz indices must be fully contracted, and operators proportional to the equations of motion can be removed [36]. The Lagrangian is organised as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_2 + \mathcal{L}_4 + \mathcal{L}_6 + \dots = \sum_n \mathcal{L}_{2n}, \quad (3.37)$$

with only even numbers of derivatives. At lowest order there is a single independent structure,

$$\mathcal{L}_2 = \frac{v^2}{4} \text{Tr} [(\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U]. \quad (3.38)$$

Expanding $U(\omega)$ in powers of ω , (3.38) returns the kinetic term plus, due to the nonlinearity of the effective Lagrangian, an infinite tower of derivative interactions involving an increasing number of NGB fields. We require for the kinetic term to be canonically normalized as $\frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \omega^a \partial^\mu \omega^a$. Expanding $U(\omega)$ generates, besides the kinetic term $\frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \omega^a \partial^\mu \omega^a$, an infinite tower of multi-NGB vertices. The overall normalisation in (3.38) is fixed to $v^2/4$ so that the kinetic term is canonical, independently of the chosen parametrisation of U .

The global symmetry can be promoted to a local one by introducing external vector sources $l_\mu(x)$ and $r_\mu(x)$ [37, 38]. When the transformation parameters are spacetime dependent ($g_{L,R} = g_{L,R}(x)$), the ordinary derivative of U in Eq. (3.38),

is no longer covariant:

$$\partial^\mu U \rightarrow (\partial g_L) U g_R^\dagger + g_L (\partial^\mu U) g_R^\dagger + g_L U \partial^\mu (g_R^\dagger). \quad (3.39)$$

These extra terms are eliminated introducing the covariant derivative

$$D^\mu = \partial^\mu - i \ell^\mu U + i U r^\mu, \quad (3.40)$$

with r^μ and ℓ^μ transforming as gauge fields (spurions):

$$l_\mu \rightarrow g_L l_\mu g_L^\dagger + i g_L \partial_\mu g_L^\dagger, \quad (3.41)$$

$$r_\mu \rightarrow g_R r_\mu g_R^\dagger + i g_R \partial_\mu g_R^\dagger. \quad (3.42)$$

and the leading-order Lagrangian reads

$$\mathcal{L}_2 = \frac{v^2}{4} \text{Tr}[(D_\mu U)^\dagger D^\mu U], \quad (3.43)$$

which reduces to Eq. (3.38) in the limit $l_\mu = r_\mu = 0$. This is the *external-source method*, which makes explicit the promotion of $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ from a global to a local symmetry.

Power counting follows Weinberg's theorem [33]: a connected diagram with L loops and N_d insertions of $\mathcal{O}(p^d)$ (bosonic) vertices scales as

$$D = 2 + 2L + \sum_d N_d (d - 2). \quad (3.44)$$

Therefore, LO is $\mathcal{O}(p^2)$ (tree diagrams from \mathcal{L}_2), and NLO is $\mathcal{O}(p^4)$: tree diagrams with one \mathcal{L}_4 insertion plus one loop diagrams built from \mathcal{L}_2 . Using a symmetry-preserving regulator (e.g. dimensional regularisation), UV divergences at a given order are absorbed by renormalising the low-energy constants in the Lagrangian at that same order [34].

3.5 Formulation of an EFT for the SM

We have showed that the SM scalar sector, in virtue of its global symmetry structure, can accommodate a description of the Higgs and the NGBs alternative to the standard one as a $SU(2)_L$ doublet, one which is ultimately rooted in the CCWZ formalism. Although the experimental measures of the Higgs properties do match SM predictions, experimental uncertainties still can accommodate alternative scenarios in which EWSB is realized differently than in the SM [39]. It remains uncertain whether the observed Higgs boson is truly the SM scalar, forming part of an $SU(2)_L$ doublet alongside the three electroweak Nambu-Goldstone bosons, or if it represents a distinct degree of freedom, separated from the Nambu-Goldstone modes, or some entirely different scenario. In this chapter, we will see that it is possible to employ the CCWZ formalism to build an effective theory with the same particle content and symmetries of the SM, without making assumptions on the nature of the Higgs field and how EWSB is realized. This theory is the Higgs Effective Field Theory (HEFT). The particles in the spectra are said to be “light” in comparison with the EWSB scale:

$$\Lambda_{\text{EWSB}} \simeq 4\pi v \sim 3 \text{ TeV}. \quad (3.45)$$

The first attempts to formulate a non-linear effective Lagrangian in the presence of a singlet Higgs boson can be found in Refs. [40, 41], and in Refs. [42, 43].

3.6 SMEFT

A straightforward approach to construct an EFT generalization of the SM is adopted in the Standard Model Effective Field Theory (SMEFT) [44, 45, 39]. It has the SM field content and gauge symmetries, and assumes a linear realization of electroweak symmetry breaking (EWSB), with the Higgs and Goldstone bosons gathered together in the $SU(2)_L$ doublet H , as in the SM.

Additionally, in SMEFT, it is assumed the existence of an unknown new physics sector extending the SM at scales higher than the EW and VEV scales, with the threshold schematically denoted as Λ .

Under these assumptions, SMEFT is built out of a series of $SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ gauge invariant operators, organized according to a power counting in their canonical mass dimension. In this expansion, the SM is the leading order (LO), and higher-dimensional operators are weighted by inverse powers of Λ . The SMEFT Lagrangian is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SMEFT}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} + \mathcal{L}^{(5)} + \mathcal{L}^{(6)} + \mathcal{L}^{(7)} + \mathcal{L}^{(8)} + \dots, \quad (3.46)$$

where, indicating with d the canonical dimension of the operators and with n_d the number of operators with dimension d , we have

$$\mathcal{L}^{(d)} = \sum_i^{n_d} \frac{c_i^{(d)}}{\Lambda^{d-4}} O_i^{(d)} \quad \text{for } d > 4. \quad (3.47)$$

The operators O_i , $i = 1, \dots, n_d$, are suppressed by Λ^{d-4} , and the couplings $c_i^{(d)}$ are dimensionless Wilson coefficients, which contain information about the underlying physics. SMEFT is systematically defined at all orders in the expansion: \mathcal{L}_{SM} contains all the renormalizable operators with $d = 4$. The number of non-redundant operators in $\mathcal{L}^{(5)}$, $\mathcal{L}^{(6)}$, $\mathcal{L}^{(7)}$, $\mathcal{L}^{(8)}$ is known, while for higher orders it has been developed a general algorithm to determine operator basis [39]. There is only one operator with dimension five, which violates lepton number. Assuming separate conservation of lepton and baryon number [29], the leading corrections to the SM arise from dimension-six operators, and the next order corrections are of dimension-8. Then, in this work, we do not consider $\mathcal{L}^{(5)}$ or $\mathcal{L}^{(7)}$ in Eqs. (3.46), (3.47). For the dimension-six operators, we use the Warsaw basis; redundancies are removed by EOM, integration by parts, and Fierz identities [44, 45].

There is only one operator with dimension five, which violates lepton number. Assuming separate conservation of lepton and baryon number [29], the leading corrections to the SM arise from dimension-six operators. For these, we use the Warsaw basis; redundancies are removed by EOM, integration by parts, and Fierz identities [44, 45]. In this work we do not take into account $\mathcal{L}^{(5)}$ and $\mathcal{L}^{(7)}$:

The symmetry breaking sector of SMEFT is built out of the $SU(2)_L$ doublet H . At dimension 6, the operators of the Warsaw basis which modify the SM

Lagrangian of the SBS sector are

$$O_H = (H^\dagger H)^3, \quad O_{H\Box} = (H^\dagger H)\Box(H^\dagger H), \quad O_{HD} = |H^\dagger D_\mu H|^2. \quad (3.48)$$

In this work the relevant operator is $O_{H\Box}$. We neglect the custodial-symmetry violating operator O_{HD} because electroweak precision data tightly constrain its Wilson coefficient C_{HD}/Λ^2 ; accordingly, we set $C_{HD} = 0$ in benchmarks [46]. The operator O_H is not a derivative operator and, as so, it does not play a role in our analysis, as we will see in Chapter 4.9. At the next order $\mathcal{O}(\Lambda^{-4})$, we will also consider the dimension 8 operator

$$O_{H\Box}^{(8)} = (H^\dagger H)^2 \Box(H^\dagger H); \quad (3.49)$$

we remark that other dimension-8 structures exist, but we do not consider them in this work. In the next section we will focus on the Higgs Effective Field Theory (HEFT) framework. We will test SMEFT-implied correlations among HEFT couplings in the chapter 4.

3.7 Higgs Effective Field Theory

The Higgs Effective Theory contains the known particle spectrum: the SM fermions and gauge bosons, the triplet of electroweak Nambu-Goldstone bosons ω^i , and the physical Higgs field h [47, 48]. As it is for SMEFT and the SM, the full HEFT satisfies the gauge symmetry $G_{\text{SM}} = \text{SU}(3) \times \text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{U}(1)_Y$, which gets spontaneously broken as $G_{\text{SM}} \rightarrow H_{\text{SM}} = \text{U}(1)_{\text{EM}}$, giving rise to the masses of the electroweak gauge bosons W^\pm and Z . In addition to the SM symmetries, HEFT extends the global symmetry to $G = \text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R \supset G_{\text{SM}}$. The pattern of EWSB is assumed:

$$G = \text{SU}(2)_L \times \text{SU}(2)_R \rightarrow H = \text{SU}(2)_{L+R}, \quad (3.50)$$

where $\text{SU}(2)_{L+R} \supset H_{\text{SM}} = \text{U}(1)_{\text{EM}}$. Note that, in the full SM, the exact chiral symmetry of the chiral sector is only approximate, as it is realized only within the scalar sector, and it gets broken when EW gauge interactions and fermions

with the scalar sector are taken into account. If one wants the theory to be a correct extension of the SM, it is necessary to reproduce the SM chiral symmetry breaking mechanism.

The HEFT Lagrangian is organised according to the so-called *chiral* power counting, i.e. the operators are ordered according to their chiral dimensions,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{HEFT}} = \mathcal{L}_2^{(\text{HEFT})} + \mathcal{L}_4^{(\text{HEFT})} + \mathcal{L}_6^{(\text{HEFT})} + \dots; \quad (3.51)$$

The dots denote the infinite tower of terms with higher chiral dimensions. The Lagrangian of Eq. (3.51) is an expansion in the number of derivatives, as it is done in Chiral Perturbation Theory (ChPT) or in the general context depicted by the CCWZ formalism of a theory exhibiting spontaneous symmetry breaking with NGB modes. However, HEFT contains a richer structure due to the presence of the SM symmetries, the fermion sector, and different types of symmetry breaking effects.

The leading order is given by the renormalizable, unbroken, massless SM, plus an additional contribution from EWSB:

$$\mathcal{L}_2^{\text{HEFT}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}}^{(0)} + \Delta\mathcal{L}_2^{(\text{EWSB})} \quad (3.52)$$

We have already reviewed the properties and structure of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}}^{(0)}$ in Chapter 2. In principle, $\Delta\mathcal{L}_2^{(\text{EWSB})}$ contains contributions of both bosonic and fermionic type. We remark the following:

- As in ChPT, to fully exploit the symmetry constraints, one extends the global symmetry to a local one making use of spurionic fields r^μ and l^μ to keep chiral invariance. In order to take into account the full SM gauge sector, and break the chiral symmetry in the same way, they have to be set to the SM gauge fields $W_\mu^{1,2,3}$ and B_μ [29].
- In order to add the SM fermions, one has to introduce auxiliary Yukawa fields to keep chiral invariance, then set them to the SM Yukawa couplings. In this way, chiral symmetry gets explicitly broken as in the SM [34].

Anyway, we will focus on the bosonic contributions from $\Delta\mathcal{L}_2^{(\text{EWSB})}$. The discussion is done in the next section.

3.7.1 Bosonic LO Lagrangian

To construct the bosonic part of $\Delta\mathcal{L}$, we begin by selecting an appropriate representation for the NGB modes and specifying the form of the covariant derivative acting on them. This requires a clear definition of how the gauge bosons are embedded within the effective theory, which will be addressed in this section.

We parameterize the NGB coordinates adopting the coset coordinates following the transformation rule of Eq. (3.32), combined into the unitary adimensional matrix $U(\omega) = \xi_L(\omega)\xi_R^\dagger(\omega)$, which in turn transforms as in Eq. (3.33). Furthermore, we can employ the canonical choice of representatives $\xi_L = \xi_R^\dagger \equiv u$, so that $U(\omega) = u^2(\omega) \xrightarrow{G} g_L U(\omega) g_R^\dagger$. The transformation rule for $u(\omega)$ under $g = (g_L, g_R) \in G$ is

$$u(\omega) \rightarrow g_L u(\omega) h^\dagger(\omega, g) = h(\omega, g) u(\omega) g_R^\dagger, \quad (3.53)$$

where the compensating transformation $h(\omega, g) \in H$ depends on the initial coordinates ω and the group elements g_L and g_R .

The Higgs field h transforms as a singlet: its dynamics is not constrained by a $SU(2)_L$ doublet structure. The couplings of the Higgs are model-dependent general functions, but the $SU(2)_L$ structure is absent in them.

To incorporate the gauge fields, we formally introduce \hat{W}_μ as a $SU(2)_L$ matrix, and \hat{B}_μ as a $SU(2)_R$ matrix. The transformation rules are

$$\hat{W}_\mu \rightarrow g_L \hat{W}_\mu g_L^\dagger + ig_L \partial_\mu g_L^\dagger, \quad \hat{B}_\mu \rightarrow g_R \hat{B}_\mu g_R^\dagger + ig_R \partial_\mu g_R^\dagger; \quad (3.54)$$

this is similar to what is done in ChPT with the left and right sources. This is why \hat{B}_μ and \hat{W}_μ are also called *gauge sources*. Here we must additionally consider the Yang Mills Lagrangian, because they are dynamical fields of the full theory. Then we need to define the corresponding field-strength tensors and their transformation rules,

$$\hat{W}_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \hat{W}_\nu - \partial_\nu \hat{W}_\mu + i[\hat{W}_\mu, \hat{W}_\nu] \rightarrow g_L \hat{W}_{\mu\nu} g_L^\dagger, \quad (3.55)$$

$$\hat{B}_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \hat{B}_\nu - \partial_\nu \hat{B}_\mu + i[\hat{B}_\mu, \hat{B}_\nu] \rightarrow g_R \hat{B}_{\mu\nu} g_R^\dagger. \quad (3.56)$$

To recover the SM gauge field, we use the identification

$$\hat{W}_\mu = -\frac{g}{2}W_\mu^a\sigma^a, \quad \hat{B}_\mu = -\frac{g'}{2}B_\mu\sigma^3, \quad (3.57)$$

which explicitly breaks the $SU(2)_R$ symmetry, while keeping the $SU(2)_L \times U_Y(1)$ intact.

The covariant derivative acting on $U(\omega)$ is defined as

$$D_\mu U(\omega) = \partial_\mu U(\omega) + i\hat{W}_\mu U(\omega) - iU(\omega)\hat{B}_\mu \xrightarrow{G} g_L D_\mu U(\omega) g_R^\dagger. \quad (3.58)$$

We can also introduce the covariant structures u_μ and $f_\pm^{\mu\nu}$,²

$$u_\mu \equiv iu(D_\mu)^\dagger u = -iu^\dagger D_\mu u^\dagger = u_\mu^\dagger \xrightarrow{G} hu_\mu h^\dagger, \quad (3.59)$$

and

$$f_\pm^{\mu\nu} \equiv u^\dagger \hat{W}^{\mu\nu} u \pm u^\dagger \hat{B}^{\mu\nu} u \xrightarrow{G} hf_\pm^{\mu\nu} h^\dagger. \quad (3.60)$$

Now we can write the bosonic part of $\Delta\mathcal{L}_2$:

$$\Delta\mathcal{L}_2^b = \frac{v^2}{4}\mathcal{F}(h)\text{Tr}(u_\mu u^\mu) + \frac{1}{2}\partial_\mu h\partial^\mu h - \frac{1}{2}m_h^2 h^2 - V(h). \quad (3.61)$$

Here we are implicitly selecting the Landau gauge. In this gauge, the ω 's are massless and we refer to them as the would-be Nambu-Goldstone bosons (WBGBs). The term $\text{Tr}(u_\mu u^\mu) = \text{Tr}((D_\mu U)^\dagger D^\mu U)$ is the model-independent Nambu-Goldstone operator which we discussed in Sect. 3.4. The Higgs scalar potential is extended as or

$$V(h) = V_0 + \frac{M_h^2}{2}h^2 + 2v^2 M_h^2 \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_n}{(2v)^n} h^n; \quad (3.62)$$

so that it can take into account Higgs self interactions of arbitrary order. Finally, $\mathcal{F}(h)$ denotes an arbitrary analytic function of h , which we'll refer to as *flare function* [13],

$$\mathcal{F}(h) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \left(\frac{h}{v}\right)^n, \quad (3.63)$$

parameterizes the interaction between the Higgs and the fields, providing the

²The notation can be quite misleading since the Higgs field h could be confused with the compensating field in the CCWZ construction (Section 3.3), as in this case.

irreducible tree-level vertices. Here, the constant v denotes the electroweak scale. It is used to compensate both the Higgs and NG fields, as in Eq. (3.34), because they are assumed to have the same origin. Then, the coefficients a_n in Eq. (3.63) are dimensionless and expected to be of order $\mathcal{O}(1)$. Since the Higgs field is a singlet under the global symmetry, every chiral invariant structure can be multiplied with such a function. In fact, in principle, also the kinetic term of the Higgs field could appear as multiplied by a similar function $\mathcal{F}_h(h)$, but it can be reabsorbed by a field redefinition of h and this is why it does not appear. However, as it is thoroughly discussed in [49, 9], in a general effective theory framework it is possible to consider the existence of an undetermined higher scale f , different from v , and use it instead of v to normalize the scalar field.

To recover the SM Lagrangian from Eq. (3.61), it is sufficient to adopt a proper choice of the coefficients: in Eq. (3.62), $\lambda_3 = 2$, $\lambda_4 = 1$, $\lambda_{n>4} = 0$, and in Eq. (3.63) $a_1 = 2$, $a_2 = 1$, $a_{n>2} = 0$.

In literature, the last two coefficients are often referred to as a , b , which are related to a_1 and a_2 as $a_1 = 2a$, $a_2 = b$. In general, a_1 and a_2 can be adjusted to fit different theoretical models [50]. In particular, we cite two relevant cases:

- In the absence of a physical Higgs in the theory, $a = b = 0$, and $a_i = 0 \forall n > 3$; this scenario is implemented in the Higgsless Effective Chiral Lagrangian (EWChL) framework.
- for the Standard Model, $a = b = 1$, and $a_i = 0 \forall n > 3$. In this case, $\mathcal{F}(h/v) = (1 + \frac{h}{v})^2$.

Notably, the flare function can be defined in both SMEFT and HEFT frameworks. This allows to map a single measurement to both scenarios, which is crucial to compare the corresponding predictions [13, 9].

3.7.2 HEFT power counting in the bosonic sector

An operator O which scales with momenta as $\mathcal{O}(p^{\hat{d}(O)})$ is said to be of chiral order $\hat{d} = \hat{d}(O)$, and the exponent \hat{d} is called the chiral dimension of O . Its value reflects

the infrared behaviour of O at low momenta and allows for a consistent power counting to organise the effective Lagrangian. In HEFT, the rules for chiral power counting are determined by the structure of the LO Lagrangian [29],[51]. In the discussion that follows, we will focus on the bosonic contribution, given in Eq. (3.61). For the NGB modes and h , we have $\hat{d}(h) = 0$ and $\hat{d}(U) = 0$, while their canonical field dimensions are compensated by the electroweak scale, v . Naturally, $\hat{d}(\partial_\mu) = 1$. Then, for the covariant derivatives it must be $\hat{d}(D_\mu) = 1$, enforcing $\hat{d}(\hat{W}_\mu) = 1$ and $\hat{d}(\hat{B}_\mu) = 1$, which in turn implies $\hat{d}(\hat{W}_{\mu\nu}) = 2$ and $\hat{d}(\hat{B}_{\mu\nu}) = 2$. We can also determine the chiral dimension of masses and gauge couplings. Since on shell particles satisfy $p^2 = m^2$, we have $\hat{d}(m) = 1$. The EW gauge couplings g and g' are proportional to the m_W and m_Z masses, as $m_W = gv/2$ and $m_Z = \sqrt{g^2 + g'^2}v/2$, then $\hat{d}(g) = 1$ and $\hat{d}(g') = 1$. Then, from Eq. (3.57), the chiral dimensions of the SM gauge fields are $\hat{d}(W_\mu) = 1$ and $\hat{d}(B_\mu) = 1$. The Higgs potential of Eq. (3.62) is requested to have chiral dimension 2, consistently with the fact that the cubic and quartic self-couplings are proportional to the Higgs mass.

Summing up, the rules for the chiral dimensions look as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u, U, \mathcal{F}(h), W_\mu, B_\mu &\sim \mathcal{O}(p^0), \\ D_\mu, \partial_\mu, \hat{W}_\mu, \hat{B}_\mu, g, g', m &\sim \mathcal{O}(p^1) \\ \hat{W}_{\mu\nu}, \hat{B}_{\mu\nu}, f_\pm^{\mu\nu}, c_n^{(V)} &\sim \mathcal{O}(p^2). \end{aligned} \tag{3.64}$$

Notably, chiral power counting preserves gauge invariance order by order: because the kinetic, cubic and quartic gauge terms have all chiral dimension = 2 [119]

- We consider the generalisation of Weinberg's power counting theorem. According to the chiral power counting, the contribution to scattering amplitudes is sorted out as a power expansion $T \sim \sum_k c_k p^k$, where p is the external momentum of the light particle.

3.8 Nambu-Goldstone equivalence theorem

The electroweak Nambu-Goldstone modes correspond to the longitudinal polarizations of the gauge bosons. Their scattering amplitudes are related by a result

known as *Nambu-Goldstone equivalence theorem* (NGET), or, shortly, *Equivalence Theorem* [52, 53, 10]. At LO, in the absence of the Higgs fields, in the limit where the energy of the center of mass of the process, \sqrt{s} , is much greater than the mass of the longitudinal gauge bosons, i.e. $\sqrt{s} \gg M_W$, it reads

$$T(V_L^{a_1}, V_L^{a_2}, V_L^{a_3}, \dots, V_L^{a_n}; X) = (-i)^n T(\omega^{a_1}, \omega^{a_2}, \omega^{a_3}, \dots, \omega^{a_n}; X) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{M_W}{\sqrt{s}}\right). \quad (3.65)$$

In the above equation, we have indicated with $V_L^{a_i}$ the longitudinal polarizations of the gauge bosons, and with ω^{a_i} the corresponding Nambu-Goldstone modes. The X denotes any other group of particles in the process. The $T(\dots)$ denotes the scattering amplitude, and the indices a_i are $SU(2)_L$ indices. Further discussions on the Equivalence Theorem can be found in Refs. [54], [55].

We remind here that custodial $SU(2)_L$ symmetry fixes the flavour tensor structure of elastic NGB scattering to

$$\mathcal{A}_{abcd}(\omega^a \omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c \omega^d) = A(s, t, u) \delta_{ab} \delta_{cd} + A(t, s, u) \delta_{ac} \delta_{bd} + A(u, t, s) \delta_{ad} \delta_{bc}, \quad (3.66)$$

with Bose (crossing) symmetry implying $A(x, y, z) = A(x, z, y)$. A single analytic function A thus governs the s , t and u channels.

We will use the Equivalence Theorem to calculate the scattering amplitude for the process $W_L^+ W_L^- \rightarrow Z_L Z_L h$, in terms of the process $\omega^+ \omega^- \rightarrow z z h$, in the limit $M_h^2, M_W^2, M_Z^2 \ll s < \Lambda^2$, where the masses of the EW gauge bosons and of the Higgs are neglected with respect to the center of mass energy \sqrt{s} ; the ultraviolet cutoff Λ sets the limits of applicability of the effective theory. In this case, the theorem reads

$$T(W_L^a W_L^b \rightarrow W_L^c W_L^d h) = T(\omega^a \omega^b h \rightarrow \omega^c \omega^d h) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{M_W}{\sqrt{s}}\right). \quad (3.67)$$

Hence, in what follows, longitudinal amplitudes are obtained from the corresponding Goldstone processes, up to suppressed mass and loop corrections.

Higgs production in VBS in HEFT in the ET approximation

In this chapter we study the process of scattering of longitudinal vector bosons with the production of one Higgs, $W_L^+ W_L^- \rightarrow Z_L Z_L h$, at energy scales $M_W^2 \ll s \ll \Lambda^2$. We conduct the analysis at leading order, in the framework of HEFT. We work in the approximation of the ET, carrying out the calculations of the scattering amplitude considering the much simpler process $\omega^+ \omega^- \rightarrow zz h$, i.e. replacing the longitudinal vector bosons with the WBGBs, neglecting $\mathcal{O}(M_W/\sqrt{s})$ effects. First we will work out a field redefinition for the relevant Lagrangian, which will allow to simplify the calculations of the scattering amplitudes. Then, we will compute the cross section, and compare it with the SMEFT prediction. We will study how hypothetical reductions of the uncertainty on this process, in combination with other multi boson processes, can potentially constrain further the a_1 and a_2 HEFT couplings appearing in the scalar Lagrangian of Eq. (3.61).

4.1 Conventions on the notation

Before starting the discussion, we clarify the notation and conventions that we will adopt throughout this chapter.

We write the WBGB matrix field as $\hat{\omega} \equiv \omega^a \sigma^a$, where the matrices σ^a are the Pauli matrices, and the indices $a = 1, 2, 3$ are flavour indices. The Pauli matrices satisfy the well-known commutation relations $[\sigma^a, \sigma^b] = 2i\epsilon^{abc}\sigma^c$, and $\{\sigma^a, \sigma^b\} = 2\delta^{ab}$ with ϵ^{abc} ($\epsilon^{123} = 1$) being the totally antisymmetric Levi-Civita symbol. We denote by ω^a the WBGB fields. We do not distinguish between upper

and lower indices: $\omega^a \equiv \omega_a$. The identity matrix in 2-dimensional space is denoted by $\mathbb{1}$, i.e. $\mathbb{1} \equiv \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$. Einstein summation convention is understood. Additionally, we adopt the following notation:

$$\begin{aligned}\omega &\equiv \sqrt{\omega^a \omega^a}, \\ \omega^2 &\equiv \omega^a \omega^a, \\ \omega^4 &\equiv (\omega^a \omega^a)^2,\end{aligned}\tag{4.1}$$

which results in the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\omega}^2 &= \hat{\omega} \hat{\omega} = \omega^2 \mathbb{1}, \\ \hat{\omega}^4 &= \hat{\omega} \hat{\omega} \hat{\omega} \hat{\omega} = \omega^4 \mathbb{1}\end{aligned}\tag{4.2}$$

For the operators, we adopt the following shorthand notations:

$$\begin{aligned}(\partial\omega)^2 &\equiv \partial_\mu \omega^a \partial^\mu \omega^a, \\ \omega \partial_\mu \omega &\equiv \omega^a \partial_\mu \omega^a, \\ (\omega \partial\omega)^2 &\equiv (\omega^a \partial_\mu \omega^a)(\omega^b \partial^\mu \omega^b).\end{aligned}\tag{4.3}$$

4.2 Relevant scalar canonical HEFT LO Lagrangian

We are interested in the leading order dynamics of the vector boson scattering (VBS) process $W_L W_L \rightarrow ZZ h$ at energy scales $M_W^2 \ll s \ll \Lambda_{\text{NP}}^2$ (kinematic regime well over the production threshold), where Λ_{NP} is the scale of new physics and M_W^2 relates to the electroweak scale, in the framework of the Higgs Effective Field Theory (HEFT) and in the approximation of the Nambu-Goldstone equivalence theorem. In force of this, concretely, we will study the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$, where ω represents a WBGB, neglecting terms of order $\mathcal{O}(M_W/\sqrt{s})$ and focusing on the dynamics of the scalar degrees of freedom.

According to Weinberg's counting (Eq. (3.44)), the Feynman diagrams necessary to compute the LO amplitude are those with zero loops (i.e., tree level diagrams) and with any number of vertices of order 2 in chiral power counting, contained in the \mathcal{L}_2 contribution to the HEFT expansion of Eq. (3.51). Since our process involves only scalar particles in the external states, we select, in particular,

the scalar (bosonic) sector of \mathcal{L}_2 , which we already presented in Eq. (3.61). For our discussion it is convenient to adopt the formalism of the NGB matrix field $U(\hat{\omega})$, whose transformation properties under the global $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry are given in Eq. (3.33).

To study the scalar dynamics in the kinematical regime of our interest, we can make some simplifications to the Lagrangian of Eq. (3.61), which we present in the following.

The first simplification is setting the potential $V(h)$ of Eq. (3.62) to zero, as we now explain. At our energy ranges, the Higgs mass can be neglected ($M_h \sim M_W \sim 0$). Then we omit both the Higgs mass term and the Higgs self-interactions, encoded in the potential of Eq. (3.62), since they are proportional to M_h . Additionally, as the analysis remains at LO and focused on interactions involving at most two Higgs particles in the external states, we will not need the terms in the potential with $\lambda_{n>3} \rightarrow 0$, which account for Higgs self-interactions with a number of Higgs greater than three. In force of these considerations, we set the potential $V(h)$ of Eq. (3.62) to zero.

The second simplification is to consider partial derivatives instead of covariant ones: since our focus is on the scalar dynamics and the interactions between the Higgs and the WBGBs, we can neglect the couplings of the WBGB fields to the transverse EW gauge bosons. This is achieved by setting $g = g' = 0$ in the covariant derivatives defined in Eq. (3.58), considering the identifications of Eq. (3.57). The resulting Lagrangian then reads

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{HEFT LO}}^{(\text{scalar})} = \frac{v^2}{4} \mathcal{F}(h) \text{Tr} \left((\partial_\mu U)^\dagger \partial^\mu U \right) + \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu h \partial^\mu h, \quad (4.4)$$

where the flare function $\mathcal{F}(h)$ is given in Eq. (3.63). We remark that this Lagrangian is that of Eq. (3.61), but with the potential $V(h)$ set to zero, and with the covariant derivatives replaced by ordinary derivatives. From now on, we will refer to the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.4) simply as \mathcal{L} .

Moreover, we note that the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.4) resembles the derivative part of the Lagrangian of the non-linear sigma model, given in Eq. (3.12); however, in Eq. (4.4), the interactions between the Goldstone modes and the Higgs are now governed by the flare function $\mathcal{F}(h)$, giving rise to interactions $\omega^{2n_\omega} h^{n_h}$, i.e.

to vertices involving an arbitrary even number of WBGBs, $2n_\omega$, and any number of Higgs bosons, n_h , while Eq. (3.12) accounts for a far more limited number of interactions of that type, i.e. only with $n_h = 1, 2$, which can be recovered from Eq. (4.4) with the choice $a_1 = 2$, $a_2 = 1$, and $a_{n>2} = 0$ in the flare function of Eq. (3.63).

To analyze the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$, we require the explicit form of the Lagrangian expanded up to $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$. This involves selecting a suitable parametrization for the field $U(\hat{\omega})$ and expanding it in powers of $\hat{\omega}/v$ to the necessary order. In the following section, we will discuss this aspect in detail. We will work in the flavour basis, where the coordinates are the fields $\{\omega^1, \omega^2, \omega^3\}$, in terms of which $\omega^\pm = (\omega^1 \mp i\omega^2)/\sqrt{2}$ and $z = \omega^3$. We will generally indicate the process as $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d h$, where a, b, c, d are flavour indices, or $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$, suppressing the flavour indices.

4.3 General parametrization for the WBGB fields

To represent the unitary matrix $U(\hat{\omega})$, we adopt the family of parametrizations derived in Ref. [56], valid up to order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$:

$$U(\hat{\omega}; \eta) = \mathbf{1} + \frac{i\hat{\omega}}{v} + \frac{\omega^2}{2v^2} + \eta \frac{i\omega^2\hat{\omega}}{v^3} - \left(\eta + \frac{1}{8}\right) \frac{\omega^4}{v^4} + \mathcal{O}(\omega^5). \quad (4.5)$$

Here, we have used the notation of Eqs. (4.1) and Eq. (4.2), and η is a free real parameter accounting for the specific choice of parametrization, and it is the *only* parameter needed up to order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$. Then, up to this order, the parametrization of Eq. (4.5) is the most general one that respects the conditions of unitarity ($U^\dagger U = U U^\dagger = \mathbf{1}$), analyticity, and independence on the specific choice of η up to linear order in the expansion of $U(\hat{\omega})$, satisfying the requirement of Eq. (3.34). The construction of this parametrization is showed in Appendix A.

By setting $\eta = 0$, one recovers the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ expansion of the familiar *spherical* parameterization,

$$U(\hat{\omega}) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2}{v^2}} + i \frac{\hat{\omega}}{v}, \quad (4.6)$$

while by setting $\eta = -\frac{1}{6}$ one recovers the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ expansion of the familiar *expo-*

ventional parametrization,

$$U(\hat{\omega}) = \exp\left\{i\frac{\hat{\omega}}{v}\right\}. \quad (4.7)$$

The choice does not affect the results for the physical observables: we use the general parametrization of Eq. (4.5) to explicitly show that the final results do not depend on η , as it should be. From now on, we will call the parametrization of Eq. (4.5) *general*. Further details can be found in Appendix A.

With Eq. (4.5), the LO HEFT Lagrangian up to order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ reads

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} = & \frac{1}{2}\partial_\mu h\partial^\mu h + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{F}(h)(\partial\omega)^2 \\ & + \frac{\mathcal{F}(h)}{2v^2} \left\{ (1+4\eta)(\omega\partial\omega)^2 + 2\eta\omega^2(\partial\omega)^2 \right\} \\ & + \mathcal{O}(\omega^6), \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

where we have employed the notation of Eqs. (4.1), (4.2), and (4.3). Indeed, the Lagrangian expressed in this form returns the already known results for the leading tree level scattering amplitudes of the processes $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d$ and $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow hh$, as we will discuss in the next section. After that, we will focus on the novel process $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d h$, which is the main focus of this work.

4.4 $2 \rightarrow 2$ processes at LO

The Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8) allows us to recover the well-known results for the scattering amplitudes for the elastic $2 \rightarrow 2$ WBGB scattering processes at leading order $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d$ and $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow hh$ [50]. We do not consider the process $hh \rightarrow hh$, as it receives contributions from our Lagrangian only at one-loop level.

We start with the process $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d$ at LO. The relevant Feynman diagrams stemming from Eq. (4.8) are depicted in Table (4.1), in Figs. (4.1a), (4.1b), (4.1c), (4.1d). Due to the underlying $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry, the scattering amplitude for the process $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d$ can be expressed in terms of a single channel function $A(s, t, u)$ as in Eq. (3.66), where s , t , and u are the Mandelstam

variables:

$$\begin{aligned} i\mathcal{A}(\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d) &= \\ &= iA_{2\omega 2\omega}(s, t, u)\delta_{ab}\delta_{cd} + iA_{2\omega 2\omega}(t, s, u)\delta_{ac}\delta_{bd} + iA_{2\omega 2\omega}(u, t, s)\delta_{ad}\delta_{bc}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

where

$$A^{2\omega 2\omega}(s, t, u) = \frac{s}{v^2} \left(1 - \frac{a_1^2}{4} \right). \quad (4.10)$$

At LO, the channel function $A_{2\omega 2\omega}$ depends only on the variable s . In the Standard Model, where $a_1 = 2$, the amplitude for the process vanishes. This cancellation relies on the presence of an Higgs sector and prevents the process from energy growth and perturbative unitarity violation [50]. In the absence of the Higgs, i.e. $a_1 \rightarrow 0$, the amplitude would lead to energy growth and subsequent perturbative unitarity violation; it is said that the Higgs boson *restores perturbative unitarity* for this process. When departures from the SM are allowed, the amplitude in Eq. (4.9) is more and more suppressed as a_1 gets closer to its SM value. However, even in the presence of the Higgs, cancellation effects do not occur, and exists a scale for unitarity breakdown [57].

We now turn to the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow hh$ at LO. The relevant Feynman diagrams from the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8) are depicted in Figs. Figs. (4.1e), (4.1f), (4.1g). In this case, we recover the result [49]

$$i\mathcal{A}_{ab}^{2\omega 2h} = iA_{2\omega 2h}(s, t, u)\delta_{ab}, \quad (4.11)$$

with

$$A_{2\omega 2h}(s, t, t) = -\frac{1}{v^2}s \left(a_2 - \left(\frac{a_1}{2} \right)^2 \right). \quad (4.12)$$

This LO amplitude is suppressed when $a_1/2 = a_2$, as it happens in the SM, which predicts this exact relation between the two parameters, with $a_1 = 2$ and $a_2 = 1$. Again, the Higgs boson in the SM is responsible for the suppression of the amplitude and the restoration of perturbative unitarity. This is not the case when a_1 and a_2 are independent parameters, and deviations from the SM relation between the two are allowed.

As we mentioned before, we do not discuss the process $hh \rightarrow hh$, as it receives contributions from our Lagrangian only at one-loop level.

Table 4.1: Feynman diagrams for the LO scattering amplitudes of the WBGBs and the light scalar h , predicted by the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8). In the first row, Figs. (4.1a), (4.1b), (4.1c), (4.1d) represent the diagrams contributing to LO $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega$. In the second row, Figs. (4.1e), (4.1f), (4.1g) represent the diagrams contributing to LO $\omega\omega \rightarrow hh$.

4.5 $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$ process at LO

Our attention will now turn to the scattering process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$. This reaction can be understood as the charged component of the more general process in the custodial (flavour) basis $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d h$, corresponding to its s -channel contribution. The suffixes a, b, c, d denote flavour indices. To maintain transparency in the discussion, we will first perform the calculation in the flavour basis, where the $SU(2)_L$ custodial symmetry structure of the theory is manifest. The relevant s -channel diagrams, which arise from the interaction terms in the effective Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8), are collected in Figure (4.2). Subsequently, we will convert the result into the charge basis. We assign momenta as (Lorentz indices are omitted)

$$\omega^a(p_a) + \omega^b(p_b) \rightarrow \omega^c(p_c) + \omega^d(p_d) + h(p_h), \quad (4.13)$$

Table 4.2: Feynman diagrams contributing to the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ (i.e., $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d h$ in the s -channel), stemming from the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8). The contributions are grouped in columns according to the couplings involved: from left to right, diagrams proportional to a_1 , in to $a_1 a_2$, and to a_1^3 . Dashed lines represent the Higgs boson, while solid lines represent the electroweak NGBs.

enforcing the global four-momentum conservation equation

$$p_a + p_b = p_c + p_d + p_h. \quad (4.14)$$

We label p_i the four-momenta of the ω_i , with $i = a, b, c, d$, and p_h the four-momentum of the field h .¹ Being all particles massless, the on-shell relations are $p_i^2 = 0 \forall i$, and $p_h^2 = 0$.

In order to describe the kinematics in the presence of an external h field, it is convenient to define the following set of generalized invariants:

$$s_h \equiv (p_a + p_b - p_h)^2 = (p_c + p_d)^2, \quad (4.15)$$

$$t_h \equiv (p_a - p_c - p_h)^2 = (p_d - p_b)^2, \quad (4.16)$$

$$u_h \equiv (p_a - p_d - p_h)^2 = (p_c - p_b)^2; \quad (4.17)$$

furthermore, we define

$$s \equiv (p_a + p_b)^2 = (p_c + p_d + p_h)^2, \quad (4.18)$$

$$t \equiv (p_a - p_c)^2 = (p_d - p_b + p_h)^2, \quad (4.19)$$

$$u \equiv (p_a - p_d)^2 = (p_c - p_b + p_h)^2. \quad (4.20)$$

Since all the external particles satisfy the on-shell relation $p^2 = 0$, the above relations also read

$$s_h = s - 2(p_a + p_b) \cdot p_h = 2p_c \cdot p_d, \quad (4.21)$$

$$t_h = t - 2(p_a - p_c) \cdot p_h = -2p_d \cdot p_b, \quad (4.22)$$

$$u_h = u - 2(p_a - p_d) \cdot p_h = -2p_b \cdot p_c. \quad (4.23)$$

Using the on-shell relation $p^2 = 0$ and the momentum conservation relation $p_a + p_b = p_c + p_d + p_h$ we find that s, t, u satisfy the following relation:

$$s + t + u = 2p_a \cdot p_h, \quad (4.24)$$

¹Here the notation can be misleading: the latin subscript i in p_i is just a label, while the latin subscript i in ω_i is a flavour index.

which implies the relation among s, t, u and s_h, t_h, u_h

$$s + s_h + t + t_h + u + u_h = 0. \quad (4.25)$$

There are two cases where the standard relation for massless particles, $s+t+u=0$, is recovered. First, in the higgsless limit, where $p_h \rightarrow 0$: in this case, $s_h \rightarrow s$, $t_h \rightarrow t$ and $u_h \rightarrow u$, implying $s_h + t_h + u_h = 0$. Second, when p_h is orthogonal to p_a : in this case, s_h, t_h and u_h do not reduce to the standard Mandelstam variables, but still satisfy the relation $s_h + t_h + u_h = 0$.

After the above premises, we are prepared to present the expression that we have derived for the scattering amplitude for our process. In terms of the flavour basis, it reads

$$\begin{aligned} i\mathcal{A}(\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d h) &= \\ &= iA(s, t, u; s_h, t_h, u_h)\delta_{ab}\delta_{cd} + iA(t, s, u; t_h, s_h, u_h)\delta_{ac}\delta_{bd} + \\ &\quad + iA(u, t, s; u_h, t_h, s_h)\delta_{ad}\delta_{bc}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

with $A(s, t, u; s_h, t_h, u_h)$ given by

$$A(s, s_h) = -\frac{s + s_h}{2v^3} \left[a_1 + a_1 a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2} \right]. \quad (4.27)$$

As we anticipated, the s -channel returns the amplitude for the charged $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$:

$$i\mathcal{A}(\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h) = iA(s, s_h) = -i\frac{s + s_h}{2v^3} \left[a_1 + a_1 a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2} \right]. \quad (4.28)$$

Eq. (4.28) can be understood as the sum of the contributions coming from diagrams involving different combinations of vertices,

$$A(s, s_h)|_{a_1} = -\frac{a_1}{2v^3} (s + s_h), \quad (4.29)$$

$$A(s, s_h)|_{a_1 a_2} = -\frac{a_1 a_2}{2v^3} (s + s_h), \quad (4.30)$$

$$A(s, s_h)|_{a_1^3} = \frac{a_1^3}{4v^3} (s + s_h); \quad (4.31)$$

specifically, Eq. (4.29) is given by the diagrams depicted in the first column

of Table (4.2), Eq. (4.30) is given by the diagrams depicted in the second row, and Eq. (4.31) is given by the diagrams depicted in the third row. Note that Eqs. (4.29), (4.30), (4.31) are *individually* η -independent, i.e., they are the same for every choice of parameterization for the $U(\hat{\omega})$ fields.

To obtain the result of Eq. (4.28) we had to compute eleven Feynman diagrams, those collected in Table (4.2). In the next section, we will illustrate how the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8), which originates those diagrams, can be “shaped” at our convenience by means of a redefinition of the fields h and ω , chosen for the calculation of the $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ to be more straightforward. This technique relies on the fact that the physical observables are not affected by change of coordinates, which are unphysical.

4.6 Redefinition of the relevant HEFT LO Lagrangian: a single vertex route to VBS + h

The Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8) generates eleven Feynman diagrams for the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ at LO, depicted in Table (4.2). Ten out of these diagrams present a vertex with three fields of the kind $\omega\omega h$, originated by the term in Eq. (4.8)

$$\mathcal{L} \supset \frac{a_1 h}{2v} (\partial\omega)^2. \quad (4.32)$$

Note that, since we are excluding the cubic Higgs self-interaction, this is the only kind of three-field vertex we can have. This is a relatively small number of diagrams to compute, and the calculation can be performed by hand, as we did; we presented the results in the previous section. But we have been lucky. In general, when dealing with a multi-boson process involving external Higgs bosons, the presence of interactions among three fields (such as those stemming from Eq. (4.32)), due to combinatorics, allows for a proliferation of Feynman diagrams topologies, introducing complications from a computational point of view, as discussed in Ref. [13].

If we were able to find a way of eliminating the term of Eq. (4.32) from the relevant Lagrangian, ten out of eleven topologies would be swept away, making

the calculation much easier. Could this be done by a choice of parametrization for the $U(\hat{\omega})$ matrices, i.e., by fixing the parameter η ? The answer is no: the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$ sector of Eq. (4.8) is independent of η .

A viable solution, instead, is resorting to the freedom that we have of choosing the coordinates of the $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ manifold: the calculation of the amplitude in Eq. (4.28) can be simplified by performing a non-linear field redefinition of the fields h and ω^a in Eq. (4.8) [58, 59, 60, 61, 36]. In fact, physical observables do not depend on the choice of coordinates, but only on geometric invariants (for instance, the curvature of field space, as discussed in Ref. [62]). In Ref. [13], the problem has been addressed for the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$ sector of Eq. (4.8), which is independent of the choice of parametrization, in view of the calculations of the amplitudes for $\omega\omega \rightarrow h^n$ fusion processes. A suitable transformation was found to eliminate the aforementioned three-field vertices and reduce the number of Feynman diagrams [63, 64].

Inspired by their work, we will retrace the steps of their construction and then explore the possibility of extending the transformation to the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ sector of the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8). The adoption of the general parametrization for the $U(\hat{\omega})$ fields (Eq. (4.5)) allows to maintain the discussion general: we just ask for the parametrization to be analytical and sufficiently regular. Our goal is to simplify the computation of the $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$ amplitude, in a way that can serve not only for LO computations, but also for loop diagrams contributing at NLO, which are left for future work.

We consider the following family of nonlinear transformations of the fields h and ω^a :

$$\begin{cases} \omega^a \rightarrow \tilde{\omega}^a(\omega, h) \equiv \omega^a + G_1(h)\omega^a + G_2(h)\frac{\omega^2}{v^2}\omega^a, \\ h \rightarrow \tilde{h}(\omega, h) \equiv h + f_1(h)\frac{\omega^2}{v} + f_2(h)\frac{\omega^4}{v^3}. \end{cases} \quad (4.33)$$

The family is parameterized by the four scalar functions $G_1(h)$, $G_2(h)$, $f_1(h)$, $f_2(h)$, assumed to be analytical in h and to depend only on the Higgs scalar field h . In principle, the field redefinition in Eq. (4.33) can include derivative terms, e.g. proportional to $(\partial\omega)^2$, but we do not need to take them into account: since the original HEFT Lagrangian lacks mass terms and already includes operators with at most two derivatives, introducing derivative terms through the field redefinition

would generate operators with four derivatives in the resulting transformed Lagrangian, and these terms would be of chiral order four and then contribute only from NLO onwards. Our analysis, instead, focuses on the LO contributions to the process. Indeed, when writing down the transformation for a certain process at a certain order in power counting, we should question ourselves whether it is convenient or not to include terms with derivatives (the derivatives, in any case, should appear in an even number, otherwise the chiral counting would be spoiled). Our analysis serves as a particular case of a general machinery, suitable to be applied to other processes. Extending our objective to simplify the Lagrangian at loop level and for higher-order corrections may require a more general transformation that includes derivative terms.

Let's now turn to the determination of the transformation of Eq. (4.33). To this end, we need to find conditions to fix $G_{1,2}(h)$ and $f_{1,2}(h)$, suitable to simplify the calculations of the scattering amplitude for the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$.

To ensure that the transformation of Eq. (4.33) is non-singular, it must hold $G_1(h) \neq -1$ in the surroundings of $h \approx 0$. Furthermore, we ask $G_1(h) \sim \mathcal{O}(h^1)$, which is equivalent to imposing the boundary condition

$$G_1(h)|_{h=0} = 0. \quad (4.34)$$

This last requirement is not strictly necessary: its absence would amount to a rescaling of the ω^a at linear order.

Under the redefinition of Eq. 4.33, the flare function transforms as

$$\mathcal{F}(h) \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{F}}(h, \omega) \equiv \mathcal{F}(\tilde{h}(\omega, h)) \equiv \mathcal{F}\left(h + f_1(h)\frac{\omega^2}{v} + f_2(h)\frac{\omega^4}{v^3}\right); \quad (4.35)$$

considering $\Delta\tilde{h}(h, \omega) \equiv \frac{\omega^2}{v}f_1(h) + \frac{\omega^4}{v^3}f_2(h)$, we can Taylor expand $\mathcal{F}(\tilde{h})$ around h and reorganize the result in a series of even powers of ω :

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{F}}(h, \omega) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \mathcal{F}(h)^{(n)} \Delta\tilde{h}(\omega, h)^n \\ &\equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{F}_n(h) \omega^{2n} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_0(h) + \mathcal{F}_1(h) \omega^2 + \mathcal{F}_2(h) \omega^4 + \mathcal{O}(\omega^6). \end{aligned} \quad (4.36)$$

We identify $\mathcal{F}_0(h) \equiv \mathcal{F}(h)$, while $\mathcal{F}_1(h)$ and $\mathcal{F}_2(h)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}_1(h) &= \mathcal{F}_1(h, f_1(h)) = \frac{\mathcal{F}'(h)f_1(h)}{v}, \\ \mathcal{F}_2(h) &= \mathcal{F}_2(h, f_2(h), f_1(h)) = \frac{f_2(h)}{v^3}\mathcal{F}'(h) + \frac{1}{2}\frac{(f_1(h))^2}{v^2}\mathcal{F}''(h),\end{aligned}\tag{4.37}$$

where primes denotes total derivatives with respect to h . we will not consider $\mathcal{F}_2(h)$ further: since it contributes at order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ in the expansion of $\mathcal{F}(h)$ in Eq. (4.36), it will appear in the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^6)$ sector of the transformed Lagrangian, which is not relevant for our purposes.

The application of Eq. (4.33) to the operators in the canonical HEFT Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8) $O_{20} \equiv (\partial\omega)^2$, $O_{4a} \equiv (\omega\partial\omega)^2$ and $O_{4b} \equiv \omega^2(\partial\omega)^2$, and to the flare function $\mathcal{F}(h)$ (as in Eqs. (4.36) and (4.37)) gives rise to new structures: we retain the operators involving up to four ω 's, and we call them $O_{21} \equiv (\omega\partial_\mu\omega)\partial^\mu h$, $O_{22} \equiv \omega^2(\partial_\mu h)^2$, $O_{41} \equiv \omega^2(\omega\partial_\mu\omega)\partial^\mu h$, and $O_{42} \equiv \omega^4(\partial_\mu h)^2$. These involve up to two derivatives of h , and they appear accompanied by coefficients which depend on h through $\mathcal{F}(h)$, $f_1(h)$, $f_2(h)$, $G_1(h)$, and $G_2(h)$. In Table 4.3 we list all the operators involved up to order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ in the transformed Lagrangian, together with the explicit expressions of their accompanying coefficients.

After the field redefinition of Eq. (4.33), the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8) up to order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ can be organized as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_2 &= \frac{1}{2}\partial_\mu h\partial^\mu h + \\ &+ C_{20}(h)O_{20} + C_{21}(h)O_{21} + C_{22}(h)O_{22} \\ &+ C_{4a}(h)O_{4a} + C_{4b}(h)O_{4b} \\ &+ C_{41}(h)O_{41} + C_{42}(h)O_{42} \\ &+ \mathcal{O}(\omega^6).\end{aligned}\tag{4.38}$$

To simplify the notation, we label O_X the generic operator associated to the coefficient $C_X(h)$, where X indicates the label. The complete list of expressions for O_X and $C_X(h)$ is given in Table 4.3. We remark that the O_X 's can contain powers of ω , partial derivatives of ω , and partial derivatives of h , while the coefficients $C_X(h)$ are analytical functions of h , and they can depend on h directly or through the parameters of the transformation (f_1, f_2, G_1, G_2) . They can also

X	O_X	$C_X(h)$
20	$(\partial\omega)^2$	$\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)^2$
21	$(\omega\partial_\mu\omega)\partial^\mu h$	$\mathcal{F}G_1'(1+G_1) + \frac{2}{v}f_1$
22	$\omega^2\partial_\mu h\partial^\mu h$	$\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{F}(G_1')^2 + \frac{1}{v}f_1'$
4a	$(\omega\partial_\mu\omega)^2$	$\frac{2}{v^2}f_1^2 + \frac{2}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)G_2$ $+ \frac{1}{2v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)^4(1+4\eta)$
4b	$\omega^2(\partial\omega)^2$	$\frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)G_2 + \frac{1}{2v}\mathcal{F}'f_1(1+G_1)^2$ $+ \frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)^4\eta$
41	$\omega^2(\omega\partial_\mu\omega)\partial^\mu h$	$\frac{4}{v^3}f_2 + \frac{2}{v^2}f_1'f_1 + \frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)G_2'$ $+ \frac{3}{v^2}\mathcal{F}G_1'G_2 + \frac{1}{v}\mathcal{F}'f_1G_1'(1+G_1)$ $+ \frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)^3G_1'(1+6\eta)$
42	$\omega^4\partial_\mu h\partial^\mu h$	$\frac{1}{v^3}f_2' + \frac{1}{2v^2}(f_1')^2 + \frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}G_1'G_2'$ $+ \frac{1}{2v}\mathcal{F}'f_1(G_1')^2 + \frac{1}{2v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)^2G_1'(1+6\eta)$

Table 4.3: List of the explicit expressions of the operators O_X and their coefficients $C_X(h)$ appearing in the Lagrangian of Eq. 4.38. Note that O_{20} , O_{4a} and O_{4b} were already present in Eq. (4.8), but accompanied by different coefficients. The dependence on h of \mathcal{F} , G_1 , G_2 , f_1 , and f_2 is understood.

depend on the parametrization for the $U(\hat{\omega})$ fields, codified by η , so that they can be understood as

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{2i}(h) &\equiv C_{2i}(h, f_1(h), G_1(h)) \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \\
 C_{4j}(h) &\equiv C_{4j}(h, f_1(h), f_2(h), G_1(h), G_2(h); \eta) \quad j = a, b, 1, 2,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.39}$$

remarking that the dependence on η , $G_2(h)$, $f_2(h)$ appears only at order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$, while $f_1(h)$ and $G_1(h)$ appear at both orders. This was expected, both from the structure of the field redefinition of Eq. (4.33), and from the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$ sector of the

original Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8), which is independent of η as a consequence of the requirement of Eq. (3.34), which says that all parameterization for $U(\hat{\omega})$ must be the same at linear order in the expansion in ω .

The expansion of $C_X(h)$ in the vicinity of $h \approx 0$ can be formally written as

$$C_X(h) = C_X^{(0)} + C_X^{(1)}h + C_X^{(2)}h^2 + \mathcal{O}(h^3). \quad (4.40)$$

To proceed systematically in the determination of the functions f_1 , f_2 , G_1 , and G_2 , we will first fix the transformation parameters by setting conditions for the coefficients at order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$; after that, we will implement the results at order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ and set further conditions to fix the remaining free functions.

4.6.1 $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$ sector

In Ref. [13], the authors worked out the field redefinition corresponding to Eq. (4.33) with $f_2(h) = 0$ and $g_2(h) = 0$, in order to simplify the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$ sector of the canonical HEFT LO Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8). Here, we will ensure that our transformation in Eq. 4.33 is consistent with their results, which serve both as a reference and as a consistency check for our calculations.

In order to eliminate the interactions involving three fields, we choose to set the following conditions:

$$C_{20}^{(1)} = 0, \quad (4.41)$$

$$C_{21}(h) = 0, \quad (4.42)$$

$$C_{22}(h) = 0. \quad (4.43)$$

Note that the coefficient $C_{20}(h)$, associated to the operator $O_{20} = (\partial\omega)^2$, cannot be made zero at all orders, as this would violate the condition $G_1(h) \neq -1$. Then, in Eq. (4.41), we just set a condition on the $\mathcal{O}(h)$ coefficient, i.e. $C_{20}^{(1)} = 0$, which is what we need to completely eliminate the three-field vertices, which are produced by the term proportional to $C_{20}^{(1)}h(\partial\omega)^2$ in the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.38). On the other hand, we are allowed to set the conditions of Eqs. (4.42) and (4.43), such that $C_{21}(h)$ and $C_{22}(h)$, given in Table 4.3, are made zero at all orders in h and the "spurious" operators O_{21} and O_{22} introduced with the field redefinition are

eliminated from the Lagrangian.

We proceed as follows. From Eqs. (4.42) and (4.42) we find an expression for $f_1(h)$ in terms of $G'_1(h)$ and $G_1(h)$, and a differential equation for $G'_1(h)$:

$$f_1(h) = -\frac{v}{2}\mathcal{F}(h)G'_1(h)(1 + G_1(h)) \quad (4.44)$$

$$\mathcal{F}'(h)G'_1(h) = -\mathcal{F}(h)G_1(h); \quad (4.45)$$

solving for $G'_1(h)$, we find

$$f_1(h) = -\frac{v}{2}\tilde{\mathcal{N}}(1 + G_1(h)) \quad (4.46)$$

$$G'_1(h) = \tilde{\mathcal{N}}\mathcal{F}^{-1}(h); \quad (4.47)$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}$ is an integration constant, which we can rewrite as $\tilde{\mathcal{N}} = -\frac{2\mathcal{N}}{v}$, with \mathcal{N} a constant. Then, finally, we have

$$f_1(h) = \mathcal{N}(1 + G_1(h)) \quad (4.48)$$

$$G'_1(h) = -\frac{2}{v}\mathcal{N}\mathcal{F}^{-1}(h). \quad (4.49)$$

We can find the expression for $G_1(h)$ order by order in h by expanding $\mathcal{F}(h)^{-1}$ and then integrating with the boundary condition for $G_1(h)$ given in Eq. (4.34). We find

$$G_1(h) = -\frac{2\mathcal{N}}{v} \int_0^h \mathcal{F}(h)^{-1} = -2\mathcal{N}\frac{h}{v} + \mathcal{N}a_1\frac{h^2}{v^2} + \frac{2\mathcal{N}}{3}(a_2 - a_1^2)\frac{h^3}{v^3} + \mathcal{O}(h^3). \quad (4.50)$$

Now that we have an explicit expression for $G_1(h)$, we can write the expansion of $C_{20}(h)$ in powers of h :

$$C_{20}(h) = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{F}(h)(1 + G_1)^2 = C_{20}^{(0)} + C_{20}^{(1)}h + C_{20}^{(2)}h^2 + C_{20}^{(3)}h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4), \quad (4.51)$$

where, using the explicit expression for $G_1(h)$ of Eq. (4.50), the coefficients read

$$C_{20}^{(0)} = \frac{1}{2}, \quad (4.52)$$

$$C_{20}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{2v} (-4\mathcal{N} + a_1), \quad (4.53)$$

$$C_{20}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2v^2} (a_2 - 2a_1\mathcal{N} + 4\mathcal{N}^2), \quad (4.54)$$

$$C_{20}^{(3)} = \frac{1}{2v^3} a_3 + \frac{\mathcal{N}}{3v^3} (a_1^2 - 4a_2). \quad (4.55)$$

We now use Eq. (4.41) to fix the integration constant \mathcal{N} to ²

$$\mathcal{N} = \frac{a_1}{4} \equiv \bar{\mathcal{N}}. \quad (4.56)$$

We give the expansions for $f_1(h)$ and $G_1(h)$, which are now fully determined, up to $\mathcal{O}(h^3)$:

$$f_1(h) = \frac{a_1}{4} - \frac{a_1^2 h}{8v} + \frac{a_1 h^2}{16v^2} + \left(\frac{a_1^2 a_2}{24} - \frac{a_1^4}{24} \right) \frac{h^3}{v^3} + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \equiv \bar{f}_1(h), \quad (4.57)$$

$$G_1(h) = \frac{a_1 h}{2v} + \frac{a_1^2 h^2}{4v^2} + \left(\frac{a_1 a_2}{6} - \frac{a_1^3}{6} \right) \frac{h^3}{v^3} + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \equiv \bar{G}_1(h). \quad (4.58)$$

We stress that fixing \mathcal{N} as in Eq. (4.56) is an arbitrary choice; for instance, we could have used instead the condition $C_{20}^{(2)} = 0$. Nevertheless, our election of $C_{20}^{(1)} = 0$ is the useful one for our purposes. With our choice, the coefficient $C_{20}(h)$ contributes, up to order $\mathcal{O}(h^3)$, as

$$C_{20}(h) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(a_2 - \frac{a_1^2}{4} \right) \frac{h^2}{v^2} + \left(\frac{a_1^3}{12} - \frac{1}{3} a_1 a_2 + \frac{1}{2} a_3 \right) \frac{h^3}{v^3} + \mathcal{O}(h^4). \quad (4.59)$$

We check that the coefficient $C_{20}^{(2)}$ (whose expression is given by the $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ term in the above Eq. (4.59)) returns the scattering amplitude for the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow hh$,

²In terms of the flare function, we can also write $\mathcal{N} = \frac{vF'(0)}{4}$.

X	O_X	$C_X(h)$
20	$(\partial\omega)^2$	$\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{F}(1+G_1)^2$
21	$(\omega\partial_\mu\omega)\partial^\mu h$	0
22	$\omega^2\partial_\mu h\partial^\mu h$	0
4a	$(\omega\partial_\mu\omega)^2$	$\frac{2}{v^2}\bar{\mathcal{N}}^2(1+\bar{G}_1)^2 + \frac{2}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+\bar{G}_1)G_2$ $+ \frac{1}{2v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+\bar{G}_1)^4(1+4\eta)$
4b	$\omega^2(\partial\omega)^2$	$\frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+\bar{G}_1)G_2 + \frac{1}{2v}\mathcal{F}'\bar{\mathcal{N}}(1+\bar{G}_1)^3$ $+ \frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+\bar{G}_1)^4\eta$
41	$\omega^2(\omega\partial_\mu\omega)\partial^\mu h$	$\frac{4}{v^3}f_2 + \frac{1}{v^2}\mathcal{F}(1+\bar{G}_1)G'_2 - \frac{6}{v^3}\bar{\mathcal{N}}G_2$ $- \frac{4}{v^3}\bar{\mathcal{N}}^3\mathcal{F}^{-1}(1+\bar{G}_1) - \frac{2}{v^2}\bar{\mathcal{N}}^2\mathcal{F}'\mathcal{F}^{-1}(1+\bar{G}_1)^2$ $- \frac{2}{v^3}\bar{\mathcal{N}}(1+\bar{G}_1)^3(1+6\eta)$
42	$\omega^4\partial_\mu h\partial^\mu h$	$\frac{1}{v^3}f'_2 - \frac{2}{v^3}\bar{\mathcal{N}}G'_2 + \frac{2}{v^4}\bar{\mathcal{N}}^4\mathcal{F}^{-2}$ $+ \frac{2}{v^3}\bar{\mathcal{N}}^3\mathcal{F}'\mathcal{F}^{-2}(1+\bar{G}_1)$ $+ \frac{2}{v^4}\bar{\mathcal{N}}^2(1+\bar{G}_1)^2\mathcal{F}^{-1}(1+6\eta)$

Table 4.4: List of the explicit expressions of the operators O_X and their coefficients $C_X(h)$ appearing in the Lagrangian of Eq. 4.61. We use $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ and \bar{G}_1 to remind that these are fixed to the results for \mathcal{N} and $G_1(h)$ given in Eq. (4.58) and Eq. (4.56), respectively. We have used Eq. (4.49) to eliminate $G'_1(h)$ in favor of \mathcal{F}^{-1} and $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$. The dependence on h of \mathcal{F} , \bar{G}_1 , G_2 , and f_2 is understood.

given in Eqs. (4.11) and (4.12), as it should be:

$$A_{2\omega 2h}(s, t, u) = -2C_{20}^{(2)}s = -\left(a_2 - \left(\frac{a_1}{2}\right)^2\right)s. \quad (4.60)$$

The Lagrangian of Eq. (4.38) now reads

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_2 = & \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu h \partial^\mu h + \\
 & + C_{20}(h) O_{20} \\
 & + C_{4a}(h) O_{4a} + C_{4b}(h) O_{4b} \\
 & + C_{41}(h) O_{41} + C_{42}(h) O_{42} \\
 & + \mathcal{O}(\omega^6).
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.61}$$

The expressions for $C_X(h)$, with $X = 20, 4a, 4b, 41, 42$, are given in Table 4.4. We note that, in Eq. (4.61), the contributions from O_{21} and O_{22} , which were at first introduced through the redefinition of the fields, are no longer present; $C_{20}(h)$ is given by Eq. (4.59), so that linear terms in h at order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$ are absent, and the coefficients $C_{4a}(h)$, $C_{4b}(h)$, $C_{41}(h)$, and $C_{42}(h)$ are understood as functions of h , $f_2(h)$, $G_2(h)$, and the parameter η representing the parameterization. In the next subsection, we will set conditions on these coefficients to fix $f_2(h)$ and $G_2(h)$.

4.6.2 $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ sector

In this subsection, we assume for $G_1(h)$ and $f_1(h)$ the expressions given in Eqs. (4.58) and (4.48), respectively, which ensure the elimination of the three-field vertices from the Lagrangian. We now turn our attention to the $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ sector of the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.61), which contains the operators O_{4a} , O_{4b} , O_{41} , and O_{42} , with coefficients $C_{4a}(h)$, $C_{4b}(h)$, $C_{41}(h)$, and $C_{42}(h)$, respectively, all given in Table (4.3). These coefficients depend on the functions $f_2(h)$ and $G_2(h)$, which are still undetermined, and on the parameter η , which represents the parameterization, with the exception of $C_{42}(h)$ (which, anyway, is not involved in our process), the only η -independent parameter at order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$. We observe that $C_{4a}(h)$ and $C_{4b}(h)$ depend on $G_2(h)$, while $C_{41}(h)$ and $C_{42}(h)$ depend on both $G_2(h)$ and $f_2(h)$. We want to use the freedom to choose $f_2(h)$ and $G_2(h)$ to set conditions on these coefficients, in order to simplify the calculation of the scattering amplitude for the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$.

We proceed as follows. First of all, we observe that the term $C_{4b}(h)O_{4b}$ in

Eq. (4.61) can be rewritten, by partial integration, as

$$C_{4b}(h)O_{4b} = -2C_{4b}(h)O_{4a} - C'_{4b}(h)O_{41} - C_{4b}(h) \left(\omega^2 \omega^a \partial_\mu \partial^\mu \omega^a \right) + \partial_\mu \left(C_{4b}(h) \omega^2 (\partial\omega)^2 \right); \quad (4.62)$$

Substituting Eq. (4.62) in Eq. (4.61), we find the combinations of coefficients $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$ and $\tilde{C}_{41}(h)$ multiplying the operators O_{4a} and O_{41} , respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C}_{4a}(h) &\equiv C_{4a}(h, G_2, \eta) - 2C_{4b}(h, G_2, \eta), \\ \tilde{C}_{41}(h) &\equiv C_{41}(h, f_2, G_2, \eta) - C'_{4b}(h, \eta), \end{aligned} \quad (4.63)$$

which explicitly read

$$\tilde{C}_{4a}(h) = \frac{2\bar{\mathcal{N}}^2}{v^2} (1 + \bar{G}_1)^2 + \frac{1}{2v^2} \mathcal{F} (1 + \bar{G}_1)^4 - \frac{\bar{\mathcal{N}}}{v} \mathcal{F}' (1 + \bar{G}_1)^3, \quad (4.64)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C}_{41}(h) &= \frac{4}{v^3} f_2 - \frac{2\bar{\mathcal{N}}}{v^3} (1 + 2\eta) (1 + G_1)^3 - \frac{4\bar{\mathcal{N}}}{v^3} G_2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{v^2} \eta \mathcal{F}' (1 + G_1)^4 - \frac{1}{v^2} \mathcal{F}' (1 + G_1) G_2 - \frac{4\bar{\mathcal{N}}^3}{v^3} \mathcal{F}' \mathcal{F}^{-1} (1 + G_1) \\ &\quad + \frac{\bar{\mathcal{N}}^2}{v^2} \mathcal{F}' \mathcal{F}^{-1} (1 + G_1)^2 - \frac{\bar{\mathcal{N}}}{2v} \mathcal{F}'' (1 + G_1)^3. \end{aligned} \quad (4.65)$$

In the above Eqs. (4.64), (4.65), we have written $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ and \bar{G}_1 in order to indicate that these quantities are fixed as in Eqs. (4.58) and (4.56).

With these rearrangements, the Lagrangian reads

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_2 &= \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu h \partial^\mu h \\ &\quad + C_{20}(h) O_{20} \\ &\quad + \tilde{C}_{4a}(h) O_{4a} + \tilde{C}_{41}(h) O_{41} + C_{42}(h) O_{42} \\ &\quad - C_{4b}(h) \left(\omega^2 \omega^a \partial_\mu \partial^\mu \omega^a \right) + \partial_\mu \left(C_{4b}(h) \omega^2 (\omega \partial^\mu \omega) \right) \\ &\quad + \mathcal{O}(\omega^6). \end{aligned} \quad (4.66)$$

The expressions for $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$, $\tilde{C}_{41}(h)$ are given in Eqs. (4.64) and (4.65), while the expressions for $\tilde{C}_{4b}(h)$ and $C_{42}(h)$ are given in Table 4.4.

We note that $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$ is independent of G_2 , f_2 , and completely determined by the fixation of G_1 (Eq. (4.58)) and \mathcal{N} , (Eq. (4.56)) respectively. Furthermore,

$\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$ does not depend on η , meaning that it is not affected by the parametrization chosen for $U(\hat{\omega})$. Then, we do not have freedom to set $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$ to zero, and we will necessarily take into account the corresponding operator O_{4a} when calculating the scattering amplitude. This was expected, since the operator O_{4a} is present in the original Lagrangian and is not generated by the field redefinition: it is a "physical" operator. We have freedom, instead, to set to zero the coefficients $C_{4b}(h)$ and $\tilde{C}_{41}(h)$, which depend on $G_2(h)$ and $f_2(h)$, respectively,

$$\begin{cases} C_{4b}(h; G_2(h), \eta) = 0 \\ \tilde{C}_{41}(h; f_2(h), G_2(h)) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (4.67)$$

Note that the second condition, from Eq. (4.63), amounts to asking $C_{41}(h) = 0$. We proceed as follows: from the first condition in Eq. (4.67) we determine $G_2(h)$, and then, substituting into the second condition, we determine $f_2(h)$. We obtain

$$G_2(h; \eta) = -\eta (1 + \bar{G}_1)^3 - \frac{v\bar{\mathcal{N}}}{2} \mathcal{F}^{-1} \mathcal{F}' (1 + \bar{G}_1)^2 \quad (4.68)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_2(h) = & \bar{\mathcal{N}}^3 (1 + \bar{G}_1) \mathcal{F}^{-1} - \frac{3}{4} \bar{\mathcal{N}}^2 (1 + \bar{G}_1)^2 v \mathcal{F}' \mathcal{F}^{-1} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\mathcal{N}} (1 + \bar{G}_1)^3 \left[1 - \frac{v^2}{4} (\mathcal{F}')^2 \mathcal{F}^{-1} + \frac{v^2}{4} \mathcal{F}'' \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4.69)$$

where $\bar{G}_1(h)$ and $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ are understood to be given by Eqs. (4.58) and (4.56) respectively. Note that $G_2(h)$ depends on η , i.e. on the choice of parametrization of $U(\omega^a)$. Furthermore, the coefficient $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$, associated to the operator O_{4a} already present in the initial Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8), does not depend on $G_2(h)$, thus neither on η .

At this point, no freedom is left in our field redefinition, which is completely fixed. We give the expansions of $G_2(h; \eta)$ and $f_2(h)$ in powers of h , up to order

$\mathcal{O}(h^3)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_2(h) = & -\left(\frac{1}{8}a_1^2 + \eta\right) + \frac{1}{8}a_1(2a_1^2 - 2a_2 + 12\eta)\frac{h}{v} \\
 & - \left(\frac{1}{8}a_1\left(\frac{11}{4}a_1^3 - 5a_1a_2 + 3a_3\right) + \frac{3}{2}a_1^2\eta\right)\frac{h^2}{v^2} \\
 & + \left[\frac{1}{24}a_1\left(10a_1^4 - \frac{53}{2}a_1^2a_2 + 6a_2^2 + 21a_1a_3 - 12a_4\right) \right. \\
 & \left. + 2\eta\left(\frac{11}{16}a_1^3 - \frac{1}{4}a_1a_2\right)\right]\frac{h^3}{v^3} + \mathcal{O}(h^4), \tag{4.70}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_2(h) = & \frac{1}{16}a_1(2 - a_1^2 + a_2) + \frac{1}{128}a_1(19a_1^3 - 8a_1(3 + 5a_2) + 24a_3)\frac{h}{v} \\
 & \left(-\frac{1}{128}a_1\left(29a_1^4 - 12a_1^2(2 + 7a_2) + 78a_1a_3 + 16(a_2^2 - 3a_4)\right)\right)h^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{384}a_1\left(113a_1^5 - 2a_1^3(33 + 208a_2) + 420a_1^2a_3 + 24a_1(a_2 + 9a_2^2 - 16a_4) \right. \\
 & \left. + 48(-3a_2a_3 + 5a_5)\right)\frac{h^3}{v^3} + \mathcal{O}(h^4). \tag{4.71}
 \end{aligned}$$

We see that $G_2(h; \eta) \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$, whereas $f_2(h) \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$ is independent on η . After all these considerations, the Lagrangian of Eq. (4.66) simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\text{HEFT}} = & \frac{1}{2}\partial_\mu h \partial^\mu h + \\
 & + O_{20}C_{20}(h) + \\
 & + O_{4a}\tilde{C}_{4a}(h) + O_{42}C_{42}(h) \\
 & + \mathcal{O}(\omega^6). \tag{4.72}
 \end{aligned}$$

In what follows, we give the Taylor expansions of the coefficients $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$ and $C_{42}(h)$ (See Table 4.4) in powers of h , which help up to understand how combinations of the parameters of the flare function contribute to the scattering amplitudes of different processes. Formally, we write

$$\tilde{C}_{4a}(h) = \tilde{C}_{4a}^{(0)} + \tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}h + \tilde{C}_{4a}^{(2)}h^2 + \mathcal{O}(h^3), \tag{4.73}$$

where the coefficients $\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(0,1,2)}$ are constants in h , and read

$$\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(0)} = \frac{1}{2v^2} \left(1 - \frac{a_1^2}{4} \right), \quad (4.74)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)} = -\frac{1}{2v^3} \left(a_1 + a_1 a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2v^3} \right), \quad (4.75)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(2)} = \frac{-9a_1^4 + 8a_1^2(3a_2 + 1) - 24a_1 a_3 + 16a_2}{32v^4}. \quad (4.76)$$

Proceeding analogously, for $C_{42}(h)$ we formally write

$$C_{42}(h) = C_{42}^{(0)} + C_{42}^{(1)}h + C_{42}^{(2)}h^2 + \mathcal{O}(h^3), \quad (4.77)$$

where the coefficients $C_{42}^{(0)}, C_{42}^{(1)}, C_{42}^{(2)}$ are constants in h and read

$$C_{42}^{(0)} = \frac{a_1}{16v^4} \left(a_1^3 - a_1(3a_2 + 1) + 3a_3 \right), \quad (4.78)$$

$$C_{42}^{(1)} = \frac{a_1}{64v^5} \left(13a_1^4 - 8a_1^2(6a_2 + 1) + 54a_1 a_3 + 16 \left(a_2^2 - 3a_4 \right) \right), \quad (4.79)$$

$$C_{42}^{(2)} = \frac{a_1}{128v^6} \left(53a_1^5 - 2a_1^3(117a_2 + 11) + 264a_1^2 a_3 + 8a_1 \left(21a_2^2 + a_2 - 36a_4 \right) + 48(5a_5 - 3a_2 a_3) \right). \quad (4.80)$$

In particular, $\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(0)}$ is directly linked to the LO amplitude for tree level $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega$, while $\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}$ is related to the LO amplitude for tree level $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$, i.e. the process we are interested in; before proceeding, we stop to make a few comments on what we have done so far.

First, note that the contribution of the operator O_{41} vanishes in on-shell calculations, due to local conservation of momentum at vertex and the NGBs being massless. The elimination of O_{41} simplifies some one-loop calculations for processes involving $\omega^4 h$ vertices (our process included), making O_{4a} the only operator accommodating four NGBs and one Higgs. In Figure 4.1 are depicted some topologies of one loop diagrams for $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$. It can be seen that in two of them O_{41} would contribute, if present in the Lagrangian.

Second, we could have proceeded in a different way to fix the transformation. For example, we could have asked $C_{42}(h) = 0$ and $C_{41}(h) = 0$ in Eq. (4.61), in order to remove the operators O_{42} and O_{41} from the Lagrangian, introduced

Figure 4.1: Topologies of the one loop diagrams contributing to the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$. Dashed lines represent the Higgs, while solid lines represent the ω fields. In principle, the first two would involve the operator O_{41} .

through the field redefinition. Following this path, we could have extracted $f_2(h)$ from the condition $C_{41}(h) = 0$ and then, substituting into $C_{42}(h)$, obtained a differential equation of the second order for $G_2(h)$; the two initial conditions needed to solve it could have been fixed, for example, by asking $C_{4b}^{(1)} = 0$ and $C_{4b}^{(0)} = 0$ in the expansion of $C_{4b}(h)$ in powers of h . However, the results for the observables would have been the same, since the scattering amplitudes do not depend on the field redefinition.

Another possibility was asking $C_{4b} = 0$ and $C_{41} = 0$ directly in Eq. (4.61), without performing the partial integration of Eq. (4.62). In this case, we would have obtained the same results for $G_2(h)$ and $f_2(h)$, for the coefficients $C_{42}(h)$ and $C_{4a}(h)$, and, again, for the scattering amplitudes.

With this approach, the $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ symmetry is no longer explicit as in Eq. (4.8): the symmetry transformations are more involved in the form of Eq. (4.72). We note that the function $C_{20}(h)$, whose expansion is given in Eq. (4.59), could appear as an "effective" flare function, but the effective couplings that it codifies are valid only at order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^2)$. At order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$, after our redefinition, the two operators O_{4a} and O_{42} contribute in different ways to the coupling with the h field, through the functions $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$ and $C_{42}(h)$, and so on at higher orders in ω . Anyway, field redefinitions are a tool to simplify the calculation of observables, and the choice of the transformation should be made according to the specific process of interest. Field redefinitions can be of particular help to simplify loop calculations, where the number of diagrams can be very high [13].

We conclude this section giving the relevant contribution for the leading order tree level $\omega^a\omega^b \rightarrow \omega^c\omega^d h$, the object of our study. After all the simplifications, the relevant terms in Eq. (4.72) read

$$\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\omega^4 h} = \tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)} O_{4a} h = -\frac{1}{2v^3} \left(a_1 + a_1 a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2v^3} \right) (\omega \partial_\mu \omega)^2 h, \quad (4.81)$$

where $\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}$, from Eq. (4.75), is the effective $\omega^4 h$ coupling. In fact, $\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}$ depends on both a_1 and a_2 : in the original Lagrangian (Eq. 4.8), a_2 was associated to the $\omega\omega hh$ vertex, and contributed at tree-level appearing in diagrams involving also a_1 three-field vertices, as can be seen in Table 4.2. After applying the redefinition of Eq. (4.33) and fixing its parameter functions as we did, these diagrams are no longer present, and their contribution is absorbed by the modified coefficients. We note also that $\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}$ is independent on η (the coefficient $\tilde{C}_{4a}(h)$ is independent on η at all orders), meaning that the choice of parametrization does not affect the amplitude, as it should be. This serves also as a consistency check for our calculations. We now switch to the charge basis, where the charged ω^\pm and neutral z fields are collected in the matrix

$$\hat{\omega} = \omega^a \sigma^a = \begin{pmatrix} z & \sqrt{2}\omega^+ \\ \sqrt{2}\omega^- & -z \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.82)$$

with $\omega^\pm = \omega^1 \mp i\omega^2$ and $\omega^3 = z$. In Table (4.5) are given the expressions in this basis for the operators defined in Table 4.3.

The contribution for the specific process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$ is contained in Eq. (4.81) and given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\omega^4 h} \supset \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\omega^+\omega^- z^2 h} &= \tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)} \partial_\mu (z^2) \partial^\mu (\omega^+\omega^-) \\ &= \tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)} (2z\partial_\mu z\omega^- \partial^\mu \omega^+ + 2z\partial_\mu z\omega^+ \partial^\mu \omega^-). \end{aligned} \quad (4.83)$$

In the next sections, we address the computation of the scattering amplitude and cross sections for this process.

X	$O_X(\omega^a)$	$O_X(\omega^\pm, z)$
20	$(\partial_\mu \omega^a)^2$	$2\partial_\mu \omega^- \partial^\mu \omega^+ + (\partial z)^2$
21	$(\omega \partial_\mu \omega) \partial^\mu h$	$\omega^+ \partial_\mu \omega^- \partial^\mu h + \omega^- \partial_\mu \omega^+ \partial^\mu h + z \partial_\mu z \partial^\mu h$
22	$\omega^2 (\partial_\mu h)^2$	$2\omega^+ \omega^- (\partial h)^2 + z^2 (\partial h)^2$
4a	$(\omega \partial_\mu \omega)^2$	$(\omega^+ \partial \omega^-)^2 + (\omega^- \partial \omega^+)^2 + 2\omega^- \omega^+ \partial_\mu \omega^+ \partial^\mu \omega^-$ $+ z^2 (\partial z)^2 + 2z \partial_\mu z \omega^- \partial^\mu \omega^+ + 2z \partial_\mu z \omega^+ \partial^\mu \omega^-$
4b	$\omega^2 (\partial_\mu \omega)^2$	$4\omega^- \omega^+ \partial_\mu \omega^- \partial^\mu \omega^+ + 2z^2 \partial_\mu \omega^- \partial^\mu \omega^+$ $+ 2\omega^- \omega^+ (\partial z)^2 + z^2 (\partial z)^2,$
41	$\omega^2 (\omega \partial_\mu \omega) \partial^\mu h$	$2(\omega^+)^2 \omega^- \partial_\mu \omega^- \partial^\mu h + 2(\omega^-)^2 \omega^+ \partial_\mu \omega^+ \partial^\mu h$ $+ 2\omega^+ \omega^- z \partial_\mu z \partial^\mu h$ $+ z^2 \omega^- \partial_\mu \omega^+ \partial^\mu h + z^2 \omega^+ \partial_\mu \omega^- \partial^\mu h + z^2 z \partial_\mu z \partial^\mu h,$
42	$\omega^4 (\partial_\mu h)^2$	$4(\omega^- \omega^+)^2 (\partial h)^2 + 4\omega^- \omega^+ z^2 (\partial h)^2 + z^4 (\partial h)^2.$

Table 4.5: Operators O_X expressed in the flavor basis (left columns) and in the charge basis (right column).

4.7 Computation of the $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$ amplitude after field redefinitions

In Section 4.5, we computed the scattering amplitude for the process $\omega^+ \omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ at LO, starting from the canonical HEFT Lagrangian of Eq. (4.8). We identified the Feynman diagrams contributing to the process, displayed in Table 4.2, and we obtained the result of Eq. (4.28).

In Section 4.6, we discussed the possibility of simplifying the calculations by performing a non-linear redefinition of the fields ω^a and h . We used the family of transformations in Eq. (4.33), depending on the four initially unconstrained func-

of the outgoing particles; the momentum conservation reads $p_a + p_b = p_c + p_d + p_h$, and all particles on-shell satisfy $p^2 = 0$. Therefore, changing $p_{c,d,h} \rightarrow -p_{c,d,h}$ in Eq. (4.84), and using the invariants s, t, u, s_h, t_h , and u_h defined in Eqs. (4.21) and on-shell relations, we easily recognize that the on-shell matrix element for our process is given by Eq. (4.26), with $A(s, t, u; s_h, t_h, u_h) = A(s, s_h)$ given by

$$A(s, s_h) = \tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}(s + s_h), \quad (4.85)$$

where $\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}$ is given in Eq. (4.75). Then, the amplitude for $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ reads

$$\begin{aligned} i\mathcal{A}(\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh) &= iA(s, s_h) = i\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}(s + s_h) \\ &= -i\frac{s + s_h}{2v^3} \left(a_1 + a_1a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.86)$$

As expected, this is the same result as Eq. (4.28). Note that the amplitude presents an angular dependence, encapsulated in s_h , Eqs. (4.15), (4.21). This is not the case in the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega$, Eq. (4.9) or $\omega\omega \rightarrow hh$, Eq. (4.11), where angular dependence is absent [13]. From now on we define

$$C_{\omega\omega h}(a_1, a_2) \equiv -2v^3\tilde{C}_{4a}^{(1)}(a_1, a_2) = a_1 + a_1a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2}, \quad (4.87)$$

where the subscripts indicate the final state in the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$. In the next section we use Eq. (4.86) to compute the cross section for $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$.

4.8 Phase space and cross section

To begin, let us consider a two-body initial state with four-momenta p_a and p_b , and a n -particle final state with four-momenta $p_i = (E_i, \mathbf{p}_i)$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$), where \mathbf{p}_i denotes the three-momentum and E_i denotes the energy of the i -th particle, satisfying $E_i^2 = \mathbf{p}_i^2 + m_i^2$. The Lorentz-invariant n -body phase-space element is

$$d\Pi_n = (2\pi)^4 \delta^{(4)} \left(q - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \right) \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{d^3\mathbf{p}_i}{(2\pi)^3 2E_i}, \quad (4.88)$$

where $q = p_a + p_b$ is the total four-momentum of the system. We also define $s \equiv q^2$. In this work all external legs are massless: $m_i = 0$ for all i , hence $E_i = |\mathbf{p}_i|$. We are interested in the case $n = 3$, i.e., a three-body final state, with four-momenta $p_X^\mu = (E_X, \mathbf{p}_X)$, where $X \in \{c, d, h\}$. The configuration is in principle described by $3 \times 3 = 9$ variables, i.e., the components of the three-momenta \mathbf{p}_X . However, the delta function in Eq. (4.88) imposes four constraints (energy and momentum conservation). Moreover, in the center-of-mass (c.m.) frame of the initial particles (where $\mathbf{q} \equiv \mathbf{p}_a + \mathbf{p}_b = 0$ and $E_h = \sqrt{s} - E_c - E_d$), the three final momenta are coplanar and we can fix the overall orientation of the system, as global rotations leave the squared matrix element invariant. This eliminates three additional degrees of freedom, leaving two independent variables; for example, we may take E_c and E_d . We next adopt the Dalitz variables [65, 66, 67], defined as

$$\begin{aligned} s_{hc} &\equiv (p_h + p_c)^2 = (q - p_d)^2 = s - 2q \cdot p_d, \\ s_{hd} &\equiv (p_h + p_d)^2 = (q - p_c)^2 = s - 2q \cdot p_c, \\ s_{cd} &\equiv (p_c + p_d)^2 = (q - p_h)^2 = s - 2q \cdot p_h, \end{aligned} \quad (4.89)$$

satisfying the massless three-body relation

$$s_{hc} + s_{hd} + s_{cd} = s. \quad (4.90)$$

Note that $s_{cd} = s_h$, which we defined in Eq. (4.15). The Dalitz variables are related to E_c and E_d in the ab c.m. frame as

$$\begin{aligned} s_{hc} &\stackrel{ab}{=} s - 2\sqrt{s}E_d, \\ s_{hd} &\stackrel{ab}{=} s - 2\sqrt{s}E_c, \\ s_{cd} &= s - s_{hc} - s_{hd} \stackrel{ab}{=} 2\sqrt{s}(E_c + E_d) - s, \end{aligned} \quad (4.91)$$

where we use $\stackrel{ab}{=}$ to indicate equalities that hold in the c.m. frame of particles a and b . We compute $d\Pi_3$ in the ab c.m. frame using (E_d, E_c) , and map it to Dalitz variables (s_{hc}, ds_{hd}) . For massless external legs the Jacobian is constant, so $d\Pi_3$ is uniform on triangular region of the Dalitz plane and zero elsewhere, and $\int d\Pi_3 \propto s$. Consequently, in $d\sigma = \frac{1}{2s} |\mathcal{A}(s, s_{cd})|^2 d\Pi_3$, non-uniformity across the Dalitz plot arises solely from the dependence of the amplitude on s_{cd} (or equivalently s_{hc} and s_{hd}), which carries the angular information: $s_{cd} = 2p_c \cdot p_d \stackrel{ab}{=} 2E_c E_d x_d$. In the limit

where all external legs are massless, the analytical expression for the hypervolume of the full phase space is [68]

$$\mathcal{V}_n = \int d\Pi_n = \frac{1}{2(4\pi)^{2n-3}} \frac{s^{n-2}}{\Gamma(n)\Gamma(n-1)}. \quad (4.92)$$

In particular, for $n = 3$,

$$\mathcal{V}_3 = \int d\Pi_3 = \frac{1}{(4\pi)^3} \frac{s}{4}, \quad (4.93)$$

showing that the volume of the phase space grows linearly with the c.m. energy squared s . As a check of the choice of variables and reference frame, before calculating the cross section, we want to reproduce this result.

We start from Eq. 4.88 with $n = 3$. We work in the ab c.m. frame, where the final three-momenta are coplanar. Without loss of generality, we can choose one of the final momenta to be oriented along the $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ axis, e.g. $\mathbf{p}_c = E_c \hat{\mathbf{z}}$, so that $\theta_c = 0$ and the polar angle $\theta \equiv \theta_d$, and we have the scalar product

$$\mathbf{p}_c \cdot \mathbf{p}_d = E_c E_d \cos \theta_d \equiv E_c E_d x_d, \quad (4.94)$$

where we define $\cos \theta_d \equiv x_d$ (analogously, $\cos \theta_c \equiv x_c$). In Figure 4.2, we show the kinematical configuration that we are adopting. In this case, Eq. (4.88) reads

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_3 = \int d\Pi_3 = (2\pi)^4 \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{p}_h}{(2\pi)^3 2E_h} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{p}_c}{(2\pi)^3 2E_c} \int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{p}_d}{(2\pi)^3 2E_d} \\ \times \delta(q - p_c - p_d - p_h). \end{aligned} \quad (4.95)$$

Now we use

$$\int \frac{d^3 \mathbf{p}_h}{(2\pi)^3 2E_h} = \int \frac{d^4 p_h}{(2\pi)^3} \delta(p_h^2 - m_h^2) \theta(E_h), \quad \theta(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } x < 0. \end{cases}, \quad (4.96)$$

where $\theta(x)$ is the Heaviside step function, and we write the volume elements $d^3 \mathbf{p}_c/E_c$ and $d^3 \mathbf{p}_d/E_d$ in spherical coordinates as $d^3 \mathbf{p}_X/E_X = |\mathbf{p}_X| d|\mathbf{p}_X| d\cos \theta_X d\phi_X$, where $X \in \{c, d\}$ (using the fact that all particles are massless). Substituting in Eq. (4.95), and integrating over $d^4 p_h$ using the four-dimensional delta function,

Figure 4.2: Kinematics of the three-body final state in the ab c.m. frame. The initial momenta are along the \hat{z} axis, with $\mathbf{p}_a = -\mathbf{p}_b$. The final momenta are coplanar, and we choose \mathbf{p}_c to be along the \hat{z} axis, so that $\theta_c = 0$. The polar angle of \mathbf{p}_d is $\theta_d \equiv \theta$, and its azimuthal angle is ϕ_d . The polar and azimuthal angles of \mathbf{p}_h are θ_h and ϕ_h , respectively.

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{V}_3 &= (2\pi)^4 \int_0^\infty \frac{dE_c E_c^2}{(2\pi)^3 2E_c} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi_c \int_{-1}^1 dx_c \\
 &\times \int_0^\infty \frac{dE_d E_d^2}{(2\pi)^3 2E_d} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi_d \int_{-1}^1 dx_d \\
 &\times \int \frac{d^4 p_h}{(2\pi)^3} \delta(p_h^2 - m_h^2) \theta(E_h) \delta(q - p_c - p_d - p_h) \\
 &= 2\pi \int_0^\infty \frac{dE_c E_c}{(2\pi)^3 2} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi_c \int_{-1}^1 dx_c \\
 &\times \int_0^\infty \frac{dE_d E_d}{(2\pi)^3 2} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi_d \int_{-1}^1 dx_d \delta((q - p_c - p_d)^2) \theta(E_h);
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.97}$$

In the last line we use the relations holding in the ab c.m. frame, including Eq. (4.94):

$$\begin{aligned} (q - p_c - p_d)^2 &= s - 2(E_c + E_d) + 2E_c E_d - 2\sqrt{s} E_c E_d x_d, \\ E_h &= \sqrt{s} - E_c - E_d, \end{aligned} \quad (4.98)$$

Integrating over $d\phi_c$, $d\phi_d$, and dx_c in Eq. (4.97) we find

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_3 &= \frac{1}{2(2\pi)^3} \int_0^\infty dE_c E_c \int_0^\infty dE_d E_d \\ &\times \int_{-1}^1 dx_d \delta\left(s - 2\sqrt{s}(E_c + E_d) + 2E_c E_d - 2E_c E_d x_d\right) \theta(\sqrt{s} - E_c - E_d). \end{aligned} \quad (4.99)$$

The delta function in the last line can be rewritten, calling $f(x_d)$ its argument, as

$$\delta(f(x_d)) = \frac{\delta(x_d - x_d^0)}{|f'(x_d^0)|} = \frac{\delta(x_d - x_d^0)}{2E_c E_d}. \quad (4.100)$$

where x_d^0 is the root of the argument of the delta function,

$$x_d^0 = \frac{s - 2\sqrt{s}(E_c + E_d) + 2E_c E_d}{2E_d E_c}. \quad (4.101)$$

and $f'(x_d^0) \equiv (df(x_d)/dx_d)|_{x_d=x_d^0}$. Then, Eq. (4.99) reads

$$\mathcal{V}_3 = \frac{1}{2(2\pi)^3} \int_0^\infty dE_c \int_0^\infty dE_d \int_{-1}^1 dx_d \delta(x - x_d^0) \theta(\sqrt{s} - E_c - E_d). \quad (4.102)$$

Now rewrite the integral in x_d as an integral over the full real axis, using the Heaviside step functions to impose the original integration limits, i.e. $-1 \leq x_d \leq 1$:

$$\int_{-1}^1 dx_d \delta(x_d - x_d^0) g(x_d) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_d \delta(x_d - x_d^0) \theta(-x_d + 1) \theta(x_d + 1) g(x_d), \quad (4.103)$$

where $g(x_d)$ is a generic function of x_d , and θ is the Heaviside step function. Using Eq. (4.103) in Eq. (4.99) and carrying out the integration in x_d , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_3 &= \frac{2}{(4\pi)^3} \int_0^\infty dE_d \int_0^\infty dE_c \theta\left(-x_d^0(E_c, E_d, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \theta\left(x_d^0(E_c, E_d, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \\ &\times \theta(\sqrt{s} - E_c - E_d); \end{aligned} \quad (4.104)$$

here, the two θ 's on x_d^0 enforce $|x_d^0| \leq 1$, i.e. a real scattering angle, while $\theta(\sqrt{s} - E_c - E_d)$ enforces energy conservation. Overall, we have the conditions

$$\begin{cases} E_c + E_d \geq \frac{\sqrt{s}}{2}, \\ E_c + E_d \leq \frac{4E_c E_d}{2\sqrt{s}} + \frac{\sqrt{s}}{2}, \\ E_c + E_d \leq \sqrt{s}, \end{cases} \quad (4.105)$$

which determine a boundary in the $E_d E_c$ plane outside which the phase-space volume is zero, with vertices $(E_c, E_d) = (0, \sqrt{s}/2), (\sqrt{s}/2, 0), (\sqrt{s}/2, \sqrt{s}/2)$. Inside the boundary, the volume density of phase-space is independent of E_c and E_d , and has constant value. From Eq. (4.105), we extract the following upper and lower integration limits for E_c and E_d , which we denote as E_c^\pm and E_d^\pm respectively:

$$\begin{cases} E_c^- = \sqrt{s}/2 - E_d, \\ E_c^+ = \sqrt{s}/2; \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} E_d^- = 0, \\ E_d^+ = \sqrt{s}/2. \end{cases} \quad (4.106)$$

With these considerations, Eq. (4.104) reads

$$\mathcal{V}_3 = \frac{2}{(4\pi)^3} \int_{E_d^-}^{E_d^+} dE_d \int_{E_c^-}^{E_c^+} dE_c. \quad (4.107)$$

Finally, it can be easily seen that the result of Eq. (4.93) for \mathcal{V}_3 is recovered, as expected, once the integration in Eq. (4.107) is carried out. From Eq.4 (4.104) we can read off the phase space element in E_c, E_d :

$$d\Pi_3(E_c, E_d; s) = \frac{2}{(4\pi)^3} dE_d dE_c \theta(-x_d^0(E_c, E_d, \sqrt{s}) + 1) \theta(x_d^0(E_c, E_d, \sqrt{s}) + 1), \quad (4.108)$$

where x_d^0 is given by Eq. (4.100), and it is understood as a function of E_c, E_d , and \sqrt{s} .

In view of the calculation of the cross section, it is useful to write the phase space density in terms of the Dalitz variables, defined in Eq. (4.89). In ab c.m. frame, using Eq. (4.91), we have

$$\begin{cases} E_c = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{s}}(s - s_{hd}), \\ E_d = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{s}}(s - s_{hc}); \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} dE_c = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{s}} ds_{hd}, \\ dE_d = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{s}} ds_{hc}; \end{cases} \quad (4.109)$$

Substituting in Eq. (4.104), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_3 &= \frac{2}{4s(4\pi)^3} \int_0^\infty ds_{hc} \int_0^\infty ds_{hd} \\ &\times \theta\left(-x_d^0(s_{hc}, s_{hd}, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \theta\left(x_d^0(s_{hc}, s_{hd}, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \theta\left(\frac{s_{hc} + s_{hd}}{2\sqrt{s}}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (4.110)$$

where

$$x_d^0(s_{hc}, s_{hd}, \sqrt{s}) = \frac{s_{hc}s_{hd} - s(s - s_{hc} - s_{hd})}{s_{hc}s_{hd} + s(s - s_{hc} - s_{hd})}. \quad (4.111)$$

As before, we note the existence of a region of the phase whose boundaries delimit a region such that the volume density has a constant value inside, while outside it is zero. From Eqs. (4.110) and (4.106), the boundaries imposed by the theta functions are determined by the conditions

$$\begin{cases} 0 \leq s_{hc} + s_{hd} \leq s, \\ s_{hc}s_{hd} \geq 0. \end{cases} \quad (4.112)$$

Carrying out the integration of Eq. (4.110), the result of Eq. (4.93) for \mathcal{V}_3 is recovered once again, as expected.

From Eq. (4.110) we read off the phase space element in the $s_{hc}s_{hd}$ plane

$$\begin{aligned} d\Pi_3(s_{hc}, s_{hd}; s) &= \frac{ds_{hc}ds_{hd}}{128\pi^3s} \\ &\times \theta\left(-x_d^0(s_{hc}, s_{hd}, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \theta\left(x_d^0(s_{hc}, s_{hd}, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \theta\left(\frac{s_{hc} + s_{hd}}{2\sqrt{s}}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (4.113)$$

where x_d^0 is given by Eq. 4.111. In Figure 4.3 it can be seen that the phase space volume density is zero outside a triangular region delimited by the boundaries of Eq. (4.112). When calculating the cross section, this implies that any departure from uniformity must come from the matrix element.

We now focus on the calculation of the cross section for the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$. The differential cross section for a process with two particles in the initial state is given, in any reference frame, by

$$d\sigma = \frac{|\mathcal{A}|^2}{4\sqrt{(p_a \cdot p_b)^2 - m_a^2 m_b^2}} d\Pi_3(q; p_c, p_d, p_h), \quad (4.114)$$

where q is the initial four momentum, and \mathcal{A} is the amplitude of the process, given in Eq. (4.86), and $m_{a,b}$ are the masses of the initial particles. In our case, $m_{a,b} = 0$ and we are working in the ab c.m. frame, so that $p_a \cdot p_b = s/2$. In Dalitz variables s_{hc}, s_{hd} , using Eqs. (4.89), $s_h = s_{hd}$, and Eq. (4.91) (in the ab c.m. frame) the amplitude reads

$$i\mathcal{A}_{\omega^+\omega^-z^2h}(\sqrt{s}; s_{hc}, s_{hd}) = -\frac{i}{2v^3}C_{\omega\omega h}(2s - s_{hc} - s_{hd}), \quad (4.115)$$

where $C_{\omega\omega h} = C_{\omega\omega h}(a_1, a_2)$ is defined in Eq. (4.87), and we adopt the notation $\mathcal{A}(\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh) \equiv \mathcal{A}_{\omega^+\omega^-zzh}(\sqrt{s}; s_{hc}, s_{hd})$ to highlight the dependence on s and the Dalitz variables.

The differential cross section $d\sigma(\sqrt{s}; s_{hc}, s_{hd})$ is given by

$$d\sigma(\sqrt{s}; s_{hc}, s_{hd}) = \frac{C_{\omega\omega h}^2}{4^5\pi^3v^6} \frac{(s - s_{hc} - s_{hd})^2}{s^2} ds_{hc} ds_{hd} \times \theta\left(-x_d^0(s_{hc}, s_{hd}, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \theta\left(x_d^0(s_{hc}, s_{hd}, \sqrt{s}) + 1\right) \theta\left(\frac{s_{hc} + s_{hd}}{2\sqrt{s}}\right). \quad (4.116)$$

As we noted, the constancy of the phase-space volume density over the permitted region in the s_{hc} and s_{hd} phase-space indicates that any departure from uniformity must come from the matrix element dependency on s_{hc} and s_{hd} ; these variables encode the angular dependence of the amplitude. Figure ?? displays the Dalitz plot for the differential cross section in Dalitz variables (Eq. 4.116). The total cross section for the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ is given by

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{2!} \int d\sigma(\sqrt{s}; s_{hc}, s_{hd}), \quad (4.117)$$

where $d\sigma$ is given by Eq. (4.116). The global $1/2!$ symmetry factor accounts for the two indistinguishable z bosons in the final state. Only two numerical integrals are required to evaluate the cross section at any energy \sqrt{s} . The result is

$$\sigma(s; a_1, a_2) = \frac{11s^2}{6144\pi^3v^6} \left(a_1 + a_1a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2}\right)^2. \quad (4.118)$$

The result has been checked with Mathematica and with MaMuPaXS [69]. We display the graphical comparison in Figure 4.4. In the SM the rate for this process is zero in the massless limit: setting $a_1 = 2, a_2 = 1$ nulls the coefficient $C_{\omega\omega h}(a_1, a_2)$

(Eq. (4.87)). In Figure 4.5 we display the cross section as a function of \sqrt{s} in a plot with logarithmic axes for some illustrative values of $C_{\omega\omega h}$. In the next section, we will use the SMEFT expansion for a_1 and a_2 to find approximate numerical value for the cross section in Eq. (4.118) in the SMEFT limit.

4.9 SMEFT expansion

In the previous sections, we calculated the amplitude for the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ in the HEFT framework, and the corresponding cross section. In this section, we aim to map this result into the SMEFT framework. As discussed in Refs. [46, 13], working in a basis where equations of motion/field redefinitions are used and custodial-breaking operators such as O_{HD} (Eq. (3.48)) are neglected (we set $c_{HD} = 0$), only one SMEFT operator controls the deformation of the flare function $\mathcal{F}(h)$ at the orders we consider here in the $1/\Lambda$ expansion, where Λ is the new physics scale.

Concretely, at dimension six (order $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^2)$) this is $O_{H\Box} \equiv (H^\dagger H)\Box(H^\dagger H)$, with coefficient $c_{H\Box}^{(6)}$, while at dimension eight (order $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$) its analogue $(H^\dagger H)^2\Box(H^\dagger H)$ appears with coefficient $c_{H\Box}^{(8)}$. These enter the SMEFT Lagrangian as $\frac{c_{H\Box}^{(6)}}{\Lambda^2}O_{H\Box}$ and $\frac{c_{H\Box}^{(8)}}{\Lambda^4}(H^\dagger H)^2\Box(H^\dagger H)$. The combinations relevant for $\mathcal{F}(h)$ up to order $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$ are [13]

$$d = \frac{2v^2 c_{H\Box}^{(6)}}{\Lambda^2}, \quad \rho = \frac{c_{H\Box}^{(8)}}{2(c_{H\Box}^{(6)})^2}. \quad (4.119)$$

Here $d \sim 1/\Lambda^2$ parametrizes the SMEFT $D = 6$ correction, while ρ encodes the relative size of the $D = 8$ corrections. The numbers below are illustrative only: we will take $\rho = 1$ as benchmark and determine d from the reference value of a_1 (Eq. (4.127)) via the leading relation $d \simeq a_1 - 2$, cf. Eq. (4.120). Rather than fixing a generic $d \sim 0.1$, we use the value implied by a reference a_1 value, without propagating uncertainties or performing any fit.

The explicit expansions of a_1 and a_2 in terms of d and ρ up to order $\mathcal{O}(v^4/\Lambda^4)$

are given below:

$$\frac{a_1}{2} = 1 + \frac{d}{2} + \frac{d^2}{2} \left(\frac{3}{4} + \rho \right) + \mathcal{O}(d^3). \quad (4.120)$$

$$a_2 = 1 + 2d + 3d^2(1 + \rho) + \mathcal{O}(d^3), \quad (4.121)$$

At $\mathcal{O}(1)$ (SM), $a_1 = 2$ and $a_2 = 1$. At $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^2)$, SMEFT predicts

$$a_2 = 2a_1 - 3 + \mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4), \quad (4.122)$$

and dim-8 deformations perturb this relation at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$. From Eqs. (4.120), (4.121) and (4.87), we can read the SMEFT expansion of the combination $C_{\omega\omega h}(a_1, a_2)$ relevant for the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$:

$$C_{\omega\omega h}(a_1, a_2) = 2d^2(1 + \rho) - d^3 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \rho \right) + \mathcal{O}(d^4). \quad (4.123)$$

Since $C_{\omega\omega h}$ starts at order $\mathcal{O}(d^2) \sim \mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$, the process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$ is dimension-8 dominated in SMEFT: the amplitude begins at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$ and the cross section at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^8)$. Using Eq. (4.123) in Eqs. (4.86) and (4.118), we obtain

$$\mathcal{A}(\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h) = -\frac{s + s_h}{v^3} d^2(1 + \rho) + \mathcal{O}(d^3), \quad (4.124)$$

$$\sigma(\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h) = \frac{11s^2}{1536\pi^3 v^6} d^4(1 + \rho)^2 + \mathcal{O}(d^5), \quad (4.125)$$

where s_h is defined in Eq. (4.15). We provide the above results at the lowest non-trivial order in the SMEFT expansion, keeping terms up to $\mathcal{O}(d^2)$ in \mathcal{A} (and thus $\mathcal{O}(d^4)$ in σ). We recall that these results are obtained in the massless limit (equivalence-theorem limit); collider predictions are out of scope. We note that in Ref. [13] the SMEFT expansion of the LO amplitude and cross section for the process $\omega\omega \rightarrow hhh$ shows the same parametric dependence on (d, ρ) as Eqs. (4.124)-(4.125), with different numerical coefficients. In particular, at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^8)$,

$$\frac{\sigma(\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h)}{\sigma(\omega\omega \rightarrow hhh)} = \frac{11}{8}, \quad (4.126)$$

in the massless (equivalence-theorem) limit. Thus the two processes are comparable in SMEFT, with $zz h$ slightly favored. In both cases, predictions are sup-

pressed starting from dim-6 SMEFT. In fact, the amplitude starts at $\mathcal{O}(\sim 1/\Lambda^4)$ (Eq. (4.124) for zzh final state) and σ at $1/\mathcal{O}(\Lambda^8)$ (Eq. (4.125) for zzh final state). This is a generic SMEFT feature for multiboson processes with three final states. In contrast, in HEFT the flare-function coefficients need not satisfy the SMEFT constraints, and this suppression can be lifted.

For an illustrative benchmark (no fit, no uncertainties), we take $d = 0.07$ and $\rho = 1$. Then, $a_1^{(\text{SMEFT})} = 2.08$, $a_2^{(\text{SMEFT})} = 1.17$ (at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$), and $C_{\omega\omega h}^{(\text{SMEFT})} = 0.02$ (at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$).

For visualization, in Figure 4.7 we overlay the curve corresponding to $C_{\omega\omega h} = C_{\omega\omega h}^{(\text{SMEFT})}$ on the same set of curves with arbitrary $C_{\omega\omega h}$ values displayed in Figure 4.5 to illustrate the parametric dependence (benchmarks only; no fit or error propagation). As $C_{\omega\omega h}$ decreases, the cross section decreases and vanishes at the SM value $C_{\omega\omega h} = 0$, as expected.

4.10 Sensitivity study

In the previous sections, we have found that HEFT predicts that the LO scattering amplitude for the massless process $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zzh$ (equivalence-theorem limit), is controlled by the parameters a_1 and a_2 of the flare function $\mathcal{F}(h)$ through the combination $C_{\omega\omega h}(a_1, a_2)$ (Eq. (4.87)). In the SM, $a_1 = 2$ and $a_2 = 1$, which nulls $C_{\omega\omega h}$, forbidding the process in the limit considered. In SMEFT, the process is allowed but with a strong suppression, as it is dimension-8 dominated, with the amplitude starting at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$ and the cross section at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^8)$ (Eqs. (4.124), (4.125)), as discussed in Section 4.9. Experimental uncertainties, however, can allow for larger deviations, that can be accommodated by the HEFT framework, where a_1 and a_2 are independent parameters. Clues of such deviations would emerge, in experiments, as an enhancement of the cross section/interaction rate, i.e., a departure from zero of $C_{\omega\omega h}$.

The aim of this section is to illustrate how improved knowledge on leading order, massless (equivalence-theorem limit) $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$, controlled by the combination $C_{\omega\omega h}$ (Eq.(4.87)), potentially returns improved constrains on the region where deviations of a_1 and a_2 from their SM values can be expected. In particular,

we ask if a reduction of the uncertainty on a_2 could be plausible. The present experimental determinations of a_2 from hh production at the LHC carry wider uncertainties than those on a_1 , which is relatively well known [13]; in Appendix B we present a compilation of the latest measurements.

We stress that this is a toy analysis, with simplified assumptions. Performing an accelerator study is out of the scope of this work: all the numerical values that we mention below are to be intended only as illustrative benchmark reference values. We do not deal with datasets nor perform rigorous statistical analysis.

To conduct our study, we take from Ref. [67] one reference value for a_1 and one for a_2 , and we look at their one-sigma uncertainties to fix plausible values for our toy uncertainties, as we describe below. For a_1 , we take as benchmark the determination from the ATLAS collaboration reported in Ref. [1], while for a_2 we take the determination reported in Ref. [70]:

$$\frac{a_1^{\text{data}}}{2} = 1.035 \pm 0.031, \quad a_2^{\text{data}} = 1.02 \pm 0.23. \quad (4.127)$$

We define a benchmark point using their central values:

$$\text{LHC BM} \equiv (a_1^{(\text{BM})}, a_2^{(\text{BM})}) \equiv (2.07, 1.02) \quad (4.128)$$

We define toy initial uncertainties on a_1 and a_2 after Eq. (4.127):

$$\Delta a_1 \equiv 0.06, \quad \Delta a_2 \equiv 0.23. \quad (4.129)$$

We stress that these choices are not precise experimental determinations, but rather serve to illustrate the impact of different possible future experimental precisions on $C_{\omega\omega h}$.

To find constraints on (a_1, a_2) , we need consider $C_{\omega\omega h}$ in combination with other observables. Combining predictions for different processes is necessary to lift degeneracies in directions corresponding to different parameters. With this purpose, we choose LO massless (equivalence-theorem limit) double Higgs production, $\omega\omega \rightarrow hh$, controlled by C_{hh} , and C_h , which quantifies the deviation of a_1 from its SM value, which are defined as below. We introduce a notation which we will

employ throughout all this section:

$$C_1 \equiv a_1 - 2, \quad (4.130)$$

$$C_2 \equiv a_2 - \left(\frac{a_1}{2}\right)^2, \quad (4.131)$$

$$C_3 \equiv \left(a_1 + a_1 a_2 - \frac{a_1^3}{2}\right). \quad (4.132)$$

Note that C_2 is the coefficient in Eq. (4.12), and C_3 is the $C_{\omega\omega h}$ in Eq.(4.87). We assume the above combinations to be independent among each others, each distributed according to a univariate gaussian distribution (drop the subscript)

$$C \sim \mathcal{N}(C^0; u(C)) \quad (4.133)$$

where C^0 is the central value and $u(C)$ is a 68% Confidence Level (C.L.) uncertainty, so that within this C.L. the observables can fluctuate as $|C - C^0| \leq u(C)$. We assume $C^0 = 0$ for every observable, i.e., the SM prediction. We discuss below how we assign the (toy) uncertainties $u(C)$. We will adopt also the following shorthand notation for the uncertainties: $u(C_i) \equiv u_i$, with $i = 1, 2, 3$. We will use either $u(C_i)$ or u_i . For $u(C_1) \equiv u_1$ and $u(C_2)$, we use naive error propagation using Eqs. (4.128) and (4.129):

$$u_1 \equiv 0.06, \quad u_2 \equiv 0.22. \quad (4.134)$$

Due to the lack of experimental data, we consider two different possibilities to assign the uncertainty $u(C_3)$ to C_3 . We choose the following values:

$$u_{3\text{I}} \equiv 0.5, \quad u_{3\text{II}} \equiv 0.06. \quad (4.135)$$

Here, $u_{3\text{I}}$ is obtained after naive propagation of the assumed errors on a_1 and a_2 (Eq. (4.129)), while $u_{3\text{II}}$ is assigned matching the assumed uncertainty on a_1 (Eq. (4.129)). This is a what-if possibility which serves to foresee what happens if future experimental measurements on this process reach a precision similar to the one on a_1 .

In this way, we can consider two scenarios below and compare them to see how improved experimental uncertainty can impact the analysis. We denote them

S_I and S_{II} , respectively:

$$S_I \equiv \{|C_1| \leq u_1, |C_2| \leq u_2, |C_3| \leq u_3 = u_{3I}\}, \quad (4.136)$$

$$S_{II} \equiv \{|C_1| \leq u_1, |C_2| \leq u_2, |C_3| \leq u_3 = u_{3II}\}. \quad (4.137)$$

Here we have used $C_i^0 = 0$ (SM hypothesis) for every i ($i = 1, 2, 3$). As expected, in both scenarios the intersection of the curves $C_i = 0$ lies exactly at the SM point $(2, 1)$. Deviations from the SM of (a_1, a_2) shift the intersection away from the SM point. Useful notation to going on with the analysis: collect the C_i 's in vectors as

$$\mathbf{C}_{12} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{13} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} C_1 \\ 0 \\ C_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{123} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \end{pmatrix}; \quad (4.138)$$

collect uncertainties in the diagonal matrix (no-correlation ansatz)

$$V \equiv \begin{pmatrix} u_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & u_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & u_3. \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.139)$$

and define

$$V_I \equiv V|_{u_3=u_{3I}}, \quad V_{II} \equiv V|_{u_3=u_{3II}}. \quad (4.140)$$

Going on with our simplified approach, we construct two toy joint log-likelihoods (or "pseudo log-likelihoods") in the space of observables $\chi^2 = -2 \log \mathcal{L}$, where \mathcal{L} is the likelihood function. We consider the following combination of observables:

$$\chi_{12}^2 \equiv \mathbf{C}_{12}^T V^{-1} \mathbf{C}_{12} = \frac{C_1^2}{u_1^2} + \frac{C_2^2}{u_2^2}, \quad (4.141)$$

$$\chi_{13}^2 \equiv \mathbf{C}_{13}^T V^{-1} \mathbf{C}_{13} = \frac{C_1^2}{u_1^2} + \frac{C_3^2}{u_3^2}, \quad (4.142)$$

$$\chi_{123}^2 \equiv \mathbf{C}_{123}^T V^{-1} \mathbf{C}_{123} = \frac{C_1^2}{u_1^2} + \frac{C_2^2}{u_2^2} + \frac{C_3^2}{u_3^2}. \quad (4.143)$$

In view of particularizing for the scenarios S_I and S_{II} , we define

$$\chi_{13I}^2 \equiv \chi_{13}^2|_{V=V_I}, \quad \chi_{13II}^2 \equiv \chi_{13}^2|_{V=V_{II}}, \quad (4.144)$$

$$\chi_{123I}^2 \equiv \chi_{123}^2|_{V=V_I}, \quad \chi_{123II}^2 \equiv \chi_{123}^2|_{V=V_{II}}. \quad (4.145)$$

Now, from Eqs. (4.130), (4.131), (4.132), we can consider the log likelihoods as functions whose domain is the (a_1, a_2) plane, and expand them around the best fit point. This is defined as given by $(a_1, a_2) = (a_{*1}, a_{*2})$ such that $\partial\chi^2/\partial a_1 = 0$ and $\partial\chi^2/\partial a_2 = 0$ simultaneously (nulls the score function). Our case is trivial, as its best fit point is given the SM point itself. This is because we set as central values for C_1, C_2, C_3 the SM value. Repeating the analysis with different values would lead to different values of the best fit points. In our case, the log-likelihoods vanish at the best fit point, i.e. $\bar{\chi}^2 = 0$. Dropping the subscripts, after defining the likelihood around the best fit point, we define $\Delta\chi^2(a_1, a_2) \equiv \chi^2(a_1, a_2) - \bar{\chi}^2$ (for us, $\Delta\chi^2(a_1, a_2)$ is the same as $\chi^2(a_1, a_2)$). The boundary of the 68% C.L. confidence region in the (a_1, a_2) plane is given by ³

$$\Delta\chi^2(a_1, a_2) = 2.30; \quad (4.146)$$

In Figure 4.8, second row, we plot the boundaries of constant likelihood for $\Delta\chi_{12}^2(a_1, a_2)$ and $\Delta\chi_{13}^2(a_1, a_2)$, with scenario I on the right and scenario II on the left.

We follow an analytical approach to extract from χ_{123}^2 (Eq. (4.143)) the variances of a_1, a_2 and ρ as functions of u_1, u_2, u_3 . In particular, we can treat u_1 and u_2 as fixed, and study the impact of a reduction of u_3 on the expected ranges where deviations of a_1 and a_2 from the SM can occur.

We expand $\chi_{123}^2(a_1, a_2)$ around the best fit values (\bar{a}_1, \bar{a}_2) . Up to quadratic

³For two parameters, the standard thresholds γ for the confidence regions boundary $\Delta\chi^2 = \gamma$ are

$$\gamma \in \{2.3 \text{ (68\%)}, \quad 5.99 \text{ (95\%)}, \quad 9.21 \text{ (99\%)}\},$$

according to the cumulative distribution function for the χ^2 distribution with two degrees of freedom: for a given confidence level C.L.,

$$\text{C.L.} = p(\Delta\chi^2) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\frac{\Delta\chi^2}{2}\right\}.$$

order, χ_{123} is approximately a bivariate gaussian distribution in the $a_1 a_2$ parameter space. We adopt the following notation: $\mathbf{a} \equiv (a_1, a_2)^T$, $\bar{\mathbf{a}} \equiv (\bar{a}_1, \bar{a}_2)^T$.

$$\Delta\chi_{123}^2 = (\mathbf{a} - \bar{\mathbf{a}})^T \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{a} - \bar{\mathbf{a}}) + \dots \quad (4.147)$$

where the dots indicate higher order terms, and Σ_i^{-1} is the Fisher information matrix,

$$\Sigma^{-1} \equiv - \left. \frac{\partial^2 \chi_{123}^2}{2 \partial a_1 \partial a_2} \right|_{\mathbf{a}=\bar{\mathbf{a}}}, \quad (4.148)$$

which provides an estimation of the covariance matrix Σ in the $(a_1 a_2)$ space. Its elements return the variances of a_1 and a_2 , and their covariance:

$$\Sigma_{11} = \text{var}^2(a_1), \quad (4.149)$$

$$\Sigma_{22} = \text{var}^2(a_2), \quad (4.150)$$

$$\Sigma_{12} = \text{cov}^2(a_1, a_2) = \rho \text{var}(a_1) \text{var}(a_2), \quad (4.151)$$

where $\text{var}(a_1) \equiv v_1$ ($\text{var}(a_2) \equiv v_2$) is the variance of a_1 (a_2), $\text{cov}^2(a_1, a_2)$ is the covariance between a_1 and a_2 , and $-1 \leq \rho \leq 1$ is the correlation between a_1 and a_2 . We obtain the following analytical expressions:

$$v_1^2(u_3; u_2, u_1) = u_1^2 - \frac{4u_1^4}{4u_1^2 + u_3^2 + 4u_2^2}, \quad (4.152)$$

$$v_2^2(u_3; u_2, u_1) = \frac{u_1^2 (u_3^2 + 16u_2^2) + u_3^2 u_2^2}{4u_1^2 + u_3^2 + 4u_2^2}, \quad (4.153)$$

$$\rho(u_3; u_2, u_1) = \frac{(u_3^2 + 8u_2^2)}{(u_3^2 + 4u_2^2)} \sqrt{\frac{u_1^2 (u_3^2 + 4u_2^2)}{u_1^2 (u_3^2 + 16u_2^2) + u_3^2 u_2^2}}. \quad (4.154)$$

We see that, in this limit, v_1 is given by u_1 , while, given our reference numerical values, v_2 is u_2 -dominated (cf. Eq. (4.134) Table (4.6)). Below we take the limit $u_3 \rightarrow \infty$ of the above Eqs. (4.152), (4.153), (4.154), i.e., when knowledge on C_3 is null. We recover the variances and the correlation coefficient yielded by χ_{12}^2 ,

Table 4.6: Numerical values of the elements of the covariance matrices extracted from χ_{12}^2 , χ_{13}^2 , χ_{123}^2 for the two scenarios considered for u_3 in Eq. (4.135), with u_1 and u_2 fixed to the values in Eq. (4.134).

	χ_{12}^2	$\chi_{13\text{I}}^2$	$\chi_{13\text{II}}^2$	$\chi_{123\text{I}}^2$	$\chi_{123\text{II}}^2$
$\text{var}(a_1)$	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.059	0.058
$\text{var}(a_2)$	0.23	0.28	0.12	0.2	0.12
ρ	0.25	0.43	0.97	0.45	0.97

Eq. (4.141), which we denote $v_{1(12)}^2$, $v_{2(12)}^2$, and $\rho_{(12)}$:

$$v_1^2(u_3; u_2, u_1) \xrightarrow{u_3 \rightarrow \infty} v_{1(12)}^2 = u_1^2, \quad (4.155)$$

$$v_2^2 \xrightarrow{u_3 \rightarrow \infty} v_{2(12)}^2 = u_1^2 + u_2^2, \quad (4.156)$$

$$\rho(u_3; u_2, u_1) \xrightarrow{u_3 \rightarrow \infty} \rho_{(12)} = \frac{u_1}{\sqrt{u_1^2 + u_2^2}}. \quad (4.157)$$

Below we take the limit $u_2 \rightarrow \infty$ of Eqs. (4.152), (4.153), (4.154), i.e., the limit in which the knowledge on . We recover the variances and the correlation coefficient yielded by χ_{13}^2 , Eq. (4.142), which we denote $v_{1(13)}^2$, $v_{2(13)}^2$, and $\rho_{(13)}$:

$$v_1^2(u_3; u_2, u_1) \xrightarrow{u_2 \rightarrow \infty} v_{1(13)}^2 = u_1^2, \quad (4.158)$$

$$v_2^2 \xrightarrow{u_2 \rightarrow \infty} v_{2(13)}^2 = \frac{16u_1^2 + u_3^2}{4}, \quad (4.159)$$

$$\rho(u_3; u_2, u_1) \xrightarrow{u_2 \rightarrow \infty} \rho_{(13)} = \frac{4u_1}{\sqrt{16u_1^2 + u_3^2}}. \quad (4.160)$$

The dependence of the above variances and correlations on u_3 are displayed in Figure 4.9.

In Table 4.6 we give the numerical values of the elements of the covariance matrices extracted from χ_{12}^2 , χ_{13}^2 , χ_{123}^2 for the two scenarios considered for u_3 in Eq. (4.135), with u_1 and u_2 fixed to the values in Eq. (4.134).

In summary, our analysis shows that including the $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$ channel, even under conservative assumptions (scenario S_{II}), can further restrict the allowed (a_1, a_2) parameter space compared to using only C_1 and C_2 . This is evident from the reduction in the variance of a_2 and the shrinking of the confidence region

in the (a_1, a_2) plane, as illustrated in Table 4.6 and Figure 4.8. Thus, improved experimental sensitivity to this process would provide valuable complementary information, helping to break degeneracies and tighten constraints on deviations from the Standard Model in the flare function parameters.

Figure 4.3: 3D surface plot of $\frac{4^5 \pi^3 v^6}{C_{\omega\omega h}^2} d\sigma$ as a function of s_{hc}/s and s_{hd}/s . Darker regions indicate higher values of the differential cross section, while white regions corresponds to vanishing $d\sigma$.

Figure 4.4: Comparison of the cross section $\sigma(\sqrt{s})v^6/C_{\omega h}^2$ in Eq. (4.118) calculated analytically (blue line) and with a Monte Carlo with MaMuPaXS (red crosses). The results show excellent agreement.

Figure 4.5: Cross section of LO $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$ (fb) for illustrative values of $C_{\omega\omega h}$, shown versus c.m. energy \sqrt{s} (in TeV). Both axes are logarithmic. Curves are computed in the massless (equivalence-theorem) limit (Eq. (4.118)).

Figure 4.6: Cross section for $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$ normalized by s^2 , shown in the (a_1, a_2) plane. The color map displays $\sigma(a_1, a_2)/s^2$ in fb/TeV^2 (massless, equivalence-theorem limit; Eq. (4.118)). The SM point is marked with a black diamond. The SMEFT benchmark (BM) obtained from Eqs. 4.120, 4.121 at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$ with $d = 0.07$, $\rho = 1$ is marked with a blue triangle, yielding $a_1^{(\text{SMEFT})} = 2.08$, $a_2^{(\text{SMEFT})} = 1.17$. The red dash-dotted line is the dim-6 SMEFT relation $a_1 = 2a_2 - 3$ (Eq. (4.122)) at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^2)$. Dimension-8 corrections perturb this relation at $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$. Benchmarks only, no fits or uncertainty propagation.

Figure 4.7: Toy comparison of $\omega^+\omega^- \rightarrow zz h$ cross sections (fb) versus the c.m. energy of the system \sqrt{s} . Both axes are logarithmic. The blue dash-dotted line is the SMEFT benchmark obtained by mapping (d, ρ) into $C_{\omega\omega h}$, with $\rho = 1$ and $d = 0.07$ from a reference a_1 (Eq. (??)). The green dash-dotted curve is obtained by mapping the reference central values of (a_1, a_2) (Eqs. (4.127)) into $C_{\omega\omega h}$ via Eq. (4.87). Both are overlaid on curves with illustrative fixed values of $C_{\omega\omega h}$ from Figure 4.5. Here $C_{\omega\omega h}$ is not an independent parameter but the derived combination $C_{\omega\omega h}(a_1, a_2) \simeq 2d^2(1 + \rho) + \mathcal{O}(d^3)$. Values are benchmark only. No fit or error propagation is performed.

Figure 4.8: Top row: curves $C_1(a_1, a_2) = 0$ (grey solid line), $C_2(a_1, a_2) = 0$ (green solid line), and $C_3(a_1, a_2) = 0$ (violet solid line). The intersection of the curves lies on the SM point (black diamond). Bands scan the corresponding toy uncertainties assigned in Eqs. (4.134)-(4.135). Right (left) column: scenario S_I (S_{II}) in Eq. (4.136) (Eq. (4.137)). Second row: 68% C.L. boundaries for χ^2_{12} (blue contour), χ^2_{13I} (χ^2_{13II}) (violet contour on the left (right)). Third row: 68% C.L. boundaries for χ^2_{12} (blue contour), χ^2_{123I} (χ^2_{123II}) (red contour on the left (right)). Benchmark SMEFT dim-8, $\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^4)$ (grey triangle) and LHC BM (Eq. (4.128), grey star) points are plotted for reference. Grey dash-dotted line: SMEFT dim-6 ($\mathcal{O}(1/\Lambda^2)$) linear relation between a_1 and a_2 .

Figure 4.9: Variances and correlation for a_1 , a_2 extracted from χ_{123}^2 (red, see Eqs. (4.152), (4.153), (4.154)), χ_{12}^2 (blue, see Eqs. (4.155), (4.156), (4.157)), χ_{13}^2 (violet, see Eqs. (4.158), (4.159), (4.160)) by gaussian approximation, displayed as functions of u_3 . The horizontal axis is in logarithmic scale. Left figure: variance of a_1 . Central figure: variance of a_2 . Right figure: correlation coefficient ρ . The two vertical dotted lines mark the scenarios u_{3I} and u_{3II} for u_3 , which we discuss in the text.

Figure 4.10: Comparison between the variances and correlation coefficient for a_1 , a_2 , as functions of u_3 (logarithmic scale), before and after including the observable $C_3(a_1, a_2)$ in the joint analysis in gaussian approximation. Blue curves: elements derived from χ_{12}^2 . Red curves: elements derived from χ_{123}^2 . Left figure: relative difference for the variance on a_1 . Central figure: relative difference for the variance on a_2 . Right figure: correlation coefficients. The horizontal axis is in logarithmic scale. Vertical dotted lines mark the scenarios u_{3I} and u_{3II} .

Conclusions

In this work we investigated the longitudinal vector-boson-scattering (VBS) process $W_L^+ W_L^- \rightarrow Z_L Z_L h$ as a probe of the electroweak scalar sector within the Higgs Effective Field Theory (HEFT). We focused on the high-energy window $m_W \ll \sqrt{s} \ll \Lambda$, working at leading order (LO) in the Equivalence Theorem (ET) limit and treating external states as massless, so that the calculation reduces to the Nambu-Goldstone boson (NGB) process $\omega^+ \omega^- \rightarrow zz h$. Transverse gauge interactions and Yukawa couplings were switched off to isolate the scalar dynamics. Within this setup we derived a compact LO amplitude (Eq. (4.86)) and the corresponding cross-section (Eq. (4.118)), both exhibiting the expected high-energy growth characteristic of VBS in the presence of derivative interactions.

A key outcome is that the VBS amplitude is controlled by a definite combination of the flare function coefficients (a_1, a_2) (Eq. (4.87)). At the Standard Model values $(a_1, a_2) = (2, 1)$, the leading high-energy pieces cancel, and the process is suppressed at the ET/massless limit, as expected. We showed that a suitable nonlinear field redefinition (Eq. (4.33)) eliminates derivative $h\omega\omega$ vertices and collapses the tree-level diagrams to a single contact diagram corresponding to the Lagrangian term given in Eq. (4.81), which involves only one derivative operator. This transformation leaves the observables unchanged, in line with S -matrix invariance, and provides a streamlined and fully equivalent route to the same analytic result.

We contrasted the HEFT predictions with the SMEFT benchmark, corresponding to the hypothesis of linear realisation of EWSB. In SMEFT, gauge-invariant operator correlations enforce relations among couplings such that multiboson $2 \rightarrow 3$ amplitudes start at $O(1/\Lambda^4)$ (Eq. (4.124)) and cross sections at $O(1/\Lambda^8)$ (Eq. (4.125)). The process $\omega^+ \omega^- \rightarrow zz h$ results to be more strongly suppressed in SMEFT than in a generic HEFT, where a_1 and a_2 are independent and the

SMEFT correlations need not apply. This difference makes the channel particularly sensitive to deviations captured by HEFT.

To assess the potential impact on (a_1, a_2) , we performed a sensitivity study that combined (i) external information on a_1 with (ii) the established $V_L V_L \rightarrow hh$ channel and (iii) prospective measurements of $V_L V_L \rightarrow V_L V_L h$ under two uncertainty scenarios (Eqs. (4.136), (4.137)). Even under conservative assumptions, adding the $Z_L Z_L h$ final state shrinks the allowed (a_1, a_2) region (Figure 4.8), illustrating that this so-far unexploited channel could play a meaningful role in tightening constraints on the Higgs-vector boson interactions once that realistic measurements become available.

The analysis has been intentionally minimalistic. We did not use experimental data and restricted ourselves to LO in the ET limit; a realistic collider assessment requires restoring finite-mass effects, including transverse polarisations, parton luminosities, acceptances, and backgrounds, as well as next-to-leading-order (NLO) corrections. These refinements, necessary to sharpen predictions and quantify uncertainties, are outside our present scope.

Several natural extensions could follow: (i) compute the NLO corrections to $\omega\omega \rightarrow \omega\omega h$ (and the corresponding $W_L W_L \rightarrow V_L V_L h$), which also constrain additional flare-function coefficients (e.g. a_3); (ii) incorporate the Higgs potential and explore higher-multiplicity final states (e.g. $2 \rightarrow 4$) [57]; and (iii) embed the present amplitude into a realistic analysis framework, complete with detector-level simulations and correlations with other Higgs and VBS observables, enabling a comprehensive global determination of (a_1, a_2) and a sharper comparison between HEFT and SMEFT hypotheses.

General parametrization

Following Ref. [56], we explain how to obtain the general parametrization given in (4.8).

Without loss of generality, it is possible to formally write an arbitrary expansion of the matrix $U(\omega^a)$ as

$$U = X(z) + i\frac{\omega^a \sigma^a}{v} Y(z), \quad z \equiv \frac{\omega^2}{v^2}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $X(z)$ and $Y(z)$ are arbitrary real functions analytic in z . The real component accounts for the terms which are even in ω , and the imaginary component accounts for the odd ones. We must require that the parametrization satisfies unitarity, $U^\dagger U = U U^\dagger = 1$. This constrains $X(z)$ and $Y(z)$ through the relation

$$X(z) = \sqrt{1 - zY^2(z)} = 1 - \frac{z}{2}Y^2(z) - \frac{z^2}{8}Y^4(z) + \dots \quad (\text{A.2})$$

We must require also that the parametrization satisfy Eq. ??; this implies that for $z = 0$, $Y(0) = 1$ and then $X(0) = 1$.

We can formally write $Y(z)$ as an expansion. To do so, we introduce a parameter η , whose particular value depends on the parameterization:

$$Y(z) = 1 + \eta z + \mathcal{O}(z^2); \quad (\text{A.3})$$

consequently, we can write

$$X(z) = 1 - \frac{z}{2} - \eta z^2 - \frac{z^2}{8} + \mathcal{O}(z^3). \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Gathering all together, and neglecting terms of order higher than $\mathcal{O}(\omega^5)$, we find the expression of Eq. (4.5). Note that the parameter η actually contributes

starting from order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^3)$ in the explicit expression of $U(\omega^a)$.

Different values of η correspond to the expansions up to the order $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ of different parametrizations of $U(\hat{\omega})$. Two relevant cases are the *spherical* and the *exponential* parametrizations. The first one is recovered for $\eta = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} U(\hat{\omega}) &= \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2}{v^2}} + i \frac{\hat{\omega}}{v} \\ &= 1 + \frac{i\hat{\omega}}{v} - \frac{\omega^2}{2v^2} - \frac{1}{8} \frac{\omega^4}{v^4} + \mathcal{O}(\hat{\omega}^6). \end{aligned} \tag{A.5}$$

Instead, setting $\eta = -\frac{1}{6}$ returns the expansion of the exponential parametrization,

$$\begin{aligned} U(\hat{\omega}) &= \exp\left\{i \frac{\hat{\omega}}{v}\right\} \\ &= \cos \frac{\omega}{v} + i \frac{\hat{\omega}}{\omega} \sin \frac{\omega}{v} \\ &= 1 + \frac{i\hat{\omega}}{v} - \frac{\omega^2}{2v^2} - \frac{1}{3!} \frac{i\hat{\omega}}{v} \frac{\omega^2}{v^2} - \frac{1}{4!} \frac{\omega^4}{v^4} + \mathcal{O}(\omega^5). \end{aligned} \tag{A.6}$$

Experimental measurements of a_2

During the LHC Run 2, several experimental collaborations have reported measurements of the a_2 parameter in the context of Higgs boson pair production, some showing wide uncertainties, but with an overall reduction of the uncertainty over the year. We summarize the last relevant experimental results for the 95% Confidence Level (C.L.) range at 13 TeV in three tables.

Searches for Higgs boson pair (HH) production in association with vector bosons ($V = W, Z$) yielded wide ranges, Table B.1. Other channels give narrower ranges, spanning approximately two units, showed in Table B.2. Finally, the most stringent results are displayed in Table B.3. More details can be found in Ref. [14]. Additionally, in Table (B.4), we provide some recent results for the values of the coefficient a_1 .

Table B.1: Wide ranges of the a_2 parameter from Higgs boson pair production in ATLAS and CMS measurements.

[range]	Experiment	Channel	Reference
$[-12.2, 13.5]$	CMS	$VHH, HH \rightarrow b\bar{b}b\bar{b}$	[71]
$[-8.6, 10.0]$	ATLAS	$VHH, HH \rightarrow b\bar{b}b\bar{b}$	[72]
$[-2.5, 4.6]$	ATLAS	$b\bar{b}ZZ^*, VVVV, VV\tau\tau, \tau\tau\tau\tau, \gamma\gamma VV, \gamma\gamma\tau\tau$	[73]
$[-1.1, 3.2]$	CMS	$b\bar{b}WW^*$	[73]

Table B.2: Ranges of the a_2 parameter from Higgs boson pair production in ATLAS and CMS measurements.

[range]	Experiment	Channel	Reference
[0.0, 2.1]	ATLAS	$bbbb$	[74]
[0.1, 2.0]	ATLAS	$b\bar{b}b\bar{b}$, $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$, $b\bar{b}\gamma\gamma$	[75]
[-0.5, 2.7]	ATLAS	$b\bar{b}\gamma\gamma$	[76]
[-0.5, 2.7]	ATLAS	$b\bar{b}\tau\tau$	[77]
[-0.17, 2.4]	ATLAS	$b\bar{b}VV^*$, $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$, multilepton	[76]

Table B.3: Most stringent ranges of the a_2 parameter from Higgs boson pair production in ATLAS and CMS measurements. In particular, the fourth entry corresponds to the CMS measurement that excluded, for the first time, the possibility of a vanishing $VVHH$ coupling with a significance of 6.3 standard deviations.

[range]	Experiment	Channel	Reference
[0.6, 1.5]	ATLAS	$bbbb$, $b\bar{b}\gamma\gamma$, $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$, multilepton, $b\bar{b}l\bar{l}$	[70]
[0.55, 1.49]	ATLAS	$b\bar{b}b\bar{b}$	[78]
[0.52, 1.52]	ATLAS	$b\bar{b}b\bar{b}$	[78]
[0.62, 1.41]	CMS	$b\bar{b}b\bar{b}$	[79]
[0.67, 1.38]	CMS	$b\bar{b}b\bar{b}$, $b\bar{b}ZZ^*$, $b\bar{b}\tau\tau$, $b\bar{b}\gamma\gamma$, multilepton	[80]

Table B.4: Reference values for a_1 , in literature referred to as $a = a_1/2 \equiv k_V$.

k_V	Experiment	Year	Citation
1.035 ± 0.031	ATLAS	2022	[1]
1.014 ± 0.029	CMS	2022	[80]
1.036 ± 0.038	CMS	2025	[81, 82]

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